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**SELF-EFFICACY AND CAREGIVER BURDEN AMONG INFORMAL CAREGIVERS
OF TERMINALLY ILL PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN
THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES**

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Acceptance Page

This Special Project titled: “**SELF-EFFICACY AND CAREGIVER BURDEN AMONG INFORMAL CAREGIVERS OF TERMINALLY ILL PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Abstract

Informal caregivers have been recognized as the backbone and strength of long-term care because of their involvement in care. However, they often are not prepared for caregiving role since illnesses are unanticipated. On top of that, most healthcare delivery models and professionals focus primarily on individual patients' care, and the support given to caregivers is by providing how to manage the practical demands of caregiving. Moreover, they do not adequately engage, educate, or support informal caregivers to improve their well-being. Being not prepared physically and emotionally and lacking the skills threatens their self-efficacy in caring and makes them unprotected from caregiver burden, which can lead informal caregivers to be the next vulnerable population after their care recipients.

The study aimed to determine the relationship between self-efficacy and caregiver burden among informal caregivers of terminally ill patients in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). This study utilized descriptive- correlational design. The samples of this study were informal caregivers of terminally ill patients, particularly in the Oncology Department of Tawam Hospital, UAE.

The result of the study showed that the two main variables, overall *Self-efficacy in caregiving* and overall *Caregiver Burden*, have a very weak negative relationship, $r_s(58) = -.12$, $p = .42$, $N = 60$ at $\alpha = .05$, however, the relationship was not statistically significant. The overall level of self-efficacy was High Self-efficacy in managing caregiving demands (M- 28.08; SD- 1.71). Among the sub-dimensions of self-efficacy were High Self-efficacy in Caring for Care Recipient (M- 8.21; SD- 1.04) and least in Caring for Oneself (M- 5.79; SD- 2.34). On the other hand, the overall level of caregiver burden was at a High Risk level for burnout or, in other words, severe level (M-36.67; SD- 0.22). Among the four burden domains, Time Dependence was the highest form

of burden experienced (M-2.84, SD- 0.98), and the least was Emotional Burden (M- 0.11; SD 0.46). Among the demographics and other work-related profiles, the study shows that caregiver burden was not related to demographics and other work-related profiles; on the other hand, Self-Efficacy and Caregiving Duration ($r_s=0.301$; $p=0.19$) were significantly related, and the rest were not significant. In this study, care recipients were independent in transferring (M- 2.28) and mobilizing (M-2.18) and severely dependent in terms of grooming (M- 1.13).

Although the main variables were unrelated, this study provided us with the degree of self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden experienced and predictors that affect the self-efficacy and burden of informal caregivers in UAE. This study recommends further research on a larger scale and test interventions in improving self-efficacy and decreasing the burden.

CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM

Introduction

Informal caregivers are family caregivers recognized as the backbone of long-term care. They provide intimate and personalized care in physical, psychological, financial, and emotional aspects; they also play a significant role in patient advocacy by coordinating the care and deciding on behalf of the patient; and they also support the decisions of competent individuals (Hampton & Newcomb, 2018). Because of this role, informal caregivers are expected to experience high stress levels, especially with the changing care demands. The care-related difficulties are the hallmark of chronic stress that overwhelms over time, and these experiences become a health hazard to caregivers, known as the caregiver burden. It has multiple responses to one's physical, emotional, social, psychological, and financial stress connected to caregiving experiences (Hiseman & Fackrell, 2017). The U.S. statistics (2020) show that 70% of caregivers who have secular jobs suffer work-related difficulties due to dual roles (National Alliance for Caregiving (NAC), 2020). Many of them felt that they have no alternative, and have no choice about taking caregiving responsibilities (49%); difficulty coordinating care increased by 7%; family caregivers who reported that their health was poor to fair increased by 4%; and 23% of Americans said caregiving has made their health worse (NAC US, 2020). Because of these experiences, some studies have already considered the caregiving role as one of the risk factors for mortality (Havyer et al., 2016; Hiseman & Fackrell, 2017; Litzelman et al., 2016; Roth et al., 2015). Despite the adverse effects of caregiving, several studies showed that self-efficacy and caregiver burden were related, and self-efficacy can attenuate the

adverse effects of caregiving (Sultan et al., 2020; Durante, 2019; Hampton & Newcomb, 2018; Yildiz et al., 2017; Unver et al., 2016). Self-efficacy is the belief in the self of being able to accomplish the task, and it positively impacts life choices and well-being (Bandura, 1994). In other words, it is their belief in their potential for success in accomplishing tasks or overcoming possible difficulties. Most informal caregivers are ill-prepared for their roles; they struggle with internal resources such as information-gathering, skills for caring, and coping behaviors for their new roles; and external resources such as budget and funds, aid from other family member, and formal care to adapt to caregiving situations, especially the fact that terminal illness can change its trajectory anytime which demands more time, care and stress (Roth et al., 2015). Being ill-prepared for the role contributes negatively to carers' confidence or self-efficacy in performing the care responsibility, which can significantly affect the quality of care provided to care recipients (Harrison, 2019; Havyer et al., 2016; Litzelman et al., 2016). Despite these negative consequences that come with caregiving, some studies show that improving a strong sense of self-efficacy in caregivers positively influences life choices, motivation, quality of functioning, resiliency to adversity, and vulnerability to stress and depression (Bandura, 1994). These positive impacts of self-efficacy are significantly reflected in their decision-making capabilities, executing care and managing symptoms of care recipients, and tackling stress in caregiving. (Harrison, 2019; Havyer et al, 2016; Litzelman et al, 2016; Yildiz et al, 2017).

Similar studies were conducted in another part of the world; Unver et al. (2016) and Yildiz et al. (2017) studied the relationship between self-efficacy and caregiver burden and were both conducted in Turkey. Yildiz et al. (2016) studied the caregiver burden and self-efficacy for informal caregivers of cancer patients, and the results

show that self-efficacy and burden were negatively related. Yildiz et al. (2016) also included the study's differences in socio-demographics and their relation to burden and self-efficacy. However, the study did not include the level of activities of the patients, which is imperative in measuring burden. According to Unver et al. (2016), the study limitation was relying on student nurses during the data collection and were not accompanied by the researcher.

On the other hand, Unver et al. (2017) did the same variable but on older adults. Unver et al. (2017) study included the characteristics of both caregiver and patient, self-efficacy and burden, and functional dependence of patients. The limitation of Unver et al. (2017) studies is that it needed to be longitudinal. Both studies needed to have diverse samples in their studies.

This study of the relationship between self-efficacy and the burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill patients will be the first in the UAE. A prior study of informal caregivers was about quality of life, conducted in 2019 by Araki. The study included the level of burden as one of the questionnaire dimensions. However, the burden result was minimal. The study of Araki suggested including the duration of caregiving and ADL of patients in future studies. Moreover, this study included Emiratis and a multinational population with expected socioeconomic benefits, which differ from Emiratis.

In UAE, cancer is the most terminal disease, showing that approximately 4,500 new cancer cases are reported yearly (UAE portal 2021; WHO, 2018). Due to the continuous increase of new cases, this simultaneously reflected the increasing demand for informal caregivers. The risk that the informal caregiver role poses, such as mortality risk, suicide risk, and vulnerability to being the next patient after the care recipient, is the motivation of this study. Examining how this unique role influences the

lives and overall well-being of these informal caregivers in the UAE is imperative. This study is interested in how self-efficacy and caregiver burden are presented in the UAE. The population is represented by a diverse culture of 87.9% expatriates and 12.1% locals (Dubai Online, 2021). Since several studies point to self-efficacy as a protective barrier to burden, this study was motivated to describe the relationship between self-efficacy and burden.

This research aims to identify the relationship between overall self-efficacy in caregiving and overall caregiver burden of caregivers in the UAE. It determines the level and specific dimensions of self-efficacy in caregiving, caregiver burden to work on, and demographic profiles, which can be used to identify risk populations. Highlighting the self-efficacy in caregiving strengths and weaknesses gives a pathway to nurses and administration to constructively intervene by adapting or designing strategies to increase self-efficacy in caring and decrease caregiver burden. This prevents informal caregivers from becoming the second patient after their care recipients and decreases the readmission frequency of care recipients. Eventually, these benefits will fall into having a healthy community and decreasing national healthcare expenses. Given the current circumstances that our health care system is facing, without the support of informal caregivers, individual personal care is impossible for most terminally ill care recipients

Aim of the Study

The study aims to determine the relationship between overall self-efficacy and the overall burden of informal caregivers of the terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates. This provides a bigger picture of the well-being of this unique role, thus opening a pathway for further research. This study describes the relationship of these

two main variables to demographic profile and other work-related variables and activity of daily living (ADL) of care recipients.

Statement of the Problem

Informal caregivers are considered as the backbone and strength of long-term care. However, they often must prepare for this role since illnesses are unanticipated. Moreover, although their involvement has been recognized, most healthcare delivery models focus primarily on individual patients. Most professionals prepare informal caregivers by providing support in managing the practical demands in caregiving. However, they do not adequately engage, educate, or support informal caregivers to improve or develop their self-efficacy in caring. Thus, leaving them unprotected from caregiver burden and leading them to the next vulnerable population after their care recipients. Due to its vulnerability to caregiver burden, the informal caregiver role is currently considered a risk for mortality. It is believed that self-efficacy or belief in their capability to accomplish tasks can attenuate caregiver burden. Thus, this study determines the relationship between self-efficacy and the burden of informal caregivers of terminally -ill persons in tertiary hospitals in the UAE.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

The general objective of this study is to determine the relationship between overall caregiver self-efficacy in caregiving and the overall caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill persons in tertiary hospitals in the United Arab Emirates.

Specific Objectives

1. To describe the sociodemographic and work-related profile of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates.
2. To describe the self-efficacy in caregiving of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 2.1 Caring for oneself self-efficacy
 - 2.2 Managing medical information self-efficacy
 - 2.3 Caring for care recipient self-efficacy
 - 2.4 Managing complex interactions and emotions self-efficacy
3. To describe the caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 3.1 Time Dependence or Objective Burden
 - 3.2 Developmental Burden
 - 3.3 Emotional Burden
 - 3.4 Physical Burden
 - 3.5 Social Burden
4. To describe the level of Activity of Daily Living (ADL) independence of care recipients of caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates.
5. To determine the relationship between overall caregiver self-efficacy in caregiving and overall caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates
6. To determine the relationship of overall self-efficacy in caregiving of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of their sociodemographic profiles:
 - 6.1 Age

- 6.2 Sex
 - 6.3 Marital status
 - 6.4 Educational Degree
 - 6.5 Race
 - 6.6 Employment Status
 - 6.7 Kinship
 - 6.8 Caregiving Duration
7. To determine the relationship of overall caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of their sociodemographic profiles:
- 7.1 Age
 - 7.2 Sex
 - 7.3 Marital status
 - 7.4 Educational Degree
 - 7.5 Race
 - 7.6 Employment Status
 - 7.7 Kinship
 - 7.8 Caregiving Duration
8. To determine the relationship between overall self-efficacy and care recipient ADL independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates
9. To determine the relationship between overall caregiver burden and care recipient ADL independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates

Significance of the Study

Examining how this unique role influences informal caregivers' lives and overall well-being is essential. The study's findings are significant to nurses, care recipients, informal caregivers, nursing administration, and nursing research.

To Nurses

The study findings bring awareness to nurses of the current situation of informal caregivers' self-efficacy in caregiving, their caregiver burden, and its possible impact on informal caregivers, patients, and the healthcare system if not addressed. Nurses can help informal caregivers realize the value of their well-being while caring for their care recipients. The study results empower nurses to design constructive interventions for the specific needs of informal caregivers. This study can empower nurses to catalyse change by leading another branch of research, interventional programs, support groups and utilizing available resources addressing self-efficacy and caregiver burden.

To Informal Caregivers

The significance of the study to informal caregivers is to bring awareness of the factors that can affect their well-being and help them realize the value of their health as they render service of care. The study result discusses that their role predisposes them to caregiver burden and lower self-efficacy in caring. This study describes which self-efficacy dimensions are their strength and weaknesses and specific caregiver burden dimensions. In this regard, as awareness and interventions are established for informal caregivers, further benefits such as less or more controlled stress, anxiety,

depression, irritability, psychological and physical issues, less risk for mortality, and a more satisfying relationship with the care recipient can be attained.

To Care Recipients

The result of the study can indirectly describe the performance of informal caregivers in the quality of care they provide for their care recipient. The more confident an informal caregiver is in performing their task, the better-quality care outcomes and hospital readmission prevention. The more confident an informal caregiver is in caring for self and care recipient, the lesser burden, irritability, and stress, and the better the caregiver and patient relationship.

To Administration

This study allows healthcare administration and agencies to consider the importance of informal caregivers' health and well-being. This study facilitates attention from administration to give importance to informal caregivers by strengthening the informal caregivers' self-efficacy and lessening the burden. This can be done by facilitating informal caregiver programs, providing or creating support groups, providing education by utilizing the data that this study provides, and using Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory as a foundation in designs and plans in order to prevent needless health problems in this group of population as they give service of care to their family. By addressing the self-efficacy and caregiver burden of informal caregivers, the administration will aid the healthcare system of the UAE by decreasing the usage of the national health budget.

To Nursing Research

This study stimulates other researchers to investigate informal caregivers' well-being further. This study is a basis for further studies to establish evidence-based practice, standards, and research utilization.

Scope and Limitation

This study assessed the self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden among informal caregivers of terminally ill patients in the United Arab Emirates. The samples were informal caregivers of terminally ill patients in the Oncology Department of Tawam Hospital. The study includes informal caregivers from the inpatient department and excludes the Outpatient department. Informal caregivers of terminally ill patients were included regardless of their tenure of care. The study utilized a *cross-sectional design*, which commenced in the last week of December to January 2022. Additionally, since the demand for care is ever-changing, this study cannot determine the changes in self-efficacy in caring and the caregiver burden of the participants in the UAE. The respondents are limited to informal caregivers caring for cancer patients in one hospital.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Literature

This chapter discusses the literature that supports the research problem involving self-efficacy and caregiver burden. This includes definitions, studies that support caregiver self-efficacy, studies of caregiver burden, and studies that discuss the relationship between variables such as demographic profile and other work-related variables and A.D.L. This literature enlightens the study of factors that affect self-efficacy and caregiver burden and the tools used to assess their levels.

The databases used for the literature review were ProQuest, Deepdye, Science Direct, Pubmed, EBSCO, and Taylor & Francis. The keywords used for the search of literature were *Self-Efficacy* and *Caregiver Burden*.

Self-Efficacy

According to Bandura (1982, p. 122), “*self-efficacy is concerned with judgments of how well one can execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situations.*” In other words, self-efficacy is the person’s belief that one has the power to produce an outcome by completing a given task related to that competency (Bandura, 1982). Self-efficacy is necessary to help determine if the coping mechanism or action will be initiated, how much effort will be used on an activity, and how resilient a person can be in adverse situations (Bandura, 1977). Self-efficacy in caregiving refers to the belief in caring for the patient’s needs (Hampton & Newcomb, 2018). A strong sense of self-efficacy or belief positively impacts life choices, motivation, quality of functioning, resilience to adversity, and vulnerability to stress and

depression (Bandura, 1994). These positive impacts of self-efficacy or confidence greatly reflect in decision-making, executing care, and managing symptoms of care recipients. On the other hand, people with low self-efficacy tend to avoid challenges, discontinue complex tasks, and be at risk for more depression and stress (Bandura, 1994), resulting in less satisfaction with life and poor quality of care (Harrison, 2019; Havyer et al., 2016; Litzelman et al., 2016;).

Studies on Self-efficacy

It is believed that the higher the level of self-efficacy, the greater the success in completing a task or goal. Self-efficacy varies depending on task demand and the characteristics of the situation. In caregiving, self-efficacy is the caregiver's belief in his or her capability to accomplish the demands of caregiving (Hampton & Newcomb, 2018). In the study of Hampton and Newcomb, 2018, they used the self-efficacy questionnaire, Caregiver Index (CGI) in which identified different sub-types of caregiver self-efficacy, they are self-efficacy in caregiver self-care, controlling upsetting thoughts in caregiving, caregiver coping, managing care recipients' disruptive behaviors, and managing care recipients' symptoms. There has been large amount of research on caregiver self-efficacy, consistently noting its importance in the overall outcomes of the caregiving experience (Kanwal et al., 2020; Hampton & Newcomb, 2018; Ellis et al., 2017; Leung et al., 2017).

The study of Hampton and Newcomb (2018) of caregivers in providing end-of-life care, proved that self-efficacy and stress were associated. The study showed that caregivers have the highest confidence in caring for their care recipient and the lowest level of confidence in caring for themselves, and almost half of the participants have a high level of perceived stress (Hampton & Newcomb, 2018). In this study, the

Caregiver Inventory subscale was explored about perceived stress. As a result, there was significant relationship between self-efficacy of caring for self and perceived stress. Overall, the study findings of Hampton and Newcomb (2018), indicated that caregivers with greater confidence in managing the demands of caregiving have lower stress levels, and caregivers with greater confidence in caring for themselves, specifically, have lower levels of perceived stress. The study highlighted the importance of caregivers' self-care needs and the potential of self-efficacy as a buffer to stress. The study of Hampton and Newcomb (2018) also examined and identified which dimension of self-efficacy-needs and interventions using the Caregiver Inventory. Importantly, in examining self-efficacy, according to Scicolone's (2018) study, it is imperative to consider the types of caregiving and patient's condition because it can end up with false positives or incongruent results. For instance, according to Scicolone (2018), relationship self-efficacy is lower to caregiver with patient with substantial cognitive impairment than those without, because they cannot recall their caregiver's name or relationship. Similarly, instrumental self-efficacy is much lower to caregiver with patients with more physical ailments than those with patients with cognitive impairment, thus, considering the type of caregiving and patients' condition is necessary.

Similar to Hampton and Newcomb's (2018) study result was the study of Steffen et al. (2018). Steffen et al. (2018) conducted a cross-national review of the Revised Scale for Caregiving Self-Efficacy (RSCSE), and as a result of their review, studies conducted in Hong Kong and in United States shows that *self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts* is positively associated with better health behaviors, health-related quality of life, and less use of psychotropic drugs. On the other hand, the research conducted in Canada, Lebanon, Italy, Spain, Taiwan, and the United States found that

self-efficacy directly affects mental health outcomes (Steffen et al., 2018). Overall, their review to different studies across different countries showed that *self-efficacy in managing disruptive behavior* and *self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts* can buffer the effect of stressors on distress (burden, depression, and anxiety symptoms).

Another critical study on self-efficacy was conducted by Tan et. Al (2021) about factors associated with caregiving self-efficacy among informal caregivers with dementia in Singapore. This study utilized the Revised Scale for Caregiving Self-Efficacy (R.S.C.S.E.), which has a 3-factor model: self-efficacy in obtaining respite (SE-OR); self-efficacy in responding to disruptive behaviors (SE-RDB); and self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts (SE-CUT). This study has five results, first it showed that outlook on life was positively associated with 3-factors (SE-OR, SE-RDB, SE-CUT). Second, social support was positively associated with self-efficacy in obtaining respite and controlling upsetting thoughts. Third, the study also showed that outlook on life and average weekly caregiving hours were factors that were positively correlated to self-efficacy in responding to disruptive behaviors (SE-RDB). Fourth, caregivers living with care recipients had significantly lower scores on SE-RDB. Lastly, age, social support, and outlook on life were positively correlated to self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts (SE-CUT), while Self-affirmation was negatively correlated to SE-CUT.

As Tan et al. (2021) found in their study, social support was associated with SE-controlling upsetting thoughts, with that being said, with more excellent social support, the caregiver has more options to find someone to entrust the care responsibility when they need breaks from caring or in need for more respite. Social support also enhances resilience to stress, as it helps individuals evaluate their stressful situation and emotional reaction to caregiving (Tan, et al., 2021). Thus,

negative thoughts such as how life was better before they became caregiver or how unfair to them to take the role, can be attenuated by social support (Tan, et al., 2021). This is supported by the Steffen et al. (2018) study in which Efficacy in Controlling Upsetting Thoughts has better health behaviors and health-related quality of life. In addition, Leung et al. (2017) also mentioned that family support has positive effect on the quality of life of patient through caregiving self-efficacy. In contrast, Leung et al (2017) also added that friend support had a significant positive direct effect on caregiver burden but minimal effect on a patient's quality of life.

Part of self-efficacy is about death and end-of-life care, with the positive outcome of more excellent family and social support to SE-controlling upsetting thoughts (Tan et al., 2021; Steffen et al., 2018; and Leung et al., 2017), and its relation to health behaviors and health-related quality of life, this might help family-caregivers to talk about death and end of life care more openly. The study conducted by Bergeholtz et al. 2020, revealed that talking about end-of-life differed widely. End-of-life conversation was a personal affair, ranging from not wanting to talk about death to being ready to plan burial, and/ or expecting doctors or nurses to open a conversation about end-of-life (Bergeholtz et al., 2020). As mentioned earlier by Tan et al., (2021), having family or social support enhances resilience and it may help attenuate the caregiver's negative thoughts, thus it may encourage them to talk more openly about the worst possible things to come.

In connection to social support, it is noted that domestic help is associated with a decreased amount of caregiving to care recipient, and decreased caregiver's adverse reaction to caregiving duties (Tan et al., 2021). Interestingly, Tan's et al., (2021) study found that having a domestic helper was not positively associated with self-efficacy in obtaining respite or help. According to Tan et al., (2021), this could be

because the questionnaire was structured in “how confident in asking for help from family or friends,” in which they do not consider their domestic a friend or family. On the contrary, according to the author, having a domestic helper was positively correlated with Self-efficacy in responding to disruptive behaviors (SE-RDB); the author surmised that a domestic helper was there to assist the caregiver in dealing with the care recipient’s behavioral issues.

Another result of the Tan et al. (2021) study was that caregivers with higher knowledge were associated with better Self-efficacy in Disruptive behavior (SE-RDB). Higher knowledge has fewer misconceptions about the disease condition and can efficiently manage the care recipient’s disruptive behavior, leading to higher SE-RDB. This is supported by Hendrix et al. (2016) and Havyer et al. (2017) study, in which gaining knowledge through training improves self-efficacy.

Another Tan et al. (2021) study result was that the higher average weekly caregiving hours were positively associated with Self-efficacy in Disruptive behavior (SE-RDB), while living with care recipients was negatively associated with SE-RDB. When caregivers care recipient more than average hours, they gain more experience and knowledge in dealing with patients with disruptive behavior, thus gaining more expertise and more self-efficacy. As Havyer et al. (2016) and Hendrix et al. (2016) mentioned in their study, routine training and self-efficacy were associated. Lack of training is associated with low self-efficacy, and training can improve caregiver self-efficacy. Therefore, living with the patient means more exposure to the patient’s care needs, more skill exposure, and higher self-efficacy. However, this is opposite from the study result of Tan et al. (2021), in which living with care recipients was negatively associated with SE-RDB.

The study of Tan et al. (2021) showed that outlook-on-life was positively associated with self-efficacy in obtaining respite, disruptive behaviors, and controlling upsetting thoughts. Tan et al., (2021), explained that caregivers with higher self-efficacy are more equipped and capable of recognizing positive sense of caregiving even in unfavorable circumstances. This is supported by the study result of Steffen et al. (2018), in which *Efficacy in Controlling Upsetting Thoughts* has better health behaviors and health-related quality of life.

Another result from the Tan et al. (2021) study was the positive association between age and S.E.- Control of Upsetting Thoughts (SE-CUT). As Tan et al. (2021) explained this could be due to the “positivity effect” phenomenon, an age-related tendency by which older people remember and give attention to more positive than negative stimuli. Thus, older caregivers can control upsetting thoughts about caregiving than younger caregivers. Tan et al. (2021) also argued that the relationship between age and SE-CUT might be due to the stage of life of a caregiver being young and at the threshold of career and taking up the responsibility of caregiver having more sacrifices to deal with than one who is retired.

Several studies attempted to improve self-efficacy by conducting interventional studies. Hendrix et al. (2016) conducted an interventional study to improve self-efficacy; they examined the effect of enhanced informal caregiver training (Enhanced-CT) protocol on cancer symptoms and caregiver stress management to caregivers of hospitalized cancer patients. The result of this study indicates that caregiver with training had more significant increase in caregiving self-efficacy for managing cancer symptoms and stress, and preparation in caregiving. However, the result was short-term. Most probably, the short-term improvement was related to a single intervention and assessment, and the changing needs of caregivers after hospital discharge

(Hendrix et al. (2016). Similarly, the study of Havyer et al. (2017) on the effects of routine training on informal caregivers of colorectal cancer patients' self-efficacy showed a consistent and significant association between training and self-efficacy. Those caregivers with low self-efficacy were higher than those who perceived inadequate training. These studies support the value of training to improve self-efficacy.

It is important to note that socio-demographic profiles serve as determinants of self-efficacy. Some studies were not medically related; however, it is imperative to include them in this review.

Self-efficacy and Race. In the U.S.A. the general self-efficacy and mortality are connected to racial differences between blacks and whites. Assari (2017) study showed that Blacks had lower general self-efficacy than Whites, which was associated with socio-demographic factors: Blacks were reported to have lower educational literacy, low wages, and more stress, more health conditions, obesity, and depressive symptoms than Whites (Assari, 2017).

Self-efficacy and family income, school, grades, and academic year. Seyedi-Andi et al. (2019) conducted study on medical student in Iran in connection to their self-efficacy and sociodemographic profile. Their study shows a significant relationship between self-efficacy, family income, kind of school, student grades, and academic year. According Seyedi-Andi et al. (2019), self-efficacy was higher in students whose family has adequate income, students in medical and dental schools, and students with academic grades > 16. Their study also found that female students had higher self-efficacy than males. However, this difference was not statistically significant, including other variables such as marital status and birthplace (native or non-native).

Self-efficacy and Gender. Yu and Deng (2022) examined gender differences in e-learners' self-efficacy. The study result shows no gender differences in e-learning except in a few countries: females significantly outperform males in Spain and the U.K; females have more positive attitudes towards e-learning than males in Austria, India, Chile, and Spain; and in the U.S.A., females present significantly higher self-efficacy than males. It was concluded by Yu and Deng (2022) that the popularity of technology among males and females may have played an essential role in closing the gap between gender differences in e-learning outcomes.

Self-efficacy and Employment. Wade-Bohleber et al. (2020) studied the association of social and psychological resources of employed and unemployed adolescents, exploring the association of social and family support, self-esteem, and self-efficacy with different dimensions of chronic stress. Their study shows that unemployment status was associated with family support, self-esteem, and self-efficacy. The association between higher self-esteem and efficacy and lower stress levels was more evident in employed youth than in unemployed youth across several dimensions of stress (Wade-Bohleber et al.,2020).

The existing literature suggests that self-efficacy or confidence in oneself can produce positive outcomes regardless of the discipline, whether in healthcare, academia, the military, or applied linguistics. The healthcare-related literature on self-efficacy claims that it can decrease or attenuate the effects of stress and burden in caregiving, especially when they have greater confidence in managing the demands of caregiving. Aside from that, self-efficacy can be improved by addressing skill development and environmental change (Durante, 2019; Hendrix et al., 2016). There are different types of self-efficacy, and the intensity of it is somehow affected by the socio-demographic profile of caregivers and the environment.

Caregiver Burden

Caregiver burden is the strain or load a caregiver bear for caring for a family member who is ill, disabled, or elderly. Caregiver burden has multiple responses to one's physical, emotional, social, psychological, and financial stressors connected to the caregiving experience (Hiseman & Fackrell, 2017). According to the National Alliance for caregiving in the U.S. (2020), 70% of caregivers with secular jobs suffer work-related difficulties due to their dual roles, and many feel they have no choice about taking on caregiving responsibilities (49%). Thus, informal caregivers are expected to experience high stress levels, especially when they struggle with information-gathering, skills needed for caring, coping behaviors, financial resources, help from another family, and formal care resources to adapt to caregiving situations.

Caregivers often encounter multiple stressful events and extended unrelenting stress. This chronic stressful experience can overwhelm the caregivers and become a health hazard. The National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion (2019) stated that informal caregiving has been associated with higher levels of depression and anxiety, higher use of psychoactive drugs, worse reported physical health, compromised immune function, and increased risk of early death. These are unneeded side effects of caring. Increased caregiver burden and mental health symptoms have been associated with low self-efficacy, which, in turn, can affect the quality of care provided to a disabled family member (Yildiz et al., 2017; Havyer et al., 2016; Litzelman et al., 2016).

Relationship Between Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden and other related Factors

Several studies show that there is relationship between self-efficacy and caregiver burden. Self-efficacy is interchangeably used with confidence, and on the other hand, caregiver burden was assessed in many different contexts; for instance, some researchers used stress, well-being, physical suffering, distress, quality of life, and depression and anxiety as critical variables to measure and describe caregiver burden. In this section, these words are used in conjunction with self-efficacy and caregiver burden (Deyhoul et al., 2020; Sultan et al., 2020; Durante, 2019; Zoladi et al., 2019; Araki, 2019; Hampton & Newcomb, 2018; Palacio et al., 2018; Yildiz et al., 2017; Ellis et al., 2017; Litzelman et al., 2016; Unver et al., 2016)

Caregiver's Self-efficacy, Burden, and Quality of Life

Most of the studies proved that self-efficacy is associated with caregiver burden. Yildiz et al., 2017, studied the level of self-efficacy and burden for informal caregivers for patients with cancer in Turkey. As a result, caregiver burden and self-efficacy have a negative relationship. This means that as the burden worsens, self-efficacy also lowers. Similarly, Ellis et al. (2017) examined the influence of patients' and caregivers' symptoms of distress on their "threat appraisal" and "self-efficacy to cope" with cancer. As a result, there was a direct association of more patient and caregiver symptoms of distress to their own lower self-efficacy and more threatening appraisal. In other words, the more patient symptoms of distress were associated with less caregiver family-related self-efficacy, and the more caregiver symptoms of distress were directly associated with more threatening patient appraisals. In addition, Litzelman K. et al. (2016) study also proved that caregivers' health and well-being were

related to patients' care satisfaction or how they perceive their care. When caregivers rated their health between poor and fair, patients were more than three more likely to report fair to poor quality of care. Exploratory analyses showed that patient psychosocial factors, communication with clinical staff, care coordination, and the caregiver's ability to take on medical and nursing tasks attenuated the relation (Litzelman et al, 2016). Litzelman et al. (2016) explained that informal caregivers provide support to the patient, including coordination of care, and caregivers who suffer mental or physical health may have limited capacity to coordinate care, attend clinical visits, and recall medical instructions, which eventually affect patients' care and cause distress. These studies showed that self-efficacy and burden are related. The more patient symptoms of distress, the less caregiver family-related self-efficacy, and caregiving self-efficacy indirectly affects the patient's quality of life.

Effects of Social Support on Caregiver's Self-efficacy, Burden, and Patient's Quality of Life

Another study related to self-efficacy and burden was conducted by Leung et al. (2017); they explored the association of two sources of social support (family and friends) and the mediating role of caregiving self-efficacy on caregiver burden and patient's quality of life. As a result, a significant association was detected. Leung et al. (2017) study result was that family support had a significant negative indirect effect on caregiver burden and a significant positive indirect effect on patient's quality of life through caregiving self-efficacy, whereas friend support had a significant positive direct effect on caregiver burden but minimal effect on patient's quality of life. Leung et al. (2017) and Sultan et al. (2020) study, both state that social support affects caregivers' well-being and self-efficacy. Palacio et al. (2018) supported Leung's claim

of social support; in his study, social support was one of the most common coping strategies of caregivers to burden. When caregivers need relief, a break, or respite, social support plays a significant role in caregivers' well-being. In Taiwan, an interventional study was conducted by Liao et al. (2022), and in this study, the effects of respite care services on caregivers who had > 14 days or longer of some time away have a lesser burden. They also identified that having female care recipients and being educated caregivers experienced less burden. Thus, as mentioned in these studies, social support, self-efficacy, burden, and the patient's quality of life were related.

Caregiver's Self-efficacy, Burden, and Psychological factors

Another study of self-efficacy and burden was conducted by Scicolone (2018); their study examined the interrelationship of caregiver well-being (physical and depression), burden, self-efficacy, and perceived social support in caregivers of veterans. It was found that the relationship between burden and depression was partially mediated by self-efficacy; however, the relationship between burden and physical health was not mediated by self-efficacy. This study also points out that self-soothing was the only self-efficacy domain significantly mediating the association between burden and depression. Self-soothing self-efficacy focuses on retaining one's well-being during emotional challenges and continual demands, such as the belief that there are things one can do to calm oneself. The study results of Scicolone (2018) were supported by Steffen et al. (2018), in which self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts is positively associated with better health behaviors, health-related quality of life, and less utilization of psychotropic drugs. In addition, Palacio et al. (2018) also found that cognitive restructuring and burden were negatively correlated in their study. Palacio et al. (2018) studied the influence of psychological factors on the burden of

caregivers of patients with advanced cancer. More than half of caregivers reported high levels of resilience. Their emotional distress was found to be moderate to high. They also have higher anxiety scores than depression scores. More than half of them did not present a burden score; according to Palacio, this was possible because there were no single caregivers per patient, which means another support system was present. The result showed that caregivers' most common coping strategies were problem-solving, social support, cognitive restructuring, emotional expression, and wishful thinking (Palacio et al., 2018). According to Palacio et al. (2018), the perception of control and competence promotes mobilizing personal resources when facing stressful situations in caring. In addition to coping strategies by Palacio et al. (2018), Lloyd et al. (2018) found that self-compassion was negatively related to caregiver burden and dysfunctional coping strategies and positively related to caregiver emotion-focused coping strategies. Dysfunctional strategies mediated the relationship between self-compassion and caregiver burden, whereas emotion-focused strategies did not (Lloyd et al., 2018). In other words, caregivers with higher self-compassion reported lower levels of burden, and this was at partially due to the use of less dysfunctional coping strategies. Thus, although Scicolone et al. (2018) mentioned that self-efficacy partially mediated burden and depression, but not a burden and physical health, psychological factors influential like self-soothing, cognitive restructuring, self-efficacy of controlling thoughts, and self-compassion can mediate burden and depression (Scicolone et al., 2018; Palacio et al., 2018; Llyod et al., 2018).

Caregiver's Self-efficacy, Burden and Care Recipient's Functionality

Another interesting study was the role of patient functionality in burden and self-efficacy. Sahai et al. (2018) studied the impact of a patient's functionality on the

caregiver's experience of burden and self-efficacy. This study has the same study result as Deyhoul et al. (2020), in which they focused on improving the performance of daily activities of daily living of stroke; the secondary result was a decreased burden on caregivers. Sahai et al. (2018) determined that caregiver burden was negatively related to caregiver self-efficacy, indicating that as the burden increased, there was a reduction in the caregiver's self-efficacy to deal with the illness. It was also found that there was a significant positive relationship between the functionality of the patient with caregiver burden and self-efficacy and between caregiver burden and caregiver self-efficacy. The patient's functionality was a significant predictor of burden, and burden was a significant predictor of caregiver self-efficacy. Tsai et al. (2021) and Liao et al. (2020) supported Sahai et al. (2018) study results, in which their study showed that burden and A.D.L. were positively associated. Tsai et al. (2021) found that there was much burden for those who care for very dependent older adults.

Moreover, the A.D.L. dependency of the patient was correlated with the length of care hours, and it was the only factor independently associated with missing hours at work or absences from work for those employed. Interestingly, from their study, physical diseases, depressive disorder, anxiety, physical activities, and life habits like smoking and drinking did not influence the burden. However, the patient's irritability was associated with burden. Behavioral and psychological symptoms of dementia worsen the caregiver's burden in providing A.D.L.s. Similarly, Liao et al. (2020) study showed that activities of daily living (A.D.L.) and instrumental activities of daily living (I.A.D.L.) of care recipients have a high burden impact on caregivers. Caregivers whose care-receiver had moderate A.D.L. needs had a higher burden than those with mild A.D.L. needs, including low I.A.D.L., which also correlated with the high burden.

Interestingly, in the Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) study among family caregivers with COVID-19 in Iran, time dependence was the most burdensome among the burden dimensions. This domain represents the length of time the caregivers devote each day caring for their patients; in contrast to Liao et al., the least was physical burden. This study points out that these caregivers experienced less physical burden than another study due to less COVID recovery duration than other diseases. As these studies suggest, burden and A.D.L. were positively associated. There was much burden for those who care for very dependent patients. That caregiver burden was negatively related to caregiver self-efficacy, indicating that as the burden increased, there was a reduction in the caregiver's self-efficacy to deal with the illness (Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022; Liao et al., 2020; Sahai et al., 2018; Tsai et al., 2018). According to Way J. et al. (2023), physical therapy can be a way to reduce the burden experienced by caregivers by improving the care recipient's function and helping the caregiver navigate the available community. They examined the role of physical therapy as a potential mediator to help reduce the burden experienced by caregivers by assessing the level of assistance before and after providing ten weeks of physical therapy and measuring caregivers' burden. As a result, caregivers experienced less burden due to decreased assistance needed for patient's A.D.L.s. However, the program led to additional burdens in several areas, such as physical demands in assisting with exercises, transportation demands to attend sessions, time demands for completing the exercises, and stress elicited from providing emotional encouragement to complete home exercises (Way, J. et al., 2023). These studies show that patients' level of dependency in activities of daily living impacts the caregiver's experience of burden; the more dependent the patient, the more caregiver burden experiences. The patient's

functionality became an essential predictor of burden, and burden was a significant predictor of caregiver self-efficacy.

Partially similar to the Scicolone et al. (2018) study was Sultan et al. (2020). While Scicolone et al. (2018) claimed that burden and depression were partially mediated by self-efficacy and that burden and physical health were not mediated by self-efficacy, Sultan et al. (2020) study shows successful mediation of self-efficacy. Sultan et al. (2020) explored the role of caregiving self-efficacy as a mediator between the relationships of “experiences of caregivers of dying heart patients” with “caregivers’ well-being.” The study showed high negative experiences: physical suffering and burden among caregivers. This study demonstrated that negative experiences of burden and physical suffering negatively affect and predict the caregiver's well-being, which was successfully mediated by self-efficacy. Findings presented the significant mediated effect of self-efficacy on the relationship of psychological, interpersonal, and social support with caregivers’ well-being (Sultan et al., 2020).

Caregiver’s Self-efficacy, Burden, and Demographic and other related profile

Some studies identified identifiers of self-efficacy and burden, which are significant and helpful in stratifying high-risk populations for self-efficacy and burden. Self-efficacy and burden are related, according to studies. It is worth mentioning the factors that affect self-efficacy and caregiver burden. Most of these factors and identifiers were connected to the study participants' demographic and related profiles.

Gender. According to Unver et al., 2016, who studied caregivers of the elderly in Turkey, found that there was a statistically significant difference between caregiver burden and the sex of caregivers. Females experience more burden than males. A similar study was conducted by Yildiz et al., 2017, who conducted a study for

caregivers of cancer patients; their study found that women have a higher care burden than men. On the other hand, Durante et al. (2019) also aimed to identify the determinants of caregiver burden in heart failure patients and found out that caregiver predictors of higher burden were, especially on time-dependence burden and total burden, female gender.

Age. In terms of self-efficacy, in the study of Unver et al., 2016, the relationship between the age of the elderly and the caregiver's score on the self-efficacy scale was found to be statistically significant. The age group younger than 30 has higher self-efficacy than those older than 50. A similar study was conducted by Yildiz et al. (2017). Their study found that the age group of 18-23 has a higher total self-efficacy grade than any other age group.

Regarding caregiver burden, Yildiz et al. (2017) found no significant difference between age group and burden. Meaning age was not related to burden. In contrast, according to Durante et al., 2019, the caregiver's older age was a predictor of higher time dependence, physical and social burden, and total burden; and the patient's predictor of higher time dependence and emotional burden was also older age. Durante et al. (2019) mentioned that patients of older age may have more health comorbidities or more dependence on A.D.L., which reduces caregivers' time to live their personal lives and could be emotionally burdensome.

Education. Regarding self-efficacy, the study conducted by Yildiz et al. (2017) showed that university graduates have higher self-efficacy than any other graduate level. Compared to more educated, low education levels encounter problems getting information or support from the health care team.

According to Unver et al. (2016), there was a statistically significant difference between caregiver burden and status of education; illiterate have a higher burden than

others. On the other hand, according to Durante et al., 2019 patient's predictors of higher burden, especially on time-dependence, social, and emotional burden, were patients with higher education. According to Durante, patients with higher education could be more critical in their care management, and this attitude could increase caregiver burden.

Employment. In terms of self-efficacy, the study by Unver et al., 2016, showed that the relationship between the employment status of caregivers and the caregiver's score on the self-efficacy scale was found to be statistically significant. Employed caregivers have higher self-efficacy than unemployed.

On the other hand, in terms of burden, the study of Yildiz et al. (2017) shows that although there was no significant difference between the burden of the employed and the unemployed, the care burden of the employed was less than that of the unemployed. Yildiz mentioned that since they spend most of their time outside, their focus and interest are directed to their job rather than patient care. Therefore, they are less affected by the adverse conditions of caregiving.

Relationship. According to Unver et al., 2016 there were statistically significant differences between caregiver burden and type of relationship; the burden was higher for caregivers who were relatives of the elderly. In contrast, the Yildiz et al. (2017) study showed that the degree of proximity to the patients does not affect the caregiving burden. However, their study found that those caring for their spouse have lower self-efficacy than any other caregiver.

Marital Status. In terms of self-efficacy, Yildiz et al. (2017) claimed in their study that single have higher total self-efficacy than married.

Regarding caregiver burden, Yildiz et al. (2017) found that married women experience a higher burden of care than single; married with children have a higher

burden of care—dependency or quality of life. According to Unver et al., 2016, there were statistically significant differences between caregiver burden and elderly score on the Barthel Index; there was a higher burden score for those who cared for very dependent older adults. Similarly, Yildiz et al., 2017 study found that caregivers with chronic diseases have a higher burden than those without. On the other hand, Javalkar et al. (2017) showed in their study that A.D.H.D. may display more significant behavioral issues, contributing to a greater burden.

Moreover, according to Durante et al. (2019), a patient's mental Q.O.L. predicted all caregiver burden dimensions (time-dependence, developmental, physical, social, and emotional) and total burden, while a patient's physical Q.O.L. predicted only time-dependence burden and emotional burden. This means a better patient physical Q.O.L. was associated with a higher emotional burden. As explained by Durante et al. (2019), patients who physically feel better are less adherent to medical and nursing recommendations, even if they know they have a severe heart condition. Low adherence of patients triggers the emotional burden of caregivers. Moreover, in the study of Durante et al. (2019), the caregiver's contribution to self-care maintenance (i.e., helping patients to maintain heart failure stable) and self-care management (i.e., helping patients to act in case of heart failure worsening) were not significant predictors of caregiver burden, in other words, it did not increase caregiver's burden. As explained by Durante et al. (2019), this can be because caregiving is rewarding; thus, it does not increase the caregiving burden. Durante (2019) also mentioned that higher mutuality (the positive quality of the relationship between patient and caregiver) predicted better self-care for patients and caregivers and decreased caregiver burden.

Similarly, Kaydok et al., 2020 compared the caregiver burden of mothers of children with cerebral palsy and healthy. It was found that children with poor functional status have a higher burden than healthy children, and at the same time, more frequent depression was observed in these mothers. Interestingly, both cerebral palsy and healthy mothers experienced a time-dependence burden. This shows that both mothers spend much time with their children.

According to the study of Javalkar et al., 2017, the related self-efficacy of the care recipient also impacts the burden of the mother; the lower the self-efficacy, the higher the burden of the caregiver.

Caregiving hours. According to Durante et al., 2019, most heart failure caregivers with fewer hours have higher social and emotional burdens associated with total caregiver burden scores. According to Durante et al. (2019) interpretation, a caregiver who commits more time to caregiving generates acknowledgement and respect from other family members and friends, which could reduce the burden. On the other hand, the relationship between caregiving hours and emotional burden, according to Durante et al. (2019), reflects feelings of shame and anger, which can be alleviated by spending more on the patient. Another is spending more time with the patient to a more positive quality of relationship, which can reduce the burden.

In Yildiz et al. (2017) study result, there was no difference between caregiving burden and caregiving less than a year and more than a year. Although the result was statistically insignificant, the burden of 13 months and more was higher than 13 to 24 hours of care.

Social Support. According to Yildiz et al. (2017), those who did not have support during the caregiving process have a higher burden. According to Durante et al., 2019, most caregivers of heart failure who have poor social support have a higher

social burden and are associated with a total caregiver burden. Durante et al. (2019) state that heart failure caregivers with fewer hours of caregiving have higher social and emotional burdens. On the other hand, in terms of self-efficacy, Yildiz et al. (2017) study showed that those who have supported have higher initiating behavior scale self-efficacy.

Quantity of medication. According to Javalkar et al. (2017), the number of children's injections and medicines was one of the predictors of increased caregiver burden. According to the author, the association of several medicines and injections to the mother's burden may suggest that she is very involved in care, or the more medicines, the sicker the patient is. In addition, the frequency of medical visits causes additional burdens, regardless of whether emergent or preventive.

On the contrary, according to Durante et al., 2019, patients who took fewer medications were predictors of higher developmental, physical, social, and emotional burdens. More medication patients took predicted better self-care, which gave caregivers fewer duties and worries and resulted in a lower burden.

Race. The study of Javalkar et al. (2017) about child-related predictors and risk factors for caregiver burden among parents of children with chronic conditions in North Carolina shows that mothers of white children reported significantly higher burdens than mothers of non-white.

Interestingly, race has to do with burden. The study of Fenton et al. (2022) about racial and ethnic disparities in cancer caregiving burden and potential sociocultural mediators stated that Black and Hispanic caregivers of cancer patients perform more caregiving and have more economic burden than non-Hispanic white caregivers. Moreover, Hispanic caregivers reported similar social/emotional and health burdens, while Black caregivers reported lower levels; and Hispanic caregivers had less health

burden than non-Hispanic White caregivers. As Fenton et al. (2022) explained, social support and caregiving preparedness partially mediated the Black-White gap for all three types of burdens.

Caregiver's Self-efficacy, Burden and Interventions

Some studies attempted to develop and improve self-efficacy, as Havyer et al. (2016) and Hendrix et al. (2016) conducted. On the other hand, Cianfrocca et al. (2018) and Zoladl et al. (2020) did the same to improve caregiver burden. Cianfrocca et al. (2018) studied the effect of multidisciplinary education on the burden, health literacy, and needs of family caregivers. The study result was increased caregiver needs assistance (CNA) and decreased total burden. As Cianfrocca et al. (2018) explained the increase in C.N.A.s means the intervention's ability to make caregivers aware of their needs. Their study showed significant decrease in burden as it shows change in the view of one's welfare role; caregivers seem to be more conscious of their role and better realized the significance of their actions regarding quality of life, safety, and patient outcome. On the other hand, Zoladl et al. (2020) conducted a randomized control trial in which a collaborative care model was applied to the caregiver burden and resilience of family caregivers of patients with mental disorders. The result of the study indicated that the intensity of caregiver burden was high in both groups initially. After intervention, the intensity decreased in both groups, but this decrease was significantly more in the experimental group. Zoladl et al. (2020) mentioned that when caregivers clearly understand their patients' illnesses, symptoms, and conditions, their stress and anxiety are reduced, and their ability to cope with their problems increases.

Overall, these studies show that self-efficacy and burden were negatively related. In other words, as caregivers experience more burden, the lesser their self-efficacy. The more patient symptoms of distress, the lesser the caregiver-related self-efficacy, and caregiving self-efficacy indirectly affects the patient's quality of life. Family or social support also significantly increases self-efficacy and decreases caregiver burden; it serves as a respite for caregivers. Aside from family/social support, studies also show that a patient's physical functionality affects self-efficacy and burden. The more dependent the care recipient, the more burdensome to caregivers, and the lesser the caregivers' self-efficacy. Importantly, these studies identified identifiers that can assist in identifying and stratifying high-risk caregivers. Moreover, the function of self-efficacy as a mediator to caregiver burden needs more studies as some studies point out that there was specific self-efficacy that can only mediate specific burden and depression but not the physical health of caregivers.

Studies on Self-efficacy and Burden Tools

Self-Efficacy Assessment Tools and Psychometric Properties

The tools for self-efficacy that will be discussed are the Caregiver Inventory (CGI) and the Revised Scale for Caregiving Self-Efficacy (R.S.C.S.E.).

Caregiver Inventory is a non-disease-specific measure of self-efficacy for caregiving that shows more comprehensive relationship orientation than currently exists in measures and considers caregivers' self-care and possible positive aspects of caregiving (Merluzzi et al., 2011). Merluzzi et al. (2011) conducted a study to analyze the Caregiver Inventory (CGI) psychometric properties. They recruited caregivers of those with dementia, cancer, advanced C.O.P.D., chronic heart failure, and Alzheimer's. As a result of the study, the internal consistency (Cronbach's α) of

21-item CGI was 0.91. Item-to-total-score correlation and α_n if item deleted indicated that all items were significantly performed and that all should be retained for inclusion in an analysis examining the structure of the CGI. Caregiver Inventory also has a Chinese version, and Leung et al. (2017) aimed to test the reliability and validity of this tool in primary caregivers of patients with palliative care needs in Hong Kong. As a result of the study, Chinese-CGI-18 demonstrated good internal consistency and test-retest reliability, with Cronbach's alpha > 0.80 and ICC values over a 2-week interval for the subsample of 69 caregivers >0.7 , respectively. The construct validity presents correlations of the three dimensions of CGI with the caregiver's CSI and C-MPSS scores and the patient's MBI score.

Another measurement tool for self-efficacy is the Revised Scale for Caregiving Self-Efficacy (RSCSE). Steffen et al. (2019) conducted a cross-national review of this instrument used with dementia family caregivers. The RSCSE has been cited sufficiently frequently and translated into multiple languages. Scale's performance has been organized with attention to translation procedures, psychometric properties, factor structure, validity, and utility within a cross-cultural perspective. The internal reliabilities for interview administration of R.S.C.S.E. have been strong: S.E.: Obtaining Respite (OR) $\alpha = .84-.95$; S.E.: Managing Disruptive Behaviors (M.B.) $\alpha = .79-.95$; SE: Controlling Upsetting Thoughts (CT) $\alpha = .75-.92$. The full scale of RSCSE $\alpha = .70-.92$. Predictors of self-efficacy demographic (ethnicity, kinship, gender) are directly related to the caregiver's level of self-efficacy among English, French, and Spanish-speaking caregivers (Steffen et al., 2019).

Overall, the Caregiver Inventory and Revised Scale for Caregiving Self-Efficacy (RSCSE) both have Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.79$. The study of Merluzzi et al. (2011) shows that the Caregiver Inventory internal consistency (Cronbach's α) was 0.91. Exploratory

factor analysis was conducted to determine the smallest number of meaningful factors underlying the items in the CGI. Fit indices indicated a four factors solution: Managing Medical Information (0.64), Caring for Care Recipient (0.78), Caring for Oneself (0.88), and Managing Difficult Interactions/Emotions (0.76), the analyses indicated that a four-factor solution provided the best fit for the data. On the other hand, the internal reliabilities for interview administration of R.S.C.S.E. were strong: S.E.: Obtaining Respite (OR) $\alpha = .84-.95$; S.E.: Managing Disruptive Behaviors (M.B.) $\alpha = .79-.95$; SE: Controlling Upsetting Thoughts (CT) $\alpha = .75-.92$. The full scale of RSCSE $\alpha = .70-.92$. The construct of S.E. is relevant and readily measurable in diverse cultures. Several identified published studies have been found that have used the scale, with translation in Arabic, Chinese, English, French, Italian, and Spanish. All the reviewed study supports the internal reliability of the subscales (Cronbach's alpha ranging from .79 to .95).

Caregiver Burden Assessment Tools and their Psychometric properties

Informal caregivers' feelings of stress and burden can be assessed with standardized questionnaires and interviews. Although stress and burden are not diagnostic labels, they are critical components of the profile of psychological and physical distress experienced by many caregivers. The tools for burden that will be discussed in this chapter are the Zarit Burden Scale and Caregiver Burden Inventory (C.B.I.) because they are the most used.

Zarit Burden Interview (Z.B.I.) is a famous caregiver self-report measure many researchers use. It consists of 22 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from 0 (never) to 4 (nearly always). A higher score indicates a higher burden. The Z.B.I. was developed as a unidimensional measure of burden. Al-Rawashdeh

(2016) conducted a study that examined the internal consistency reliability, convergent, and construct validity of the Zarit Burden Interview (Z.B.I.) in caregivers of patients with heart failure (H.F.). As a result, the reliability of Z.B.I. in this study was 0.92, indicating internal consistency. The item-total correlations of the Z.B.I. were acceptable, ranging from 0.40 to 0.76. The psychometric properties of the Z.B.I. have been most commonly reported in caregivers of dementia, cancer, and brain trauma patients (Al-Rawashdeh, 2016). However, this study recommends using the Z.B.I. total score rather than specific dimensions or subscales.

The Z.B.I.'s psychometric proprieties have been greatly examined in caregivers of patients with dementia and demonstrate strong evidence for reliability and validity in that population (Ankri, 2005; Hebert, 2000; & Seng, 2010, as cited by Al-Rawashdeh, 2016). The Z.B.D. has also been examined in caregivers of patients with cancer (Higginson, 2008, as cited by Al-Rawashdeh, 2016) and brain injury (Siegert, 2010, as cited by Al-Rawashdeh, 2016). The reported Cronbach's alpha for the Z.B.I. in caregivers of patients with cancer and dementia ranged between .85 and .93 (Flynn, 2011; Hebert, 2000; Higginson, 2008, as cited by Al-Rawashdeh, 2016). Evidence for the criterion validity of the Z.B.I. has been demonstrated in caregivers of patients with dementia in whom the Z.B.I. was highly correlated with the Burden Assessment Scale (Seng, 2010, as cited by Al-Rawashdeh, 2016). Evidence of Z.B.I. construct validity was demonstrated through strong correlations with the General Health Questionnaire-28, an established measure of distress (Seng, 2010, as cited by Al-Rawashdeh, 2016).

Another tool for measuring caregiver burden is the Caregiver Burden Inventory (C.B.I.). The Caregiver Burden Inventory was validated in 1989 (Marvardi et al., 2005). It is a self-administered questionnaire used to assess the perceived burden. It consists

of 24 items measured on a 5-point Likert Scale, where 0 represents the absence of perceived stress, and four is the maximum stress level. The items are divided into five subgroups: 1. Time-dependent burden 2. developmental burden (Dev-B) 3. Physical burden (Phys-B), 4. Social burden (Soc-B), caused by conflict of roles concerning one's job or family; and 5. Emotional burden (Emot-B). As a result, the C.B.I. showed very high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha value >0.80). Multiple regression analysis revealed that patients' behavioral disturbances and disability significantly influenced the time-dependent burden. In conclusion, C.B.I. proved to be an effective multidimensional tool for evaluating the impact of burden on many aspects of caregivers' lives.

The key points are that these two burden tools, the Zarit Burden Tool and C.B.I., are reliable and valid; researchers should choose which tool to use according to their research question and interest. The reliability of Z.B.I. in this study was 0.92, indicating internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha did not change significantly when deleting any item, remaining close to the full-scale Cronbach's alpha of .92. All item-total correlations were significantly and positively correlated with the total score, supporting the homogeneity of the scale. The item-to-item correlations were significant and ranged between .30 and .70. It was therefore suggested to interpret data using the Zarit-total score rather than the sub-score.

The C.B.I. showed a high internal consistency of Cronbach's alpha value >0.80 (Cianfrocca, 2018; Marvardi et al., 2005). The study of Marvardi et al. (2005) points out some influential factors that can make the score of these tools high; for example, old age had a significant influence only on the variance of physical burden; being a spouse influenced only Emotional Burden. However, anxiety and depression represent the factors that most significantly influence all aspects C.B.I. evaluates. The study

proved that identifying the primary type of burden in every caregiver could help design a focus intervention.

Psychometric properties of Barthel Index: Activity of Daily Living Assessment Tool

The Barthel Index (B.I.) was initially developed by Florence Mahoney and Dorothea Barthel in 1955. The Barthel Index measures the degree of assistance an individual requires on ten items of mobility and self-care A.D.L. This tool was usually used with stroke patients, neuromuscular or musculoskeletal disorders, and oncology patients. The reliability of B.I. is traditionally described using either κ statistics. κ statistics range from $\kappa=0.00$ (no agreement other than expected by chance) to $\kappa=1.00$ (complete agreement). Standard definitions were used of poor ($\kappa=0.00-0.20$), fair ($\kappa=0.21-0.40$), moderate ($\kappa=0.41-0.60$), good ($\kappa=0.61-0.80$), and excellent ($\kappa=0.81-1.00$) agreement. All calculations were performed using Comprehensive Meta-analysis software. As a result, from 20 210 titles, 306 abstracts were reviewed, 12 studies met inclusion criteria, and ten were included in the meta-analysis ($n=543$ participants; a range of participants in studies, 7–21); there was substantial clinical heterogeneity concerning the method of B.I. application; population studied and assessors. Internal validity of the search strategy was confirmed as an independent third reviewer found no titles other than those already selected by the original two researchers (Duffy et al., 2013). The external validity of the search strategy was confirmed as all prespecified titles were included in the search results. Overall inter-observer reliability of standard administration of the B.I. was excellent ($\kappa_w, 0.93$; 95% confidence interval (CI): 0.90–0.96 random effects modeling). In addition, the study of Unver et al. (2016) used the same instrument in assessing the dependency of their participants and mentioned that the internal consistency was 0.93 and Cronbach's

coefficient were .99 and .93, which indicates good reliability and validity (Unver et al., 2016).

Synthesis

Most family members need to prepare for their caregiving role. Being ill-prepared for the role contributes negatively to carers' confidence or self-efficacy in performing the care responsibility. The care-related difficulties are the hallmark of chronic stress that overwhelms over time, and these experiences become a health hazard to caregivers, known as the caregiver burden.

Many studies about self-efficacy and caregiver burden have shown that they are negatively related. Self-efficacy in caregiving pertains to the belief that one can perform a specific task in managing the demands of caregiving. Self-efficacy has been an interest of this study because of its ability to affect the psychological state of motivation, behavioral change, and physiological stress. Self-efficacy can also help determine if a coping mechanism or action will be initiated, the effort that will be used up on an activity, and how resilient a person can be in the face of an adversary. Several studies have highlighted the role of self-efficacy as a moderating factor against caregiver burden and other disciplines. Some of the factors that have been identified affecting the self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden were the physical functionality of the patient, the family and social support that the caregiver receives, and the distress that the patient and caregiver experience. They play a significant role in decreasing caregiver burden and increasing self-efficacy.

Another critical point is that self-efficacy can be improved through training, education, and improving the patients' lives. However, one of the interventional studies proved that the positive outcome did not last long. This claim, though, needs to be more robust since the literature that tests interventional longevity is very limited. As

was seen in other literature, self-efficacy and burden were affected by different caregiver and patient characters. Therefore, it is imperative to know which dimension of caregiver self-efficacy and caregiver burden are the weaknesses and strengths that can affect the well-being of caregivers to design a more individualized intervention.

Findings from other related literature have inconsistent results of self-efficacy and caregiver burden. Thus, the results of each study cannot be generalized. This could be attributed to the different characteristics of patients and care recipients. For this reason, this study intends to determine the self-efficacy and caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the U.A.E.

Theoretical Framework

The proposition of Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory is studied about caregiver burden.

Albert Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory

Albert Bandura, a psychologist who developed self-efficacy theory (S.E.T.) in 1977, proposed that this S.E.T. is the determining force of behavioral change. Behavioral change plays a big part in nursing. According to Bandura (1994), "*self-efficacy is people's beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives.*" In other words, it is a person's belief in their ability to succeed in certain situation. These beliefs influence how individuals feel, think, motivate themselves, and behave.

Bandura's theory assumes that a person's beliefs in their coping capabilities affect how much stress and depression they experience in threatening or difficult situations. A person who believes they can manage threats they do not easily get triggered by disturbing thought patterns. However, those who believe they cannot

control threats experience high anxiety arousal and dwell on coping deficiencies. Self-control of thought processes is critical in regulating thought, stress, and depression (Bandura, 1994). Stress has been connected as significant contributing factor to many physical dysfunctions, but according to this theory, it is not the stressful life conditions by itself but the perceived inability to manage debilitating stress (Bandura, 1994). This means that exposure to stressors with the ability to control them has no adverse biological effects. However, exposure to the same stressors without the ability to control them weakens the ability to control the immune system. The impairment of immune function increases vulnerability to infection, contributes to the development of physical disorders, and accelerates disease progression. This theory also claims that the stronger the perceived self-regulatory efficacy of a person, the more successful he will be in reducing health-impairing habits and adopting and integrating health-promoting habits into a regular lifestyle. This means people are more likely to engage in healthy behaviors when they feel confident in their capabilities to carry out those behaviors successfully.

Overall, this theory assumes that the stronger the sense of self-efficacy, the lower the stress or burden of a person; thus, identifying the current self-efficacy and burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill and its relationship is imperative so individuals who are struggling may be provided with opportunities to obtain mastery experiences, positive social persuasion, witnessing positive modeling necessary to enforce high levels of self-efficacy and manage caregiver burden.

Conceptual Framework

The diagram shows the relationship between caregiver self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden. The independent variable is the caregiver's self-

efficacy, and the dependent variable is the caregiver's burden. Therefore, this study assumes that caregiver self-efficacy in caregiving is inversely related to caregiver burden. When a caregiver has higher perceived self-efficacy, the caregiver is a burden. The straight line is shown to the relationship between these two variables. Caregiver self-efficacy has four dimensions: caring for oneself, managing medical information, caring for the recipient, and managing complex interactions and emotions. The caregiver burden has five dimensions: time dependence or objective burden, developmental burden, emotional burden, physical burden, and social burden. The socio-demographic profile of the participants, which is connected with broken lines, shows an indirect relationship between self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Relationship of informal caregivers' self-efficacy and burden.

Figure 1 shows that the confounding variable in this study is socio-demographic profiles and care recipient A.D.L. dependency. Socio-demographic profiles such as age, sex, marital status, educational degree, race, employment status, kinship, and caregiving duration are related to self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden. A.D.L. dependency includes assessment of bathing, grooming, stairs, toilet use, dressing, bladder, bowels, feeding, mobility, and transfer.

Operational Definition of Terms

Self-Efficacy

The person believes that one has the power to produce an outcome by executing courses of action that are required to deal with the prospective situation. *Self-efficacy caregiving* refers to the belief in the self of being able to care for the patient's needs. This is the independent variable of this study, and it will be measured by the Caregiver Inventory tool using the Linkert scale. This study will be measured in terms of four dimensions of self-efficacy: caring for oneself, managing medical information, caring for the care recipient, and managing complex interactions and emotions.

- *Caring for Oneself Self-Efficacy*

Self-care practices can include maintaining one's health and well-being, actively seeking support, and maintaining some activity apart from the caregiving situation. It also includes dealing with helplessness and "letting go" in recognizing the limits of personal control.

- *Managing Medical Information Self-Efficacy*

Predominantly focuses on the interface with the medical community and obtaining and understanding care-related information. He manages the patient's medical regimen and communicates with healthcare providers.

- *Caring for Care Recipient Self-Efficacy*

It focuses on caregiving aspects typically found in caregiver measures and includes tasks such as feeding, bathing, toileting, and treatment adherence.

This factor also includes aspects of caregiving that focus on the relationship with the care receiver and the positive aspects of caregiving. This factor includes the caregivers' expectations regarding their ability to provide support.

In the context of a close relationship, establish open communication and enable care receivers to express themselves. This also identifies positive aspects, or "good moments," in their role as caregivers.

- *Managing Difficult Interactions & Emotions Self-Efficacy*

It includes talking about death and dying, dealing with negative feelings from the person for whom they are giving care, being able to express negative feelings, and dealing with criticism.

Caregiver Burden

Caregiver burden is the strain or load borne by a caregiver for caring. It has multiple responses to one's physical, emotional, social, psychological, and financial stressors connected to the caregiving experience. This is the study's dependent variable, and it will be measured by the Caregiver Burden Inventory tool using the Likert scale. In this study, caregiver burden has five dimensions: developmental burden, emotional burden, physical burden, social burden, and time dependence or objective burden.

- *Developmental Burden*
 - refers to the sense of failure regarding one's hopes and expectations
- *Emotional Burden*
 - refers to any embarrassment or feeling of shame caused by the patient
- *Physical Burden*
 - refers to physical stress and somatic disorders
- *Social Burden*
 - is caused by conflicting roles concerning one's job or family
- *Time Dependence or Objective Burden*
 - stress caused by restriction of one's time

Terminal Illness

Terminal illness in this study pertains to cancer in different sub-types: malignant solid tumor, hematologic malignancy, palliative cancer, pediatric oncology, and hematology.

Statement of Hypothesis

Ha1: There is a significant relationship between informal general caregiver self-efficacy in caregiving and general caregiver burden.

Ha2: There is a significant relationship between informal general caregiver's self-efficacy in caregiving and the selected demographic profiles such as:

2.1 age

2.2 sex

2.3 marital status

2.4 educational degree

2.5 race

2.6 employment status

2.7 kinship

2.8 caregiving duration

Ha3: There is a significant relationship between informal general caregiver's burden and the selected demographic profiles such as:

3.1 age

3.2 sex

3.3 marital status

3.4 educational degree

3.5 race

3.6 employment status

3.7 kinship

3.8 caregiving duration

Ha4: There is a significant relationship between general self-efficacy in caregiving and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates

Ha5: There is a significant relationship between general caregiver burden and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methodology that this study utilized. This chapter includes the research design and its rationale, population and sampling methods, research settings, data collection procedure, pilot study, data collection and management, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational design. This study described self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden and tested their relationship. This study tested the relationship between self-efficacy and sociodemographic profile, self-efficacy and A.D.L., self-efficacy and caregiver burden, caregiver burden and sociodemographic profile, and caregiver burden and A.D.L.

Research Sampling

The population in this study were informal caregivers caring for one or more relatives affected by terminal disease. The purposive or judgmental sampling technique, which is a non-probability sampling technique, was utilized to select the samples from the Oncology department. Purposive sampling is a sampling method in which participants are selected based on a personal judgment about which one is the most representative. Exactly 60 participants were admitted as the population to the study.

Inclusion criteria

1. A direct informal caregiver of terminally ill patients,
2. Caring for family members, regardless of caregiving duration,
3. With or without the assistance of a professional caregiver and

Exclusion criteria

1. Cannot communicate in English or Arabic,
2. Volunteers or non-familial caregivers
3. and those informal caregivers whose care receiver recently died

Research Setting

The research setting was in the Oncology department of Tawam Hospital in the United Arab Emirates. This was the preferred setting because Tawam Hospital Oncology Services is the U.A.E.'s national referral center for cancer care. The informal caregivers in this department can stay with their care recipient during COVID-19 strict regulations. Informal caregivers in this department experience different stress levels because patients have unpredictable conditions.

The inpatient oncology unit comprises oncology, hematology, palliative care, and pediatric oncology units. It has a total bed capacity of 70. S.M.U. 1, which caters to services for malignant solid tumors, has a 19-bed capacity and has approximately 1076 admissions annually. S.M.U. 2, which caters to services for hematologic malignancy, has 21- a 21-bed capacity and has approximately 4,897 admissions annually. S.M.U. 3, which caters to services for palliative cancer with a 12-bed capacity, had approximately 375 admissions annually. The Pediatric Oncology and

Hematology department has an 18-bed capacity and approximately 1047 admissions annually.

The Oncology department of Tawam Hospital treats all solid tumors, hematologic disorders, and malignancies. Whether the treatment is curative, controlling, or palliative, they provide care for cancer diseases. Contemporary treatment modalities are available, including but not limited to systemic chemotherapy, immunotherapy, targeted therapies, radio-therapeutic treatment, regional chemotherapy, trans-arterial chemoembolization, radiofrequency ablation, biological treatments, and others.

Data Collection Procedure

The following was the data collection procedure of the study. The study participants were recruited from the inpatient department of Oncology according to inclusion criteria. The study procedure consists of the following (see Figure 2):

Figure 2. Diagram of the study protocol.

Upon approval of the study proposal from the University of the Philippines Open University and Institutional Review Board, a letter of request was sent to the research and ethics committee of Tawam Hospital for study approval. The latter took a month for hospital review and approval due to Covid restrictions. Once the study was approved, recruitment, orientation, and training of research assistants for obtaining consent, distributing questionnaires, and collecting data was initiated. The roles and responsibilities of the research assistants were discussed. It includes research protocols and ethical considerations. Open communication was encouraged between the researcher, the assistant researcher, and the participants. The researcher ensured availability at all times of need for the entire duration of data collection. A pilot study was conducted, as detailed in the pilot study section. Participants were selected, and an informal interview was conducted to ensure they met the inclusion criteria. Informed consent was obtained prior to the study. Ethical principles were consistently observed. The participants were assured of their anonymity and confidentiality. They have the right to withdraw at any time from the study without bearing any consequences. Responsibilities were explained to the participants in accepting the role as part of the study to obtain accurate findings and prevent attrition. The participants were expected to complete the questionnaires from the researcher. Participants answered the questionnaires, which included the sociodemographic questionnaire, Caregiver Burden Inventory, Caregiver Inventory questionnaire, and Barthel Index. They reflected on their answers by choosing numbers that best describe their thoughts and feelings. After answering the questionnaires, the research assistants collected and secured the questionnaire. The contact number of the nurse researcher was given to the participants as reflected in the Informed Consent Form in case of clarifications and questions for a speedy response.

Roles

Researcher

The researcher provided direction for the study, which included an explanation of inclusion and exclusion criteria, target population, and consent. The researcher provided premade dialogue for consent and introduction of questionnaires to prevent missing important points. The researcher maintained open communication between the research assistant and participants to address questions and clarifications. The researcher was required to have a Good Clinical Practice certificate before initiating the study.

Research Assistant

The research assistants were nurses. They acquired consent and disseminated questionnaires using premade dialogue. They assisted with any questions and clarifications from participants. They stayed the entire duration of the study. They continuously observed privacy and confidentiality while collecting and encoding data. The research assistants were required to have a Good Clinical Practice certificate before initiating the study.

Pilot Study

This study's four (4) questionnaires were prepared in English and Arabic. The instruments were pretested to subjects to refine and evaluate the tool and process of data collection prior to the actual study. It took 25-30 minutes for the participants to answer the questionnaires.

Data Collection Methods

The trained research assistants collected the data to eliminate researcher bias. Four self-administered questionnaires were utilized in this study. It was introduced using a semi-formal approach. There was a debriefing of the actual data collection to the trained researcher. Descriptions and instructions were given to the participants, which include the purpose of the study, risk, benefit, anonymity, and rights, which are included in the consent; how to answer the questionnaires; and they are free to ask questions and clarifications from the research assistants; and free to terminate from research anytime.

The participants were expected to answer four questionnaires: a Demographic questionnaire, a Caregiver Inventory questionnaire (CGI), a Caregiver Burden Inventory questionnaire, and a Barthel Index questionnaire. The questionnaires were collected, kept in an individualized brown envelope, and checked for completeness by the trained assistant researcher, emphasizing confidentiality and anonymity.

Data Analysis and Management

Statistical analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS). Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential analysis. Since randomness and independence of the observations were not satisfied, nonparametric tests for statistical data treatment were employed. Research objectives 1, 2, 3, and 4 will utilize a descriptive statistic, and 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 Spearman rho correlation will be used (see Table 1).

Table 1*Goals, Objectives, and Data Analysis and Management*

Research Objectives	Tools	Variable/Level of Measurement	Statistical Test
1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of: 1.1 Sex 1.2 Marital status 1.3 Age 1.4 Education 1.5 Race 1.6 Employment 1.7 Other related employment information	Sociodemographic Questionnaire	Nominal/ Ordinal	Descriptive: Frequencies, Mean, Percentage
2. To describe the self-efficacy of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of the following self-efficacy dimensions: 2.1 Caring for oneself self-efficacy 2.2 Managing medical information Self-efficacy 2.3 Caring for care recipient self-efficacy 2.4 Managing difficult interactions and emotions self-efficacy	Caregiver Inventory Tool	Self-efficacy Interval scale	Descriptive: Means

Research Objectives	Tools	Variable/Level of Measurement	Statistical Test
<p>3. To describe the caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of the following self-efficacy dimensions:</p> <p>3.1 Time Dependence or Objective Burden</p> <p>3.2 Developmental Burden</p> <p>3.3 Emotional Burden</p> <p>3.4 Physical Burden</p> <p>3.5 Social Burden</p>	Caregiver Burden Inventory Tool	Caregiver Burden <i>Ordinal scale</i>	Descriptive: Means
4. To describe the level of Activity of Daily Living (A.D.L.) independence of care recipients of caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates.	Barthel Index	Activity of Daily Living (A.D.L.) independency <i>Ordinal scale</i>	Descriptive: Means
5. To determine the relationship between overall caregiver self-efficacy and overall caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates	Caregiver Burden Inventory Tool Caregiver Inventory Tool	Self-efficacy <i>Interval/ Ratio Scale</i> Caregiver Burden <i>Interval/ Ratio Scale</i>	Spearman rho correlation
6. To determine the relationship of overall self-efficacy of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of their sociodemographic profile	Demographic questionnaire Caregiver Inventory Tool	Self-efficacy- <i>Ordinal</i> Age – <i>Ordinal</i> Educational Degree- <i>Ordinal</i> Caregiving Duration- <i>Ordinal</i> Self –efficacy- <i>Ordinal</i>	Spearman Rho correlation
6.1 Age			
6.2 Sex			

Research Objectives	Tools	Variable/Level of Measurement	Statistical Test
6.3 Marital status 6.4 Educational Degree 6.5 Race 6.6 Employment Status 6.7 Kinship 6.8 Caregiving Duration		Sex- <i>Nominal</i> Marital status- <i>Nominal</i> Race- <i>Nominal</i> Employment Status- <i>Nominal</i> Kinship- <i>Nominal</i>	Chi-Square
7. To determine the relationship of overall caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates in terms of their sociodemographic profile		Caregiver Burden- <i>Ordinal</i> Age – <i>Ordinal</i> Educational Degree- <i>Ordinal</i> Caregiving Duration- <i>Ordinal</i>	Spearman rho correlation Chi-Square
7.1 Age 7.2 Sex 7.3 Marital status 7.4 Educational Degree 7.5 Race 7.6 Employment Status 7.7 Kinship 7.8 Caregiving Duration		Sex- <i>Nominal</i> Marital status- <i>Nominal</i> Race- <i>Nominal</i> Employment Status- <i>Nominal</i> Kinship- <i>Nominal</i>	
8. To determine the relationship between overall self-efficacy and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates	Caregiver Inventory Tool and Barthel Index	Self-efficacy- <i>Ordinal</i> Barthel Index- <i>ordinal</i>	Spearman rho correlation
9. To determine the relationship between overall caregiver burden and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates	Caregiver Burden Inventory Tool and Barthel Scale Index	Caregiver Burden- <i>Ordinal</i> Barthel Index- <i>ordinal</i>	Spearman rho correlation

Instrumentation

Four (4) sections of the questionnaire were utilized in this study. This includes the demographic and related work profiles, caregiver inventory questionnaire (CGI), caregiver burden inventory (CBI), and Barthel Index. The demographic and related work profiles were self-made based on factors deemed valuable in the literature. The other three questionnaires were adopted and were chosen according to a variable of interest. All questionnaires were prepared in Arabic and English for the informal caregivers. The questionnaires were translated by an official translator and back-to-back by the medical staff of Tawam Hospital.

The demographic and other work-related questionnaire was subdivided into general demographics, which include gender, marital status, age group, educational attainment, race, employment status, and other work-related details such as caregiver relationship to care recipient, duration of caregiving, if with or without a private nurse. Using these profiles, we can compare and contrast and identify who is at the most risk of caregiver burden and less confidence among the caregivers.

Self-efficacy was measured by adopting the Caregiver Inventory (CGI) of Merluzzi (2011). This questionnaire is a non-disease-specific questionnaire, meaning it applies to any disease to assess informal caregiver's self-efficacy. This questionnaire can assess self-care and communication variables that other questionnaires do not focus on (Hampton, 2018; & Merluzzi, 2011). Self-care is the practice of activities to maintain life, and it is an essential part of the questionnaire to see differences in caregiver burden and self-efficacy (Gonzalo, 2019). The caregiver Inventory questionnaire consists of questions arranged into four sub-scales: managing medical information (items 19,14,1), caring for the care recipient (items 2,6,7,8,13,18,21), caring for oneself (items 3,9,11,15,16), and managing difficult

interactions and emotions (item 4,5,10,12,17,20). Previous study shows that CGI has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.93 for the total scale and subscale ranged from 0.74 to 0.80: Managing Medical Information (0.64), Caring for Care Recipient (0.78), Caring for Oneself (0.88), and Managing Difficult Interactions/Emotions (0.76), indicating good to excellent reliability (Hampton, 2018; Merluzzi et al., 2011). The level of self-efficacy is measured using a Likert scale and interpreted as follows. A high subscale score of nine would indicate "total confidence and high self-efficacy" for the subscale; five for "moderately confident"; a low subscale score of 1 indicates a "lack of confidence and low self-efficacy" for the subscale. The total score is the sum of each subscale score. A high score of 36 would indicate that caregivers have a high level of confidence and high self-efficacy in their ability to manage caregiving demands; a low score of four indicates a lack of confidence or low self-efficacy in managing caregiving demands (Hampton, 2018).

Several measurements were developed to measure caregivers' burden, and most of them heavily rely on the overall burden score to interpret. In this study, the Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI), developed by Novak and Guest (1989), will be adopted to measure caregiver burden. This tool quantifies not only the global burden according to score but also evaluates and quantifies different aspects of burden through subgroups: time dependence or objective burden, developmental burden, emotional burden, physical burden, and social burden. The CBI is a multi-dimensional questionnaire measuring five burden dimensions of caregivers: (a) Time Dependence or objective burden, evaluating stress caused by a restriction of one's time or with family member's time (items 1-5); (b) Developmental burden, referring to the sense of failure regarding one's hopes, expectations and opportunities (item 6-10); (c) Emotional burden, referring to any embarrassment or feeling of shame towards the

patient(items 20-24).; (d) Physical Burden, referring to physical stress and somatic disorders items (11-14); (e) Social Burden, caused by conflict of roles concerning one's job or /and other family members(items 15-19). Previous studies show that CBI has a very high internal consistency; both the scale and dimensions of CBI proved to be very reliable, with Cronbach's alpha value of >0.80 (Marvardi et al., 2005; Cianfrocca et al., 2018). The CBI consists of 24 items measured on a Likert scale. Scores for each item are evaluated using a Likert scale ranging from 0 (absence of stress) to 4 (maximum stress level). All of the scores on the 24-item scale are summed, and a total score >36 indicates a risk of "burning out," whereas scores near or slightly above 24 indicate a need to seek some form of respite care (Novack & Guest, 1989 as cited in Cianfrocca et al.,2018).

The Activity of Daily Living (A.D.L.) independence was measured using the Barthel Index. The Barthel Index was developed by Mahoney and Barthel in 1965. The Barthel Index measures the degree of assistance an individual requires on ten items of mobility and self-care A.D.L. This tool was usually used with stroke patients, neuromuscular or musculoskeletal disorders, and oncology patients. The internal consistency was 0.93, and Cronbach's coefficients were .99 and .93, which indicates good reliability and validity (Unver et al., 2016). This questionnaire is an ordinal scale used to measure performance in activities of daily living (A.D.L.). Ten variables describe A.D.L. and patient mobility: assessment of bathing, grooming, stairs, toilet use, dressing, bladder, bowels, deeding, mobility, and transfer. The score is 0-100; the higher the number reflects a greater ability to function independently (Unver et al., 2016; Upadhyay, 2021). The Index is a three-item ordinal rating scale, each is rated in terms of whether the patient can perform the task independently, with some assistance, or depends on help based on observation (0 unable, 1 needs help, two

independent) (Unver et al., 2016; Upadhyay, 2021). The final score is x 5 to get a number on a 100-point score. Proposed guidelines for interpreting Barthel scores are that score of 0-20 indicate “total” dependency, 21-60 indicate “severe” dependency, 61-90 indicate “moderate” dependency, and 91-99 indicates “slight” dependency. Most studies use 60/61 as the cutting point (Unver et al., 2016; Upadhyay, 2021).

Ethical Considerations

Before conducting the research, ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Review Board (ERB) of the University of the Philippines Open University and Tawam Hospital. Informed consent was obtained from the participants. Their anonymity and confidentiality were safeguarded. The purpose of the study was fully discussed, and the data they provided will be used in the study. They have the right to voluntarily participate or withdraw from the study without the risk of incurring penalties or rewards. The following bioethical principles were considered:

a. Self-determination

The participants were capable of controlling their destinies. The participants were treated as autonomous agents with the freedom to choose without external controls. *Informed consent* was introduced in which they were oriented about the study, including the benefits and harm. They were given the choice of whether to participate and could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

b. Privacy and confidentiality

The participants were entitled to share personal information to the extent they wished, and as a researcher, he had the obligation to maintain confidentiality. The management and storage of data were considered. In the event of study publication, the identity of the participants shall not be revealed.

c. Justice

The participants were treated fairly. The general results will be shared once the research is completed and the study's outcome is found beneficial. Researchers were accessible at any point of the study to clarify any information. There was no prejudicial treatment if the participants decided to quit after agreeing to participate.

d. Openness and Integrity

Full disclosure of the study to the participants. The nature of the study was fully described. They had the right to voluntarily participate in the study without the risk of incurring penalties or rewards; they also had the right to refuse participation or terminate it at any time without giving reasons and prejudice.

e. Compassion and Veracity

Honesty, truthfulness, and compassion were considered and observed during the entire duration of the study. These characteristics were significant in establishing trust and relationships with the participants. This helped them see the study's good intentions and their value as participants.

f. Beneficence and Maleficence

This was to protect the participants from any discomfort and harm, that one should do good. The study poses a minimal or temporary risk to the participants; questionnaires can elicit negative emotional responses. The entire process of answering questionnaires can evoke physical and mental fatigue.

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the research sample's demographics and other work-related data, followed by other research problems. This chapter presents the data collected, analyzed, and enriched by related studies such as published journals, research articles, theses, and dissertations.

Table 2

Demographic Profile and Work-related Variable of Informal Caregivers

Respondents' Profile	Frequency (N=60)	%
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	21	35
Female	39	65
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Single	27	45
Married	33	55
<i>Age (in years)</i>		
12-18 (Adolescent)	0	0
19-40 (Young Adult)	25	42
41-65 (Middle Aged Adults)	35	58
>65 (Old Adults)	0	0
<i>Education</i>		
High School	14	23.3
Diploma	17	28.3
Bachelor's degree	29	48.3
<i>Race</i>		
Emirati	16	26.7
Non-Emirate	44	73.3
<i>Employment</i>		
Employed	35	58.3
Unemployed	25	41.7
<i>Has your employment status changed because of your caregiving duties?</i>		
No	28	46.7
Yes	32	53.3

Respondents' Profile	Frequency (N=60)	%
<i>Employment status change</i>		
Change Job	5	12.5
File family/medical leave	12	37.5
Leave of absence	7	22
Decrease working hours	1	3
Early retirement	1	3
Have to quit the job	7	22
<i>Relationship to the person you cared for:</i>		
Husband	2	3.3
Wife	11	18.3
Son-in -law	0	0
Daughter-in-law	2	3.3
Brother	5	8.3
Sister	11	18.3
Mother	14	23.3
Father	10	16.7
Other (relative)	5	8.3
<i>Duration of care</i>		
Less than 6 months	9	15
6-11 months	21	35
1-3 years	23	38.3
3-5 years	6	10
More than 5 years	1	1.7
<i>Does the individual you are caring for live with you?</i>		
Yes	59	98.3
No	1	1.7
<i>Do you receive assistance from private Nurses or caregivers?</i>		
Yes	11	18.3
No	49	81.7

Table 2 shows the demographic profile and work-related variable of informal caregivers in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretation will be as follows.

Gender. In this study, the profile of the respondents is as follows: 65% of the participants were female. This result is similar to other studies conducted in other parts of the world, such as Turkey, the U.S.A., Columbia, Iran, and Spain. Varying estimates across different countries indicate that 56.8 % to 90% of all caregivers were women

(Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022; Tsai et al., 2021; Tan et al., 2021; Durante et al., 2019; Palacio et al., 2018; Hampton et al., 2018; Yildiz et al., 2017; Ellis et al., 2017; Unver et al., 2016; Havyer et al., 2016; Litzelman et al., 2016). Although caregivers were predominantly women, studies show that around 10 % to 44% were men; their numbers recently steadily increased, so much that they may constitute almost half of the primary caregivers (Sharma et al., 2016). Currently, the gender proportion of the U.A.E. comprises 68.58% male and 31.42% female (Global Media Insight, 2023); with this proportion, there may be a future shift in caregiver numbers.

In addition, according to Williams et al. (2017), females dominating the proportion of caregivers is most likely due to societies and cultures that endorse the traditional value of women as natural caregivers. Women are expected to care, and women must care. Women, on the other hand, adhere to these stereotypical gender norms that women are primary caregivers. In the same way, Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) mentioned that in the socio-cultural context, the responsibility of caring for children, the elderly, and family members with disabilities or sick is most of the time-integrated as part of the homemakers' responsibility. Traditionally, in Emirati culture, the society is based on patriarchy in which the father of the eldest male is the head of the family. Although the U.A.E. endorses gender equality by assuring equal rights for sexes in education, employment, and property, most Emirati women prefer marriage and raising children because, in U.A.E. society, this role places a high value (Countries and their Culture, n.d.). Due to gender disproportion, female caregivers suffer more from negative consequences of caregiving than males, such as psychological distress, physical health conditions, and other caregiving-related burdens (Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022; Durante et al., 2019; Yildiz et al., 2017; Unver et al., 2016; Sharma et al., 2016). Although caregiving is female-dominated, both men's and women's caregivers are

driven by a similar sense of affection, commitment, and family responsibility (Sharma et al., 2016).

Marital Status. More than half of the caregivers were married (55%), and the rest were single or widows. This result is consistent with other studies that show that most caregivers were married (Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022; Leung et al., 2020; Lloyd et al., 2019; Zoladl et al., 2019; Palacio et al., 2018; Ellis et al., 2017; Litzelman et al., 2016; Havyer et al., 2016; Unver et al., 2016). In Emirati society, although females have the same opportunities as males in all aspects, most Emirati women prefer marriage and raising children because this role is highly valued in U.A.E. society (Countries and their Culture, n.d.; Commisceo-global, 2020). Thus, the Emirati woman or wife in the family embraces the caring and nurturing responsibility within the household. This phenomenon is aligned with the socio-cultural context in which societies and cultures endorse the traditional value of women as natural caregivers, and women, on the other hand, adhere to these stereotypical gender norms that women are primary caregivers (Williams et al., 2017; Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022).

Age. Most caregivers were Middle-aged adults (41-65 years; 58%), followed by young adults (19-40 years; 28.3%). This result is similar to other study results in which the majority of their participants were Middle-aged adults (47 to 60 years old) (Durante et al., 2019; Lloyd et al., 2019; Hampton et al., 2018; Cianfrocca et al., 2018; Palacio et al., 2018; Havyer et al., 2016; Ellis et al., 2017). In the U.A.E., the majority of the population falls in the age group of 25 to 54 years, which can be attributed to the expatriate working population (Global Media Insight, 2023).

According to Erick Erickson's psychosocial Theory, Middle-aged adults are in a phase where they create and nurture by having children or creating positive change that benefits others. They continue to build their lives by focusing on career and family.

Being successful in this phase means that they are contributing to society by being active in their home and community (Cherry & Susman, 2022). The virtue that is achieved in this phase is care. They are proud of their accomplishments, witnessing their children grow into adults, and developing a sense of unity with wife/husband are essential accomplishments in this stage (Cherry & Susman, 2022).

On the other hand, young adults are at a stage in which they are exploring personal relationships by forming intimate, loving relationships with other people. Success in this stage forms a relationship that is enduring and secure. The virtue that is achieved in this phase is love. It is marked by the ability to form lasting, meaningful relationships with other people (Cherry & Susman, 2022).

Therefore, the ages of our participants were at the peak of the psychosocial stage, where they were building and securing relationships with others by caring and loving.

Education. All participants could attend school ranging from High School to Bachelor's degree. Almost half of them were Bachelor graduates (48.3%); this result was similar to Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) in Iran, in which the most minor educational attainment was High School (23.3%). The U.A.E. government views higher education as a significant instrument for development. The U.A.E. has the highest ratio of students entering higher education globally (Countries and their Culture, n.d). The U.A.E. government provides free education to its nationals from elementary to college. Expatriates, on the other hand, should pay out of their pocket. Some studies showed that education and training, specifically in caring, can improve self-efficacy (Havyer et al., 2016; Cianfrocca et al., 2018).

On the other hand, Yildiz et al. (2017) stated that caregivers with lower educational levels suffer more emotional stress and have worse physical health status

than those with higher educational levels. Unver et al. (2016) supported this statement since low levels of education have challenges in acquiring information or other support from nurses and other healthcare-related personnel, which causes stress and adds to the burden. In contrast, when caregivers understand the patient's illness, symptoms, and condition, their stress and anxiety are reduced, and their ability to cope with their problems increases (Zoladl et al., 2020). In this study, all our participants were educated, and challenges in any health-related issues, such as healthcare education, comprehension, and access, will not be as stressful as those who did not attend school.

Race. The majority of our participants were non-Emirati (73.3%), and the rest were Emiratis (26.7%). This disproportion is because most of the U.A.E.'s population comprises expatriates, who constitute 89% (T.G.M. Research, 2022). The Emiratis are the native Arab citizen population of U.A.E. The Non-Emirati is composed of expatriates, with the largest group from South Asia 49.88% (India 27.49%, Bangladesh 7.4%, Pakistan 12.69%), Egyptians 4.23%, Philippines 5.56% and others 38.55 (Global Media Insight, 2023).

According to Transcultural Nursing theory, cultural background influences a person's perception of health and how they will respond to health teachings. In Leininger's book (1991, pp 36-37, as cited in Añonuevo et al., 2000), she wrote:

“Culture as learned and transmitted values, beliefs, and practices that provide a critical means to establish culture care patterns from the people... Culture was seen as the blueprint for living, remaining healthy, or for dying. Care was culturally defined and known to people and especially how they saw and knew care from their context... These cultural care life experiences were influenced by specific cultural values, views about the world, social structure factors, language, ethnohistory, environmental context, and health care system.”

Many Islamic teachings influence the views of Muslims about health, illness, and dying, and it will be discussed as follows.

Culture and Social Stratification

The Emirati culture is a mix of Arabian, Islamic, and Persian cultures, with influences from the cultures of East Africa and the Indian Subcontinent (Countries and their Culture, n.d.). Emirati society is categorized into two: the nationals and the foreign immigrants. The Emirati citizens are divided into four social classes: 1. The ruling sheik, who holds the highest political position, power, and wealth; 2. Merchant class, who sell international consumer goods; 3. Middle-class professionals who have benefitted from free state education; 4. The newly settled Bedouin nomads, former pearl divers, and oasis farmers are low-income groups (Countries and their Culture, n.d.). Emiratis also have social symbol stratification; the male national is seen wearing the traditional dress of a white robe (candor), and women wear long black cloaks (abaya) and head cover (hijab) (Countries and their Culture, n.d.).

The Women and Men relative status.

Although women and men have equal rights and opportunities, patriarchal ideology is still visible in social life. Men receive employment preferences in a high administrative position. Women are not significant in religious life and politics, as these are considered male domains. Most decision-making must be conferred by the husband or eldest male in the family, including health-related decisions (Countries and their Culture, n.d.).

Welfare System

Emiratis and non-Emiratis benefit in different ways. Emirati nationals benefit from the welfare system, such as womb-to-tomb free services, free universal health care, education, social security, family allowances, electricity and water, and housing for low-income groups (Countries and their Culture, n.d.). This is their method of distributing the oil wealth among the locals. On the other hand, the immigrant population also benefits to some extent, particularly regarding medical care. Suppose an expat does not have or has expired insurance and gets severely sick. In that case, government hospitals still provide all the medical care needed, such as chemotherapy and dialysis, and will arrange transportation/ flights to send them back home. Also, employers and sponsors of foreign expats are responsible for providing health insurance coverage for their employees and their families (1 spouse and 3 children under 18 years) (U.A.E. Government portal, 2023). However, if an expatriate is not employed, they must take out private insurance to cover medical bills. These differences in benefits between Emirati and Non-Emirati give a glimpse of the socioeconomic gap connected to living conditions, health, leisure and food, social environment, and social life.

Religion and Beliefs

Islam is the official religion and is the dominating religion in the United Arab Emirates, which is approximately 76% of the population (Wikipedia, 2023). There are two branches of Islam, Sunni and Shi'a groups; they have much more in common in their beliefs and practices than differences (Pruitt, 2022). However, when Muslims from different backgrounds are compared, they have varying cultures even though they share the same core spiritual practices (Attun et al.,2023). The primary religion in

the U.A.E. is Sunni Muslim, which has a prominent influence on local architecture, music, attire, cuisine, health perception, and lifestyle (Commisceo-global, 2020; Wikipedia, 2023).

The study by Elbarazi et al. (2017) showed that 81% of Emirati participants said their religious beliefs influenced their perception of health. The theme that explains these influences were “fatalism’ and ‘preservation of life.’ Under the subtheme of fatalism, the respondents answered the most to the Inevitability and invincibility sub-theme, in which God preordains powerlessness to change health status. On the other hand, under “preservation of life’, most of them appreciate life, expressing willingness to endure suffering and disability with patience in the expectation of rewards in the hereafter. This study only shows that anything out of their control is in the control of God, and suffering and dying are considered a test from Allah (Elbarazi et al.,2017).

Islamic Belief and Influence on Health Perception

Many Islamic teachings influence the views of Muslims about health, illness, and dying. Muslims believe in absolute timeless knowledge of God (Al Qadaanwal Qadar), fate, destiny, and the supreme power of God over human life (Elbarazi et al.,2017). With this belief, any illness that they cannot control is predestined. On the contrary, Islam also teaches that they have choices over their actions and should protect their health and preserve life. The Prophet Muhammad's teaching mentioned that preserving life and health is an act of worship and being highly praised by God (Elbarazi et al.,2017; Attun et al.,2023). This belief can quickly reinforce motivation for health preservation and illness prevention action. In addition, the Quran also encourages Muslims to accept illness, suffering, and dying with patience, and calamities can absolve the sins of a pious Muslim (Elbarazi et al.,2017; Attun et al., 2023). The concepts of submission, acceptance, fatalism, and inevitability give

direction to Muslims to make important decisions about health as a gift from God and endure with patience and acceptance the suffering and disability in expectation of rewards in the hereafter (Elbarazi et al.,2017) Congenital disability is considered as a test of their faith in God Attun et al.,2023

Other Islamic teachings affect health practices, such as choices of food. It is prohibited to eat pork and its by-products, alcohol, animal fats, and meat that has not been slaughtered according to Islamic custom (Attun et al.,2023; Queensland Health (n.d.). At the time of their holy month, known as Ramadan, most Muslims fast; however, sick, young, and old are excused from this practice if it is detrimental to their health. Fasting for Muslims is a form of purifying the body and soul (Attun et al.,2023; Queensland Health (n.d.).

The way of dressing also affects health practices; Islam requires both men and women to dress modestly. For men, this means keeping the area between the navel and knees covered; for women, only the face, hands, and feet are exposed (Attun et al.,2023). The modesty practice can affect the health care assessment as some patients do not want to expose their bodies; family members are usually present during the examination, or same-sex practitioners can attend to them (Attun et al.,2023; Queensland Health (n.d.). Male doctors may have to communicate through a spouse if the patient is female. Beards are religious symbolic in men, most of them. Avoid shaving unless it is essential (Attun et al.,2023).

Regarding organ donation and transplant, some Muslims accept these procedures, and others believe it is unacceptable (Attun et al.,2023; Queensland et al.).

For reproductive health, contraception is permitted temporarily under certain conditions. However, permanent contraceptives such as vasectomy and tubal ligation

are only allowed if the woman's health is at risk from additional pregnancies (Queensland Health, n.d.). Abortion, on the other hand, is permitted prior to 120 days under certain circumstances and is not permitted as a method of family planning. In assisted reproductive technologies, it is generally accepted in Islam. However, sperm donor, surrogacy, and sperm that has been cryopreserved are prohibited if the father has died (Queensland Health, n.d.).

Given death and dying, they believe that God predestines death. If a Muslim patient is in the final stage of a terminal illness, Islam does not require treatment, and under the circumstances, disconnection from the life support system is permitted. Suicide and euthanasia are forbidden. However, if a patient suffers from a terminal condition and has no hope of recovery, it is allowed to stop medical treatment (Queensland Health, n.d.). Even that is the case in their faith and culture, do not resuscitate orders from doctors are not yet widely accepted, this is because Quran encourages Muslims to accept illness, suffering, and dying with patience (Attun et al.,2023; Elbarazi et al.,2017)

In the Transcultural Nursing theory, nurses are responsible for understanding the role of Culture in the patient's health. Not only can a cultural background influence a patient's health, but the patient may also be taking home remedies that can affect his or her health (Añonuevo et al., 2000).

Employment status. In this study, more than half of the caregivers (58.3%) were employed, and more than half experienced changes in work status (53.3%). Most of them have to file family/medical leave to attend to the needs of the care recipient (37.5%), followed by quitting their job (22%), filing a leave of absence (22%), decreasing their working hours (3%) and early retirement (3%). According to Wade-Bohleber et al. (2020), the association between higher self-esteem and efficacy and

lower stress levels was more pronounced in employed youth than in unemployed youth across several dimensions of stress. On the other hand, the study by Yildiz et al. (2017) showed that the burden of the unemployed was more than employed. In contrast, Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) study showed that employed caregivers had more care burden than the unemployed. Thus, employment can be a source to divert caregivers' attention from caregiving responsibilities and increase their self-efficacy or a source of burden or stress to provide financial aid to sick family members.

As expected, changing employment status due to caring affects financial status, but this is only a little of the case amongst Emiratis. In the U.A.E., companies must hire a percentage of Emiratis; otherwise, they will pay (U.A.E. et al.). This is because of Emiratization, a government's advocacy to increase and preserve Emirati culture and identity by employing Emiratis in the workforce. To encourage more Emiratis to join the workforce, the government has salary support for Emirati graduates of Dhs 5,000 monthly for 5 years for university graduates and one-year salary support of Dhs 8,000 a month for skilled Emiratis under training (Sebugwaano, 2023). This is on top of their basic salary from the company. So, Emiratis have higher financial capability than that of an expat. So, unlike expats, they still have allowances even if they shift or temporarily stop working. On the other hand, expatriates, if one of the couples stops working or the primary carer is the sole provider and has to stop working, their financial status change can be felt tremendously, and maybe one of their responsibilities, such as sending money back home, might be halted. The limitation of this study is identifying the specific number of Emiratis that have changed their job condition, as well as their salary bracket.

Relationship. In this study, regarding the relationship of carers to recipients, most of them were mothers (23.3%), followed by wives (18.3%) and sisters (18.3%). This shows that Emirati women embrace the caring and rearing responsibility of the household as a woman of the house. This result is in contrast with other studies in which the majority of the relationships were wife-patient and children-patient relationships (Tan et al., 2021; Durante et al., 2019; Zoladl et al., 2019; Cianfrocca et al., 2018; Palacio et al., 2018) (Unver et al., 2016; Havyer et al., 2016; Ellis et al., 2017; Litzelman et al., 2016). In the U.A.E., even though Emirati women were given equal rights and opportunities with males, most women chose marriage and raising children, because this role in society places a high value (Countries and their Culture, n.d.). This shows that women are responsible for caring for the house, most likely due to societies and cultures that endorse the traditional value of a woman as a natural caregiver. Women are expected to care, and women must care. Conversely, women adhered to these stereotypical gender norms that women are primary caregivers (Williams et al., 2017).

Duration of care. In this study, most participants cared for their recipients for 1-3 years (38.3%), and few reached more than 5 years (1.7%). The majority of the participants are recipients of 1-3 years. The limitation of this study is not including O.P.D. Cancer patients, in which the chances of meeting participants rendering care longer than three years, were not included. Despite this limitation, studies support that routine training and self-efficacy were associated; lack of training is associated with low self-efficacy (Havyer et al., 2016; Hendrix et al. (2016). Therefore, the longer the informal caregiver renders care, the longer the exposure and repetitive care skills, and the higher their self-efficacy in giving care.

On the other hand, according to Yildiz et al. (2017) study, as the caregiving period increases, the burden of care increases. On the contrary, Durante's study (2019) showed that fewer hours of caregiving per week has higher social and emotional burdens. Durante (2019) mentioned that this phenomenon can be because less time spent with patients affects their relationship. More time spent with patients means better relationships, which can attenuate burden. More time devoted to caring also bring about appreciation from other family members, colleagues, and friends, which could reduce the caregiving burden.

Living Condition. In this study, almost all participants lived with their care recipients (98.3%), and few were not living together (1.7%). This is consistent with the Tsai et al. (2021) study in which 91.5% of caregivers lived with their care recipient. In this study, 81.7% of the participants care for their care recipients alone, without assistance from private nurses in their homes. On the other hand, 18.3% hired private nurses to assist them in caring for their sick family members. It is also customary in every Emirati household that each household employs two live-in domestic servants, usually Asian; this helps the woman in managing the house. (Countries and their Culture, n.d.; Commisceo-global, 2020). Caregiving is demanding, and no one is equipped to do it alone. Otherwise, they are at risk for caregiving adverse effects. Having a private nurse, another family member, or a domestic servant to help is a form of respite care that relieves caregiving demands or decreases other household obligations. According to Liao et al. (2022), caregivers who utilized in-house respite care decreased significantly compared to nonusers' caregiver burden scores.

Table 3

Level of Self-efficacy of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates

Self-Efficacy Dimensions	Mean Score	SD
A. Managing medical information self-efficacy		
1. Coping with information overload	8.27	0.84
14. Understanding medical information from doctors, nurses, or other sources	8.12	1.01
19. Asking physicians and nurses questions	8.12	0.96
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>8.17</i>	<i>0.94</i>
B. Caring for care recipient self-efficacy.		
2. Listening and learning from the person as to how to care better for him/her	8.33	0.93
6. Being able to notice the “good moments” in caregiving when they occur	8.25	0.93
7. Allowing the person to have and express his/her feelings	7.27	1.53
8. Assisting the person with Activities, such as feeding, washing, dressing, or toileting	8.45	0.87
13. Providing emotional support to the person I am caring for	8.30	0.91
18. Assisting and encouraging the person in following through with all treatments and taking all prescribed medications	8.40	0.81
21. Maintaining a close relationship with the person I am caring for	8.48	0.56
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>8.21</i>	<i>1.04</i>
C. Caring for oneself self-efficacy.		
3. Letting go of things I cannot control	5.80	2.26
9. Continuing to take care of yourself (for example: exercise, diet, sleep)	6.00	1.70
11. Continuing to engage in personal activities that you like to do	3.30	2.23
15. Seeking support for yourself	7.77	1.37
16. Dealing with feelings of helplessness	6.10	1.54
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>5.79</i>	<i>2.34</i>

Self-Efficacy Dimensions	Mean Score	SD
D. Managing complex interactions and emotions self-efficacy.	4.30	2.25
4. Expressing negative feelings about the illness	7.07	1.82
5. Maintaining hope	6.05	2.26
10. Talking openly and honestly with the person	3.12	1.80
12. Talking about death and dying	7.07	1.87
17. Dealing with the person expressing negative feelings toward you when they occur	7.83	1.06
20. Dealing with criticism from others	5.91	2.51
<i>Composite Mean</i>		
General	28.08	1.71

Self-efficacy Interpretation:

CGI (Individual)	CGI (General)
1.00- 3.67 - Low	1-12 - Low
3.68-6.34 - Moderate	13-24 - Moderate
6.35- 9.00 - High	25-36 – High

Table 3 shows the level of self-efficacy of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretations are as follows.

In caregiving, self-efficacy is the caregiver's belief or perception of his or her capability to accomplish the demands of caregiving (Hampton & Newcomb, 2018; Nogales-Gonzalez, 2015). This study tackles the general caregiving self-efficacy of caregivers caring for terminally ill family members and the four caregiving self-efficacy dimensions: Caring for oneself self-efficacy, Managing medical information self-efficacy, Caring for care recipient self-efficacy, and Managing difficult interactions and emotions self-efficacy.

In this study, the general result of self-efficacy in caregiving of informal caregivers was High (M- 28.08; SD- 1.71), which is similar to the study result of Unver et al. (2016) but with a higher result compared to the study result of Hampton et al.,

(2019) and Yildiz et al., (2017). The study results also showed High levels in two self-efficacy dimensions: *Caring for care recipients* (M- 8.21; SD- 1.04) and *Managing medical information* (M- 8.17; SD- 0.94). Moderate Self-efficacy followed her in two other dimensions: *Managing difficult interactions and emotions* (M- 5.91; SD- 2.51) and *Caring for oneself* (M- 5.79; SD- 2.34).

Caregivers were most confident in *Caring for care recipients* (M- 8.21; SD- 1.04). This result is similar to the Hampton et al. (2019) study in which caregivers had the highest level of confidence in caring for the care recipient and the lowest level of confidence in caring for themselves. In *the Caring for care recipient* dimension, caregivers have High Self-efficacy in *maintaining a close relationship with the person they care for* (M8.48; SD 0.56), followed by *assisting the person with activities, such as feeding, washing, dressing, or toileting* (M- 8.45; S 0.87). The least self-efficacy subdimension in *Caring for a care recipient* was *allowing the person to have and express his/her feelings* (M- 7.27; S- 0.87).

Caregivers in this study have high *Self-Efficacy in Caring for Their Care Recipients*. According to several studies, self-efficacy can be improved through training and education (Cianfrocca et al., 2018; Palacio et al., 2in18; Havyer et al., 2016; Handrix et al., 2016;). This result is most likely due to the basic caregiving information that Tawam Hospital provides as part of its comprehensive cancer care program. However, the caregivers have the lowest score in *Caring for One Self-Efficacy*. This result reflects that the support caregivers received was practical demands for caregiving, like feeding, washing, dressing, and toileting, but not including health information.

On the other hand, the lowest score among the four main dimensions was *Caring for Themselves* (M- 5.79; SD- 2.34). Although it was the lowest scored self-

efficacy, the level was Moderate. Under *the Caring for Themselves* self-efficacy dimension, caregivers have High self-efficacy in seeking support for themselves (M-7.77; SD- 1.37) but are not at all confident in continuing to engage in personal activities that they like to do (M-3.30; SD- 2.23). This is likely due to investing more time with patients and ignoring their care needs (Durante, 2019; Palacio et al., 2017). In this study, caregivers suffer from a Time dependence burden, in which they struggle with a personal time restriction, another factor contributing to ignoring their needs. The study by Durante et al. (2019) shows that the more time caregivers spend with the care recipients, the less emotional burden they have; this can be another reason they devote more time to caregiving and less to themselves.

Another significant result of this study is that caregivers were Not confident (self-efficacy) in talking about death and dying; it was the least-scored subdimension (M-3.12; SD- 1.80). The study conducted by Bergeholtz et al. 2020, revealed that talking about end-of-life differed widely. End-of-life conversation was an individualize matter, ranging from not wanting to talk about it to being ready to plan burial, and expecting doctors and nurses to open a conversation about it (Bergeholtz et al., 2020). There are several reasons why there is difficulty talking about death and dying; some of the reasons are not wanting to face the reality of the end of life, not having the time to become involved, and not having the emotional reserves to deal with such an intense situation (Morrow, 2021).

In Islamic teachings, Muslims believe in the absolute timeless knowledge of God (Al Qadaanwal Qadar), fate, destiny, and the supreme power of GOD over human life (Elbarazi et al.,2017). With this belief, any illness that they cannot control is predestined. In addition, the teaching of Prophet Muhammad mentioned that preserving life and health is an act of worship and being highly praised by God

(Elbarazi et al.,2017; Attun et al.,2023). The concepts of submission, acceptance, fatalism, and inevitability lead Muslims to make important decisions about life and health as a gift from God and endure with patience and acceptance the suffering and disability in expectation of rewards hereafter (Elbarazi et al.,2017). With these teachings, not talking about death and dying can be their way of “Preserving life” until the end to show that they persevered with patience and accepted suffering. “Preservation of life” until the end, according to their Prophet, is an act of worship highly praised by God and rewards in the hereafter (Elbarazi et al.,2017). Do Not Resuscitate/ Do Not Intubate orders from doctors are not yet widely accepted in Emirati culture.

On the other hand, under “preservation of life’, most of them appreciate life, expressing willingness to endure suffering and disability with patience in the expectation of rewards in the hereafter.

Table 4

Level of Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates

Caregiver Burden	Mean	SD
Time Dependence or Objective Burden		
1. My care receiver needs my help to perform many daily tasks.	3.00	0.92
2. My care receiver is dependent on me.	3.05	0.87
3. I have to watch my care receiver constantly.	3.17	0.78
4. I have helped my care receiver with many essential functions.	2.83	1.17
5. I do not have a minute’s break from my caregiving chores.	2.15	1.16
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>2.84</i>	<i>0.98</i>
Developmental Burden		
6. I am missing out on life.	1.85	1.09
7. I wish I could escape from this situation.	2.75	1.20

Caregiver Burden	Mean	SD
8. My social life has suffered.	2.30	1.36
9. I feel emotionally drained due to caring for my care receiver.	2.23	1.28
10. I expect things to be different at this point.	2.37	1.21
<i>Composite Mean</i>	2.28	1.26
Emotional Burden		
20. I feel embarrassed by my care receiver's behavior.	0.30	0.81
21. I feel ashamed of my care receiver.	0.12	0.37
22. I resent my care receiver.	0.03	0.26
23. I feel uncomfortable when I have friends over.	0.03	0.26
24. I feel angry about my reactions toward my care receiver.	0.07	0.31
<i>Composite Mean</i>	0.11	0.46
Physical Burden		
11. I am not getting enough sleep.	2.32	1.03
12. My health has suffered.	1.63	1.21
13. Caregiving has made me physically ill.	1.63	1.21
14. I'm physically tired.	2.15	1.26
<i>Composite Mean</i>	1.93	1.21
Social Burden		
15. I do not get along with other family members as I used to.	0.48	0.75
16. Others do not appreciate my caregiving efforts in my family.	0.73	1.25
17. I have had problems with my marriage.	0.10	0.35
18. I do not do as well at work as I used to.	0.83	0.89
19. I resent other relatives who could but do not help.	0.55	0.91
<i>Composite Mean</i>	0.54	0.91
General Score	36.67	0.22

Caregiver Burden Inventory Interpretation:

CBI (Individual)

- 0.00-0.80 - No burden
- 0.81-1.60 - Low burden
- 1.61-2.40 - Moderate burden
- 2.41-3.20 - High Burden
- 3.21-4.00 - Very High Burden

CBI (General)

- > 36 – High Risk for burnout
- <36 – 24 at Risk and Needs to seek some form of respite care
- < 24 – Does not need respite care

Table 4 shows the level of caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretations are as follows.

Caregiver burden is the strain or load borne by a caregiver for caring. It has multiple responses to one's physical, emotional, social, psychological, and financial stressors connected to the caregiving experience (Hiseman & Fackrell, 2017). Caregiver burden was assessed in many different lights, closely related to burden. For instance, some researchers used stress, well-being, physical suffering, distress, quality of life, and depression and anxiety as critical variables to measure burden. (Deyhoul et al., 2020; Sultan et al, 2020; Durante et al., 2019; Zoladl et al., 2019; Araki, 2019; Hampton & Newcomb, 2018; Palacio et al., 2018; Yildiz et al, 2017; Ellis et al 2017; Litzelman et al., 2016; Unver et al, 2016). This study determined the general level of burden of caregivers as well as the type of burden.

In this study, the general burden of caregivers of terminally ill patients in UAE presents that they were at *High Risk for Burn Out* or, in other words, severe level, and needed some form of respite care (M-36.67; SD- 0.22). Other study results show that caregivers' burden ranges from moderate to intense (Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022; Zoladl, 2020; Cianfrocca et al., 2018; Yildiz et al., 2017; Unver et al., 2016). Differences in results can be due to differences in study type, type of illness, instruments, settings, and support from the healthcare system. According to Hampton

et al. (2019), self-efficacy in *Caring For Oneself* and *Perceived stress* in caregiving were significantly related, but not the other three self-efficacy dimensions (medical information self-efficacy, caring for care recipient self-efficacy, and managing difficult interactions and emotions self-efficacy). In the Hampton et al. (2019) study, the participants scored the least in *caring* for themselves and reported high levels of perceived stress. Hampton's study results were similar to this study's; participants scored least in *caring* for self-efficacy, and we can assume that is the reason for the high total burden score. The limitation of this study is that the relationship of each self-efficacy subdimension to the burden subdimension and vice versa still needs to be addressed. In addition, the burden level of caregivers can be due to the two main reasons caregivers do not have time for themselves: the feeling that they are not in sync with their peers and missing out on their lives.

In this study, among the caregiver burden dimension, caregivers felt that *Time Dependence or Objective* was at a *High burdensome level*, and among the four burden domains, this was considered the highest form of burden. (M-2.84, SD- 0.98). Time Dependence, or objective burden, is stress caused by a restriction of one's personal time or family member's time (Novack & Guest, 1989, as cited in Cianfrocca et al.,2018). In the Time dependence domain, they felt *High burdensome level* in the following subdomain (arranged in high to low order): they have to watch the care receiver constantly (M- 3.17; SD – 0.78); dependent on them (M- 3.05; SD 0.87); care receiver needs help to perform many task (M- 3.00; SD -0.92); and have to help them with many essential functions (M-2.83; SD- 1.17); and at *Moderately burdensome level* when they do not have a minute break from caregiving chores (M-2.15; SD 1.16). This study result is similar to the study of Cianfrocca et al. 2018 and Sheikhbardsiri et

al. 2022, in which the highest form of burden is *Time dependence*. Caregivers do not have spare time to spend with themselves and other family members.

Although UAE society is family- and kin-oriented, this is only significant in social identification and one stands in the community. Most families prefer to live in the same neighborhood as their kin. However, over 80 percent of national households live as nuclear families in their own houses (Countries and their Culture, n.d.). This shows that their care responsibility heavily depends on the nuclear unit of the family, primarily on the women in the family. This also applies to expats who do not have extended family with them.

Moreover, according to Tsai et al., 2021, the number of care hours is correlated with ADL dependency of the patient. The fact that the Time dependence burden was the worst burden experienced in this study indirectly reflects the dependency of the care receiver on the family caregiver to meet their daily needs to maintain health or to survive. These help needs may extend from daily living activities, taking medication, and assisting them in medical check-ups and treatments, in which caregivers spend a significant amount of time to meet the demands.

The second burden they experience is *Developmental Burden* (M- 2.28; SD- 1.26), which refers to caregivers feeling out of sync with their peers or missing out on their lives. Under this subdomain (arranged in high to low order), caregivers in this study wished that they could escape from their situation (M-2.75; SD 1.20), and this was rated as a *High burdensome level*. They rated the following subdomain as *Moderately burdensome level*: they are expecting things to be different at this point of their life (M – 2.37; SD 1.21); they felt that their social life had suffered (M- 2.30; SD- 1.36); they felt emotionally drained due to caregiving (M- 2.23; SD 1.28), and they felt that they were missing out of their life (M- 1.85; SD-1.09). This is in conjunction with

the Time dependence burden, in which they do not have time to themselves because of care responsibility and family dynamics. In contrast, in the study of Cianfrocca et al. (2018), this domain was the least scored type of burden in caring for oncological and neurological chronic disease. Cianfrocca et al. (2018) conducted a theoretical training course for caregivers, decreasing the Developmental Burden. This only shows the effectiveness of changing one's perception of role, which can make caregivers more conscious of their role and understand and accept better the significance of their actions in terms of quality of life, safety, and patient outcomes (Cianfrocca et al., 2018).

Physical burden: Caregivers also claimed that they did not get enough sleep (M- 2.32; SD 1.03) and felt physically tired (M- 2.15; SD 1.26); they rated these feelings as *Moderately burdensome level*. In the study of Sheikhbardsiri et al. 2022, this is the least scored domain; he mentioned that the results' inconsistencies could be due to different recovery periods of patients. For instance, a COVID-19 patient recovers faster than a dialysis patient. Therefore, the latter needs more assistance in care. Furthermore, since most caregivers were middle-aged adults, these age groups usually already have an underlying condition that makes it more difficult to care for themselves and the patient. It is more burdensome, especially if they need assistance in toileting at night or in an unstable condition that demands extra effort and time and disrupts standard sleep patterns. The caregivers felt moderately burdensome, most probably because this study's patients depended on grooming, which requires fine motor skills.

Among the types of burden, the least-scored type is *Emotional Burden* (M- 0.11; SD 0.46). Emotional burden refers to any embarrassment or feeling of shame toward the patient. They do not feel embarrassed (M-0.30; SD-0.81), ashamed (M- 0.12; SD-0.37), angry (M-0.07; SD-0.31), and resent (M-0.03; SD-0.26) to their care

receiver nor felt uncomfortable when their friends are visiting (M=0.03; SD=0.26), they felt no emotional burden at all. In contrast to this study, Cianfrocca et al. (2018) study result shows that Emotional burden is the second scored type of burden that they felt in carrying for oncological and neurological chronic disease. This study shows that although they felt they missed opportunities and were restricted in their personal or family member's time (Time and Development burden), they were not ashamed or had ill feelings towards their care receiver. The level of acceptance can be rooted in gender roles imposed by society, the expectation from the family to the family member's caregiver, or the emotional bond that develops between the caregiver and care recipient (Williams et al., 2017). Emirati women embrace the caring and rearing responsibility of the household as a woman of the house. In UAE, most women choose marriage and raising children even though the government prioritizes them in educational and job opportunities. This is because UAE society places a high value on these roles (Countries and their Culture, n.d.).

Table 5

Level of Activity of Daily Living (A.D.L.) Independence of Care Recipients in the United Arab Emirates

Type of Activity of Daily Living	Mean Score	Total Score (x 50)	Level of Dependency
Feeding	1.83	91.5	Slight
Bathing	1.75	87.5	Moderate
Grooming	1.13	56.5	Severe
Dressing	1.82	91	Slight
Bowel	1.67	83.5	Moderate
Bladder	1.67	83.5	Moderate
Toilet Use	1.82	91	Slight
Transfer	2.28	114	Independent
Mobility	2.18	109	Independent
Stairs	1.72	86	Moderate

Interpretation:

- 0 - 20
 - indicate "total" dependency.
 - No participation by the care receiver in any aspect of the A.D.L. activity. There was full staff performance of an activity.
- 21 - 60
 - indicate "severe" dependency
 - Extensive assistance: The patient performed part of A.D.L. but needed weight-bearing support.
 - Weight-bearing assistance encompasses the physical assistance provided when the caregiver flexes a muscle and uses 25%-75% effort.
- 61 - 90
 - indicate "moderate" dependence
 - The care receiver was highly involved in the activity and received physical
 - help in guided maneuvering of limb(s) or other non-weight-bearing assistance
 - Guided Maneuvering and Non-weight bearing means that the caregiver did not flex his/her muscles while helping the resident. Only lightly touched the patient to guide a hand or a shoulder.
- 91 - 99
 - indicates "slight" dependency.
 - Care receivers need oversight (monitoring and standing by), encouragement, or cueing.
- >100
 - indicates independent."
 - if the care recipient completed the activity with no help or oversight

Table 5 shows the level of activity of daily living (A.D.L.) independence of care recipients in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretation are as follows.

In this study, care recipients were independent in transferring (M- 2.28) and mobilizing (M- 2.18) and, in contrast, were severely dependent in terms of grooming (M- 1.13). Grooming involves nail care and activities of brushing and combing hair. In contrast to transfer and mobility activities, grooming involves fine motor skills, which involve using smaller muscles of the hands. Thus, in A.D.L., care recipients in this study were severely dependent on fine motor activities. Although the care-recipients-needs for other A.D.L.s, such as feeding, bathing, dressing, and toileting, were *slight to moderate*, they still require assistance, effort, and time from the caregivers.

Studies could be more extensive regarding self-efficacy and care recipients' A.D.L. However, according to this study's results, the more dependent our patients were on task, the higher the caregivers' self-efficacy.

On the other hand, in terms of burden, the study of Tsai et al., 2021 and Unver et al., 2016, shows that burden and A.D.L. were positively associated. It was found that there was much burden for those caring for dependent older adults. Moreover, the A.D.L. dependency of the patient is correlated with the number of care hours. According to Tsai et al., 2021, it is the only factor independently associated with missing hours at work or absences from work for those employed. In this study, 53% have to make job changes and adjustments. A patient's dependency on A.D.L. means an increase in care hours that need to be spent, and if it is not well managed, it can lead to a *Time Dependence burden*. In time, missing their secular job can also create the feeling that they are not in sync with their peers, eventually leading to a *developmental burden*. Some studies proved that improving A.D.L.'s performance in stroke decreases caregivers' burden (Sahai et al., 2018; Deyhould et al., 2020). In

addition, the study of way J et al. (2023) proved that physical therapy can improve caregiver burden experience. Thus, physical therapy can decrease the caregiver burden experience by improving the care recipient's function.

Table 6

Relationship of Overall Caregiver Self-efficacy and Overall Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill in the United Arab Emirates

Variables	Spearman's rho	Interpretation	p-value
Overall caregiver self-efficacy VS. Overall caregiver burden	- 0.12	Very weak negative relationship	0.42

$\alpha = 0.05$, level of significance

Table 6 shows the relationship between overall caregiver self-efficacy and overall caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretations are as follows.

In this study, the overall result of self-efficacy in caregiving was High (M- 28.08; SD- 1.71), especially in *Caring for care recipients* (M- 8.33; SD- 1.04) and *Managing medical information* (M- 8.17; SD- 0.94). On the other hand, the overall caregiver burden results showed that they were at high risk for burn or, in other words, severe level, especially in *the Time dependence burden* domain (M-2.84, SD- 0.98).

Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between total caregiver self-efficacy and the total caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill. As a result, the two main variables were *very weak negative correlations*, $r_s(58) = -.12$, $p = .42$, $N = 60$ at $\alpha = .05$. As caregiver self-efficacy increases, the caregiver burden decreases. However, the relationship between the two variables was not statistically significant. This means that their self-efficacy in

caregiving, regardless of whether it improves or declines, is not related to caregiver burden and vice versa. The reason for a weak relationship can be due to inadequate sample size.

Their self-efficacy in caregiving was High because of the education comprehensive cancer care program they received from Tawam Hospital. Education plays a significant role in improving their self-efficacy; all of the participants in this study were educated. Their total caregiver burden was at the highest level; however, our study result does not affect their confidence in performing their care responsibility. The participants in this study experienced the burden the most in the Time Dependence dimension, in which they suffered time constraints in doing responsibilities other than caring. Most of the participants in this study were employed (58.3%) and married (55%). The limitation of this study is determining the relation between each self-efficacy-subdimension and caregiver burden-subdimension.

The study result is opposite to other studies, in which they showed that there is a relationship between these two variables (Sultan et al., 2020; Scicolone et al., 2018; Havyer et al., 2017; Ylidiz et al., 2017; Ellis et al., 2017; Leung at al., 2017; Hendrix et al., 2016; Unver et al., 2016). Most studies would agree that self-efficacy and burden have a negative relationship, like the study by Hampton et al. (2019). It shows that *self-efficacy in caring* for oneself and *perceived stress* in caregiving were significantly related, but not the other three self-efficacy dimensions (Hampton et al., 2019); the participants scored the least in caring for themselves and reported high levels of perceived stress, presence of more anxiety and depression. Other similar studies also show that self-efficacy and burden were negatively related; the higher the burden, the lower the self-efficacy (Ellis et al., 2017; Yildiz et al.,2017; Unver et al., 2016). Since self-efficacy and caregiver burden were related to most studies, most researchers were

improving self-efficacy to decrease the adverse effects of caregiving. Other studies proved that self-efficacy can act as an attenuating or buffer variable for adverse effects of caregiving, such as decreasing caregiver burden and stress, improving well-being, as well as patient outcome (Sultan et al., 2020; Deyhoul et al., 2019; Hendrix et al., 2016). Several studies show that improving self-efficacy is through education, other forms of skill improvement, and empowerment programs. (Sultan et al., 2020; Deyhoul et al., 2019; Cianfrocca et al., 2018). According to Bandura's self-efficacy theory, one's belief in the capability to manage a particular situation is related to better outcomes. Thus, identifying what kind of efficacy to improve is crucial since needs are individualized. The inconsistent results in different studies prove that needs differ across individuals or cases. However, the sustainability of self-efficacy improvements is in question due to the limitations of studies. The Hendrix et al., 2016) study shows that the training program successfully improved self-efficacy and decreased caregivers' stress and preparedness. However, it did not last long. The lack of sustainability of the result may be related to a single dose of nature and the changing needs of caregivers. Lastly, self-efficacy can mediate the distress and burden in caregiving and can improve well-being in caregiving (Deyhoul et al., 2020; Sultan et al., 2020; Sahai et al., 2018; Scicolone, 2018; Ellis et al., 2017; Leung et al., 2017; Yildiz et al., 2017; Unver et al., 2016).

Table 7.a

Relationship of Overall Self-efficacy of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates and Demographic and Work-related Profiles

Variables	Spearman's rho	Strength of Correlation	p-value
Age	-.127	Very weak	0.33
Educational Degree	-.093	Very weak	0.48
Caregiving Duration	.301*	Weak	0.02

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation:

Range of absolute correlation coefficient (r_s)	Strength of Correlation
0.8- 1.00	Very strong
0.60-0.79	Strong
0.40-0.59	Moderate
0.20- 0.39	Weak
0-0.19	Very Weak

Table 7.b

Relationship of Overall Self-efficacy of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates and Demographic and Work-related Profiles

Variables	Chi-Square (χ^2)	df	p-value
Sex	19.34	26	0.82
Marital Status	31.71	26	0.20
Race	28.04	26	0.36
Employment Status	19.54	26	0.81
Relationship	196.82	182	0.21
Change of Employment	23.84	26	0.59
Living with the care recipient	14.24	26	0.97
With the assistance of private caregivers	36.07	26	0.09

<0.05 level of significance

Table 7.a and Table 7.b show the relationship between the self-efficacy of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates and demographic and work-related profiles, discussions, and interpretations as follows.

Age and Self-Efficacy. This study shows that self-efficacy and age have a *fragile negative relationship* ($r_s -0.127$; $p 0.334$); this means that as age advances, self-efficacy also declines. However, this relationship is not significantly correlated. This means that the caregiver's self-efficacy is not affected by age. Most participants were middle-aged adults (58%), but this does not determine self-efficacy. A young adult can feel self-confident in caring as a middle-aged adult does. Self-efficacy can be gained in any age group. However, this is refuted by Tan et al. (2021), in which there was positive association between age and self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts. According to Tan et al. (2021), older people remember and pay attention to more positive than negative stimuli. Thus, older caregivers can control upsetting thoughts about caregiving than younger caregivers.

Education and Self-Efficacy. This study shows that self-efficacy and education have a *weak negative relationship* ($r_s - 0.93$; $p 0.478$); this means that as individual education advances, self-efficacy or confidence decreases, but the relationship is not that strong. This can be due to a small sample size. However, this study shows no significant relationship between education and self-efficacy; the correlation was insignificant. This means that educational attainment (e.g., Master's, bachelor's, etc.) does not define a person's self-efficacy or confidence in caring for terminally ill family members.

On the other hand, some studies showed that education and training, specifically in caring, can improve self-efficacy. The study of Havyer et al. (2016) shows that routine training in cancer care and self-efficacy were associated, and lack

of training was associated with low self-efficacy. Another study by Cianfrocca et al. (2018) shows that multidisciplinary educational course on the burden, health literacy, and the needs of family caregivers improved their well-being. Caregivers became more conscious of their role and better understood the significance of their actions in terms of quality of life, safety, and patient outcomes Cianfrocca et al. (2018).

Similarly, the study of Hendrix et al. (2016) shows that training programs improved caregiver self-efficacy for cancer symptom management and in preparation for caregiving. In this study, all participants were educated (100%). However, educational attainment such as a master's or bachelors does not define one's self-efficacy in caring. However, education and training on how to care for terminally ill family members do improve self-efficacy.

Caregiving duration and Self Efficacy. This study shows that self-efficacy and caregiving duration have a *weak positive relationship* ($r=0.301$; $p 0.02$); the longer the caregiving duration, the higher the self-efficacy or confidence. The weak relationship can be due to the small sample size. This study supports a significant relationship between caregiving duration and self-efficacy, and the correlation was significant. According to Havyer et al. (2016), routine training and self-efficacy were associated, and lack of training is associated with low self-efficacy.

Similarly, the study of Hendrix et al. (2016) shows that training improved caregiver self-efficacy for cancer symptom management and in preparation for caregiving. Most of the participants in this study had a care duration of 1 to 3 years (38.3%) and others 6 to 11 months (35%), which means they were already exposed to caring and training. The longer the informal caregiver renders care to an ill family member, the higher their self-confidence in giving care. This can be due to more prolonged exposure and repetitive care skills that they render.

Sex and Self-Efficacy. The study shows that self-efficacy and sex have no relationship (χ^2 19.34; df 26; p 0.82); this means that self-efficacy is not determined by gender, whether the caregiver is male or *female*. No current literature on caregiving self-efficacy supports the relationship between these two variables. However, in another discipline, such as in academe, Yu et al. (2022) show that e-learning self-efficacy generally have no significant gender difference except in a few countries in which female outperformed males. In this study, caregiving self-efficacy does not have a relation to gender; although the majority of the participants were female, being a woman or a man does not determine high or low self-efficacy, and vice versa.

Marital Status and Self-Efficacy. The study shows that self-efficacy and marital status have no relationship (χ^2 31.71; df 26; p 0.20). This means that self-efficacy is not determined by marital status. No current literature on caregiving self-efficacy supports the relationship between these two variables. However, the result of this study is similar to Seyedi-Andi et al. (2019) in studying self-efficacy and the demographic profile of Iranian Medical Science students, in which marital status and self-efficacy were not statistically related. As a result, in this study, being married, single, or divorced does not define one's self-efficacy or confidence in caring for terminally ill family members.

Race and Self-Efficacy. The study shows no *relationship* between self-efficacy and race (χ^2 28.04; df 26; p 0.36). This means that race did not determine self-efficacy in caring between locals and expatriates. The study between self-efficacy and race is minimal, especially regarding care. However, a notable study was done between Black and White Americans in the U.S.A. The study of Assari (2017) about general self-efficacy and mortality in the U.S.A. between black and white shows that black has lower general self-efficacy, and this association was fully explained by their

socioeconomic factors (education and income). According to Assari (2017), socioeconomic status is a significant determinant of a sense of self-efficacy.

Interestingly, for blacks whose lives were under multiple disadvantages and experienced multiple exposures to a wide range of risk factors in resource-scarce environments- high self-efficacy may have harmful effects (Assari, 2017). Assari (2017) also mentioned that the lower self-efficacy may reflect their awareness of blocked opportunities due to structural racism that operates as a systematic barrier for blacks who wish to enjoy a life comparable to whites. Thus, the low general self-efficacy of blacks does not increase their mortality risk; this can be due to race-related attitudes and beliefs, outlooks and experiences, and world views (Assari, 2017), and not just about socioeconomic status. According to Assari (2017), another reason for self-efficacy and race relation can be explained by Social Comparison Theory by Fisher (1954 as cited in Assari, 2017),

“attitude about self is the result of individuals’ comparing themselves with others”.

As discussed, Emiratis have far better social standing. Expatriates might not have the same social opportunities as the Emiratis, but their lives improved compared to their lives back in their country and to some of their friends who are left behind. As Assari (2017) mentioned, socioeconomic status is a significant determinant of sense of self-efficacy. Thus, comparing themselves to the less fortunate gives them a sense of social and economic achievement, which contributes to their self-efficacy or confidence in life. Their experience and worldview contribute to their self-efficacy or confidence and positive outlook. However, despite these explanations, in this study, being Emirati or non-Emirati does not determine high or low self-efficacy, and vice versa; they were not related.

Employment status and Self Efficacy. The study shows that self-efficacy and employment status have no relationship (χ^2 19.54; df 26; p 0.81). This means that whether a person is employed does not define who has better caregiving self-efficacy. No current literature on caregiving self-efficacy supports the relationship between these two variables. However, in another discipline, the study of Wade-Bohleber et al. (2020) about employed adolescents showed otherwise. They studied the association of social and psychological resources of employed and unemployed adolescents, exploring the association of social and family support, self-esteem, and self-efficacy with different dimensions of chronic stress. Their study shows that unemployment status was associated with family support, self-esteem, and self-efficacy. The association between higher self-esteem and efficacy and lower stress levels was more pronounced in employed youth than in unemployed youth across several dimensions of stress. In this study, 58.3% were employed; however, this does not determine self-efficacy, and vice versa; these variables were unrelated.

Relationship between caregiver and care receiver and Self-efficacy. The study shows that self-efficacy and the relationship between caregiver and care receiver were unrelated (χ^2 196.82; df 182 ; p 0.21). This means that regardless of whether it is the father-care receiver, mother-care receiver, sister-care receiver, or brother-care receiver relationship, this does not define how high or low one's self-efficacy is; vice versa, they were unrelated. No current literature on caregiving supports the relationship between these two variables.

Change in employment status and Self-efficacy. In this dimension, change in employment status involves changing jobs, filing a leave of absence and medical leave, increasing work hours, or changing or quitting the job. The study result shows that self-efficacy and changes in employment status have no relationship (χ^2 23.84; df

26; p 0.59). No current literature on caregiving supports the relationship between these two variables. However, in other disciplines, Wade-Bohleber et al. (2020) shows that employed adolescent have higher self-efficacy than unemployed adolescent, and these changes can be closely related to the employment status variable. In this study, 53.3% changed employment status while caring. However, this does not have to do with self-efficacy in caregiving, as they were unrelated.

They were living with the care recipient and self-efficacy. The study shows that self-efficacy and living with the care recipient have no relationship (χ^2 14.24; df 26; p 0.97). This means a carer living with the patient needs higher self-efficacy. This result is similar to the study result of Tan et al. (2021), in which living with a care recipient was negatively associated with Self-Efficacy in responding to disruptive behaviors. However, some literature implies that the more exposed a person is to skill and knowledge, the higher the self-efficacy (Havyer et al., 2016; Hendrix et al., 2016; Tan et al., 2021). Most participants (98.3%) lived with their care recipients. However, this does not increase or decrease self-efficacy, and vice versa; they were unrelated.

With the assistance of private caregivers and self-efficacy. The study shows that self-efficacy and the assistance of private caregivers have no relationship (χ^2 36.07; df 26; p 0.09). Most participants in this study had no assistance (81.7%), and some were with assistance (18.3%) from formal caregivers; however, regardless of whether informal caregivers sought assistance, their caregiving self-efficacy was not affected, and they were not related. Private caregivers are caregivers who underwent formal education in caring, and having such help is a form of respite care or social support. According to Tan et al. (2021), social support was associated with self-efficacy in controlling upsetting thoughts. Thus, with more excellent social support, the caregiver is more likely to be able to find someone to entrust the responsibility of

care when they feel the need for some respite. It is also customary in that each household employs two live-in domestic servants, this helps the woman in managing the house but not the care for sick family member, however, this will help a portion of household burden (Countries and their Culture, n.d.; Commisceo-global, 2020).

Table 8.a

Relationship of Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates and Demographic and Work-related Profile

Variables	Spearman's rho	Strength of Correlation	p-value
Age	-.234	Weak	0.07
Educational Degree	.150	Very weak	0.25
Caregiving Duration	.156	Very weak	0.23

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 8.b

Relationship of Overall Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates and Demographic and Work-related Profile

Variable	Chi-Square	df	p-value
Sex	29.60	25	0.24
Marital Status	25.52	25	0.43
Race	24.46	25	0.49
Employment Status	34.15	25	0.11
Relationship	168.44	175	0.63
Change of Employment	31.34	25	0.18
Living with the care recipient	11.19	25	0.99
With the assistance of private caregivers	19.59	25	0.77

<0.05 level of significance

Table 8a and Table 8b show the relationship between the caregiver burden of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates, and demographic and work-related profiles, discussions, and interpretations are as follows.

Age and Burden. This study shows that caregiver burden and age have a *weak negative relationship* ($r_s -0.234$; $p 0.072$), which means that caregiver burden also declines as age advances. However, this relationship needed to be stronger, and this can be due to the small sample size. This study shows that self-efficacy and age were not significantly correlated. Most of the participants in this study were middle-aged adults (58%); however, whether the caregiver was young or old does not determine the caregiver's burden because they were unrelated. This result is in contrast to Durante et al.'s (2019) study results on caregivers of heart failure, in which they identified that advanced age was one of the identifiers of a higher burden on caregivers. Their study shows that older caregiver was associated with higher time dependence, physical, social, and total burden. Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) study of caregivers of Covid 19 shows a similar result, in which caregivers above 40 had a higher rate of caregiver burden. These results can be due to health problems and co-morbidities that limit the older caregiver's time to socialize or depend on their physical needs.

Educational degree and burden. This study shows that caregiver burden and education have a *fragile positive relationship* ($r_s 0.150$; $p 0.253$); this means that as individual education advances, caregiver burden also increases, but the relationship was not that strong and was not correlated. Contrary to this study results, the study of Unver et al. (2016) on caregivers of the elderly and Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) study of caregivers with heart failure shows that low education had a higher burden. On the other hand, higher education level was identified as one of the predictors of time

dependence burden dimension or restricted caregiver time (Durante et al., 2019). A low level of education has challenges in acquiring information or other support from nurses and other healthcare-related personnel, which causes stress and adds to the burden (Unver et al., 2016). In contrast, highly educated people can be too critical of treatment plans, and this critical attitude could increase the caregiver burden (Durante et al., 2019). However, in this study, all the participants were educated (100%), but regardless of whether or not a degree, the educational degree does not determine caregiver burden, and vice versa; they were unrelated.

Caregiving duration and burden. This study shows that caregiver burden and caregiving duration have a *fragile positive relationship* ($r_s -0.25$; $p 0.05$); this means that the longer the caregiving duration, the higher the caregiver burden. However, there was no significant relationship between the two variables. Most of the caregivers in this study rendered 1-3 years (38.3%); however, regardless of whether the caregiver rendered less or more duration in care, it does not determine the caregiver burden; it does not have a relationship. This is in contrast with Yildiz et al. (2017) and Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) study, in which the longer the duration of caregiving, the more caregiver burden; this can be related to patient care dependency.

Interestingly, the study of Durante et al. (2019) shows that the longer the duration of care, the lower the emotional and social burden. This can be due to a positive relationship between the patient and caregiver, and devoting more time to caregiving can generate appreciation from another family member, reducing the burden (Durante et al., 2019). In this study, regardless of whether the caregiver rendered less or more duration in care, it does not determine the caregiver burden; it does not have a relationship.

Sex and Burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and sex do not have a relationship (χ^2 29.60; df 25; p 0.24). This means that caregiver burden is not determined by gender. In this study, most carers were female (65%), and the rest were male (35%). However, this does not determine the caregiver's burden, or vice versa, as they do not have a relationship. This result is in contrast to other study results, which identified that being female is one of the factors of higher caregiver burden (Durante et al., 2019; Unver et al., 2016; Yildiz et al., 2017; and Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022). The female caregiver had a higher time-dependence burden dimension (Durante et al., 2019). In this study, the majority of the carers were mothers, wives, and sisters; this only shows that females were dominating the proportion of caregivers, and this is associated with a socio-cultural context in which the responsibility of caring lies frequently with homemakers (Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2022; Williams et al., 2017). Because of this responsibility, women are at risk for caregiver burden; however, in this study, gender does not determine caregiver burden, and they were unrelated.

Marital Status and Burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and marital status do not have a relationship (χ^2 25.52; df 25; p 0.43). This means that caregiver burden is not determined by marital status. This study result is in contrast with Yildiz et al. (2017) study, in which married caregivers had a higher caregiver burden than single and having children. Most of our participants were married (55%), and the rest were single (45%); regardless of the marital status, it does not determine caregiver burden, or the other way around, they do not have a relationship.

Race and Burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and race do not have a relationship (χ^2 24.46; df 25; p 0.49). This means that the caregiver burden between Emiratis and expatriates was not determined by race, contrary to the study of Javalkar et al. (2017) and Fenton et al. (2022). Javalkar et al. (2017) studied child-

related predictors and risk factors for caregiver burden among parents of children with chronic conditions in North Carolina, which shows that mothers of white children reported significantly higher burdens than mothers of non-white. On the other hand, the study of Fenton et al. (2022) studied racial and ethnic disparities in cancer caregiving burden and potential socio-cultural mediators. As a result, Black and Hispanic cancer caregivers perform more caregiving and have more financial burden than non-Hispanic white caregivers. Hispanic caregivers reported similar social/emotional and health burdens, while Black caregivers reported lower levels. Hispanic caregivers had less health burden than non-Hispanic White caregivers. Social support and caregiving preparedness partially mediated the Black-White gap for all three types of burdens (Fenton et al.,2022). Even though race and burden were not related, the limitation of this study is identifying the difference of burden between Emirati and Non-Emirati.

Employment status and burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and employment status do not have a relationship (χ^2 34.15; df 25; p 0.11). In this study, most participants were employed (58.3%), and the rest were unemployed (41.7%). Most of them had experienced a change in employment to meet caregiving demands. However, in our study result, being employed or not does not define caregiver burden or the other way around. They were not related.

In contrast to the study result, Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) showed that employed caregivers had more care burden than unemployed caregivers. The family is expected to offer financial aid to sick family members and, at the same time, are required to spend more time on patient care, thus putting a heavier burden on the caregiver. On the other hand, this is refuted by Yildiz et al. (2017); the study showed

that the employed have a lesser caregiver burden than the unemployed; this is because employment can be a way to divert attention from caregiving.

Relationship between caregiver and care receiver and burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and the relationship between caregiver and care receiver do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 = 168.44$; df 175; p 0.63). This means the relationship between the caregiver and care receiver and the caregiver burden does not exist. In this study, the majority of the carers were mothers (23.3%), wives (18.3%), and sisters (18.3%), followed by fathers (16.7%) and lastly, husbands (3.3%). Regardless of the carer and care receiver relationship, it does not determine the caregiver burden because, in this study, the relationship does not exist. This study result is similar to the study of Yldiz et al. (2017), in which they determined that the degree of proximity to the patient does not affect the caregiving burden. In contrast, Unver et al. (2016) show that the caregiver burden of relative and unrelated caregivers was higher. On the other hand, Hooker et al. (2018) study result suggests that patients who feel that they have a good quality relationship with their caregivers have more confidence in engaging in required self-care behaviors, and caregivers who perceive their relationship with their patients as being of good quality are more confident in patient's abilities to engage in self-care, thus lesser burden.

Change in employment status and burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and changes in employment do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 = 31.34$; df 25; p 0.18). This means that the relationship between change in employment and caregiver burden does not exist. In this study, 53.3% changed employment status while caring; however, even with these changes, this does not determine the burden in caregiving, as they were not related. In this dimension, change in employment status involves changing jobs, filing a leave of absence and medical leave, increasing work hours, or

changing or quitting the job. No current literature shows that changing employment status and burden are related. However, Sheikhbardsiri et al. (2022) showed that employed caregivers had more care burden than unemployed because of time and financial needs adjustment, especially if the family member is expected to provide care.

Living with the care recipient and burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and living with the care recipient does not have a relationship (χ^2 11.19; df 25; p 0.99). This means the relationship between the carer living with the patient and the caregiver burden does not exist. Most participants (98.3%) lived with their care recipients. However, this does not increase or decrease the caregiver burden, and vice versa; they were unrelated. No current literature on caregiving supports the relationship between these two variables. Although these two variables are unrelated, Yildiz et al. (2017) study shows that employed caregivers had a lesser burden of care than unemployed caregivers. Since employed spend most of their time away from the patient and focus on jobs rather than patient care, they are less affected by the adverse conditions of caregiving.

With the assistance of private caregivers and burden. The study shows that caregiver burden and the assistance of private caregivers do not have a relationship (χ^2 19.59; df= 25; p=0.77); the relationship does not exist. Although not correlated, having private caregivers is a form of respite care. Respite care is an available service that provides family caregivers some time away from their care responsibilities and a way to sustain their caregiving role (Liao et al., 2022). The study result of Liao et al. shows that having respite care services significantly decreased the caregiver burden of the family caregivers. In this study, 81.7% did not have assistance from private caregivers; this reflects that most of them do not seek respite care. It is customary in

that each Emirati household employs two live-in domestic servants, this helps the woman in managing the house but not the care for sick family member, however, this will help a portion of household burden (Countries and their Culture, n.d.; Commisceo-global, 2020). However, in this study, regardless of whether they have assistance, it does not determine the caregiver burden; the relationship does not exist.

Table 9

Relationship of Overall Self-efficacy and Care Recipient A.D.L. Independence of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates

Variable	Spearman's rho	Strength of Correlation	p-value
Feeding	-.157	Very weak	.232
Bathing	-.388	Weak	.002
Grooming	.003	Very weak	.983
Dressing	-.344	Weak	.007
Bowel	-.252	Weak	.052
Bladder	-.290	Weak	.025
Toilet Use	-.172	Very weak	.190
Transfers	-.163	Very weak	.213
Mobility	-.105	Very weak	.909
Stairs	-.226	Weak	.082

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 9 shows the relationship between the self-efficacy and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretations are as follows.

Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was used to assess the relationship between self-efficacy and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates. There was a statistically significant weak negative relationship between self-efficacy and bathing, $r_s(58) = -.388$, $p = .00$, $N = 60$, self-efficacy and dressing, $r_s(58) = -.344$, $p = .00$, $N = 60$, and self-efficacy and bladder care, $r_s(58) = -.290$, $p = .03$, $N = 60$ at 0.05 significance level.

According to our study results, the more dependent our patients were on task, the higher the caregivers' self-efficacy. Caregiver self-efficacy in informal caregivers was higher when caring for the recipients who were unable to bathe than those who needed help or were independent; higher when caring for recipients who were unable to get dressed than those who needed help or the independent; higher when caring for the recipients who have no control/incontinence of the bladder than those who have partial bladder control or who have complete control.

There is no current literature that supports self-efficacy and patients' dependency. However, some literature implies that the more exposed a person is to skill and knowledge, the higher the self-efficacy. The study of Havyer et al. (2016) supports that lack of training is associated with low self-efficacy. Similarly, the study of Hendrix et al. (2016) shows that training improved caregiver self-efficacy. In this study, the caregivers' self-efficacy level was High, especially in caring for the care recipient; this is most probably because of the comprehensive cancer care program.

Therefore, the more dependent the patient is on A.D.L., the more exposure to A.D.L. needs; the more skill exposure, the higher the self-efficacy.

Table 10

Relationship of Overall Caregiver Burden and Care Recipient A.D.L. Independence of Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in the United Arab Emirates

Activities of Daily Living	Spearman's rho	Strength of Correlation	p-value
Feeding	-.164	Very weak	0.21
Bathing	-.011	Very weak	0.93
Grooming	-.238	Weak	0.07
Dressing	.077	Very weak	0.56
Bowel	.123	Very weak	0.35
Bladder	-.073	Very weak	0.58
Toilet Use	.076	Very weak	0.56
Transfers	-.357**	Weak	0.01
Mobility	-.375**	Weak	0.00
Stairs	-.116	Very weak	0.38

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed)

Table 10 shows the relationship between caregiver burden and care recipient A.D.L. independence of informal caregivers of terminally ill in the United Arab Emirates; discussions and interpretations are as follows.

Spearman rank correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between caregiver burden and care recipient A.D.L. independence in the United Arab Emirates. This study showed a statistically significant *weak negative relationship* between caregiver burden in executing transfers, $r_s(58) = -.357, p=.00, N = 60$, and caregiver burden and assisting for mobility, $r_s(58) = -.375, p=.00, N = 60$ both at .01 significance level.

The study result shows that caregiver burden in informal caregivers was higher when caring for recipients who needed significant help in transfers than those who were unable or needed minor help; higher when caring for recipients who were immobile than those who were wheelchair dependent, or walked with the help of one person, or the independent. According to the study of Unver et al. (2016), a very

dependent older adult incites a higher burden on the caregiver. This is similar to the Javalkar et al. (2017) study result in which mothers of children with physical disabilities had a higher burden than mothers without.

Among the activities that assess care recipient A.D.L.'s independence, transfer, and mobility require lifting, more effort, and more challenging body positions compared to other activities that involve grooming, feeding, bathing, dressing, and toilet use. This is burdensome, especially for caregivers with physical limitations and health issues. Most of the caregivers who participated in this study were middle-aged adults (58%), an age in which health issues usually occur. In contrast to our study result, caregivers of COVID patients in Iran experienced *physical burden* as the lowest domain (Sheikhbardsiri et al., 2020); the difference can be due to the recovery time of COVID vs. other diseases like dialysis. The study by Durante et al. (2019) also stated that better patient physical function was associated with a higher emotional burden. This can be associated with patients when they have better physical health, do not have symptoms, and are less adherent to medical and nursing recommendations even though they have diseases such as heart failure.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study assessed the self-efficacy and burden of caregivers of terminally ill patients in a tertiary hospital in the United Arab Emirates. This study also determined the sociodemographic profile of the caregivers and tested the relationship between self-efficacy and sociodemographic profile, self-efficacy and ADL, caregiver burden and sociodemographic profile, and caregiver burden and ADL.

The study came up with the following results:

Sociodemographic and other work-related variables:

- a. *Sex.* 65% of informal caregivers of terminally ill patients in UAE are females.
- b. *Age.* The majority of the caregivers were Middle-aged adults (58%), followed by young adults (42%)
- c. *Race.* Most participants were non-Emirati (73.3%), followed by Emirati (26.7 %).
- d. *Marital Status.* More than half of the caregivers were married (55%), and the rest were single or widows (45%).
- e. *Relationship.* The relationship of carers to the recipient, most of them were mothers (23.3%), followed by spouses (18.3%) and sisters (18.3%).
- f. *Education.* All the participants could attend school, ranging from High School to a Bachelor's degree. Almost half were Bachelor graduates (48.3%), and the least were High School graduates (23.3%).

- g. *Employment status.* More than half of the caregivers (58.3%) were employed. More than half of them experienced changes in work status (53.3%). Most of them have to file for family/medical leave to attend to the care recipient's needs (38.7%), followed by 25% having to quit their jobs and 12.5% having to change their job.
- h. *Duration of care.* Most participants cared for their recipients for 1-3 years (38.3%), and few reached more than five years (1.7%).
- i. *Living Condition.* Almost all participants lived with their care recipients (98.3%), and few were not living together (1.7%). 80% of the participants care for their care recipients by themselves, without assistance from private nurses at their homes. On the other hand, 18.3% hired private nurses to assist them in caring for their sick family members.

II. Self-efficacy of informal caregivers

The general result of self-efficacy of informal caregivers was *highly confident* in managing caregiving demands (M- 28.08; SD- 1.71). Under self-efficacy, they scored high in two self-efficacy dimensions: *Caring for care recipient* (M- 8.21; SD- 1.04) and *Managing medical information* (M- 8.17; SD- 0.94). They were moderately confident in two other dimensions: *Caring for oneself* (M- 5.79; SD- 2.34) and *Managing difficult interactions and emotions* (M- 5.91; SD- 2.51).

III. Caregiver Burden of informal caregivers

The overall caregiver burden was at a High-Risk level, and among the four burden domains, *Time Dependence or Objective* was the highest form of burden that informal caregivers felt (M-2.84, SD- 1.05). Under the Time dependence domain, they

felt *much burdensome level* in the following subdomain (arranged in high to low order): they have to watch the care receiver constantly (M- 3.17; SD – 0.78); were dependent on them (M- 3.05; SD 0.87); care receiver needs help to perform many tasks (M- 3.00; SD -1.93); and have to help them with many essential functions (M-2.83; SD- 1.17); and at *moderately burdensome level* when they do not have a minute break from caregiving chores (M-2.15; SD 1.16).

The least-scored burden type is *Emotional Burden* (M- 0.11; SD 0.46). Emotional burden refers to any embarrassment or feeling of shame toward the patient. They least feel embarrassed (M-0.30; SD-0.81), ashamed (M-0.12; SD-0.37), angry (M-0.07; SD-0.31), and resent (M-0.03; SD-0.26) to their care receiver nor felt uncomfortable when their friends are visiting (M-0.03; SD-0.26).

IV. The activity of Daily Living Independency of Care Recipients

In this study, care recipients were independent in transferring (M- 2.28) and mobilizing (M- 2.18) and severely dependent in terms of grooming (M- 1.13).

V. Relationship of caregiver self-efficacy and caregiver burden of informal caregivers.

There was a *very weak negative* correlation between caregiver self-efficacy in caregiving and caregiver burden, $r_s(58) = -.12$, $p = .42$, $N = 60$ at $\alpha = .05$. This means that as caregiver self-efficacy increases, the caregiver burden decreases. However, the relationship between the two variables was not statistically significant.

VI. Relationship of self-efficacy and informal caregivers' demographic and work-related profiles:

Among the demographic and other work-related profiles, *Caregiving duration and Self-efficacy* have a significant relationship, and the rest were not significant.

- a. *Age and Self-Efficacy.* This study shows that self-efficacy and age have a *very weak negative relationship* ($r_s -0.127$; $p 0.334$); this means that self-efficacy or confidence also declines as age advances. This study shows that self-efficacy and age were not significantly correlated. This means the caregiver's self-efficacy is not affected or related to age. A young adult can feel self-confident in caring as a middle-aged adult does. Self-efficacy can be gained in any age group.
- b. *Education and Self-Efficacy.* This study shows that self-efficacy and education have a *very weak negative relationship* ($r_s - 0.93$; $p 0.478$); this means that as individual education advances, self-efficacy or confidence also decreases. However, this study shows no significant relationship between education and self-efficacy; the correlation was not significant. This means that educational attainment (e.g., Master's, Bachelor's, etc.) does not define your self-efficacy or confidence in caring for terminally ill family members.
- c. *Caregiving duration and Self Efficacy.* This study shows that self-efficacy and caregiving duration have a *weak positive relationship* ($r_s-0.301$; $p 0.19$); the longer the caregiving duration, the higher the self-efficacy or confidence. The weak relationship can be due to the small sample size. This study supports that there was a significant relationship between caregiving duration and self-efficacy, and the correlation was significant. The longer the informal caregiver

renders care to an ill family member, the higher their self-confidence in giving care.

- d. *Sex and Self-Efficacy.* The study shows that self-efficacy and sex have no relationship (χ^2 19.34; df 26; p 0.82). This means that self-efficacy is not determined by gender, whether the caregiver is male or female.
- e. *Marital Status and Self-Efficacy.* The study shows that self-efficacy and marital status have no relationship (χ^2 31.71; df 26; p 0.20). This means that self-efficacy is not determined by marital status. Being married, single, or divorced does not define one's self-efficacy or confidence in caring for terminally ill family members.
- f. *Race and Self-Efficacy.* The study shows that there was no *relationship* between self-efficacy and race (χ^2 28.04; df 26; p 0.36). This means that race did not determine self-efficacy in caring between locals and expatriates.
- g. *Employment status and Efficacy.* The study shows that self-efficacy and employment status have no relationship (χ^2 19.54; df 26; p 0.81). They do not have a significant relationship; they were not correlated. This means that whether a person is employed or not does not define which has better caregiving self-efficacy.
- h. *Change in employment status and Self-efficacy.* The study result shows that self-efficacy and changes in employment status have no relationship (χ^2 23.84; df 26; p 0.59). This means changes in employment do not have to do with self-efficacy in caregiving.
- i. *Relationship between caregiver and care receiver and self-efficacy.* The study shows that self-efficacy and the relationship between caregiver and care receiver were unrelated (χ^2 196.82; df 182 ; p 0.21). This means that regardless

of whether it is a father-care receiver, mother-care receiver, sister-care receiver, or brother-care receiver relationship, this does not define how high one's self-efficacy is.

- j. *Living with the care recipient and self-efficacy.* The study shows that self-efficacy and living with the care recipient have no relationship (χ^2 14.24; df 26; p 0.97). This means that a carer living with the patient does not mean higher self-efficacy or vice versa.
- k. *With the assistance of private caregivers and self-efficacy.* The study shows that self-efficacy and the assistance of private caregivers have no relationship (χ^2 36.07; df 26; p 0.09). This means that regardless of whether informal caregiver seeks assistance in caring with professional nurses, their caregiving self-efficacy is not affected; they are not related.

VII. Relationship of caregiver burden and Informal caregivers' Demographic and Work-related Profile

The study shows that caregiver burden and sociodemographic and other work-related profiles do not have a relationship; the relationship does not exist.

- a. *Age and Burden.* This study shows that caregiver burden and age have a *weak negative relationship* (r_s -0.234; p 0.072), which means that caregiver burden also declines as age advances. This study also shows that self-efficacy and age were not significantly correlated.
- b. *Educational degree and burden.* This study shows that caregiver burden and education have a *very weak positive relationship* (r_s 0.150; p 0.253); this means that as individual education advances, caregiver burden also increases, but the relationship was not that strong and was not correlated.

- c. *Caregiving duration and burden.* This study shows that caregiver burden and caregiving duration have a very weak positive relationship ($r_s -0.25$; $p 0.05$); this means that the longer the caregiving duration, the higher the caregiver burden. However, there was no significant relationship between the two variables.
- d. *Sex and Burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and sex do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 29.60$; $df 25$; $p 0.24$). This means that the caregiver burden is not determined by gender, whether male or female.
- e. *Marital Status and Burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and marital status do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 25.52$; $df 25$; $p 0.43$). This means that caregiver burden is not determined by marital status. Being married, single, or divorced does not define one's caregiver burden in caring for terminally ill family members.
- f. *Race and Burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and race do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 24.46$; $df 25$; $p 0.49$). This means that the caregiver burden between locals and expatriates is not determined by race.
- g. *Employment status and burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and employment status do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 34.15$; $df 25$; $p 0.11$). This means that whether a person is employed does not define their caregiving burden.
- h. *Relationship between caregiver and care receiver and burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and the relationship between caregiver and care receiver do not have a relationship ($\chi^2 168.44$; $df 175$; $p 0.63$). This means that the relationship between the caregiver burden and *the relationship between the caregiver and care receiver* does not exist.

- i. *Change in employment status and burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and changes in employment do not have a relationship (χ^2 31.34; df 25; p 0.18). This means that the relationship between change in employment and caregiver burden does not exist.
- j. *Living with the care recipient and burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and living with the care recipient does not have a relationship (χ^2 11.19; df 25; p 0.99). This means the relationship between the carer living with the patient and the caregiver burden does not exist.
- k. *With the assistance of private caregivers and burden.* The study shows that caregiver burden and the assistance of private caregivers do not have a relationship (χ^2 19.59; df 25; p 0.77); the relationship does not exist.

VIII. Relationship of self-efficacy and care recipient ADL independence

According to our study results, the more dependent our patients were on task, the more confident or higher self-efficacy for the caregivers.

There was a statistically significant weak negative relationship between self-efficacy and bathing, $r_s(58) = -.388$, $p = .00$, $N = 60$; self-efficacy and dressing, $r_s(58) = -.344$, $p = .00$, $N = 60$; and self-efficacy and bladder care, $r_s(58) = -.290$, $p = .03$, $N = 60$ at .05 significance level. In other words, caregiver self-efficacy in informal caregivers was higher when caring for the recipients who were unable to bathe than those who needed help or were independent; to recipients who were unable to get dressed than those who needed help, or independent; to the recipients who have no control/incontinence of the bladder than those who have partial bladder control, or who have complete control.

IX. Relationship of Caregiver Burden and Care Recipient ADL Independence of Informal Caregivers

Among the activities that assess care recipient ADL independence, transfer, and mobility were activities that require lifting, more effort, and challenging body positions compared to other activities that involve grooming. This study showed a statistically significant *weak negative relationship* between caregiver burden in executing transfers, $r_s(58) = -.357, p=.00, N = 60$, and assisting for mobility, $r_s(58) = -.375, p=.00, N = 60$ both at .01 significance level. The score for caregiver burden in informal caregivers was higher when caring for recipients who needed major help in transfers and were immobile ($Mdn = 2.00$) than for those who were wheelchair dependent or walked with the help of one person or the independent.

CONCLUSION

In this study, more than half of the participants were female. Majority of the caregivers were Middle aged adults (41-65 year; 58%) followed by Young-adults (19-40 years; 28.3%), this result is similar to other study results. Almost 75% of the participants were non-locals. More than half of the participants were married; most caregivers were mothers, wives, and sisters. All the participants could attend school, ranging from High School to a Bachelor's degree. Almost half were Bachelor graduates, and almost a quarter were High School graduates. More than half of the caregivers were employed, and more than half experienced changes in work status. Most of them have to take medical leave to attend to the care recipient's needs, quit jobs, and change their job. Most participants cared for their recipients for 1-3 years. Almost all of the participants live with their care recipients and take care of their care recipients by themselves, without assistance from private nurses.

In this study, overall caregiving self-efficacy and overall caregiver burden had *a negative relationship*. However, it was insignificant, opposite to most of the other study results. However, the result shows that the general level of self-efficacy was *High Self-efficacy* in managing care demands. Among the self-efficacy dimensions, they were *High Self-efficacy in Caring for care Recipients* and least in *Caring for Oneself*. This only shows that they were confident in their care quality. However, since *Caring for Themselves* was the lowest score, caregivers in this study were very confident in caring for their care recipient, most likely due to caregiving support offered by nurses and doctors. This reflects that the adequate support that healthcare professionals provide is most probably the practical demands for caregiving, but not including caregivers' needs for self-care. Another significant result of this study was that caregivers were not confident talking about death and dying; overall, it is the least-scored subdimension.

In the relationship between overall self-efficacy and informal caregivers' demographic and work-related profile, Caregiving duration has a significant relationship with Self-efficacy, and the rest were not significant. It only shows that the longer the informal caregiver cares for an ill family member, the higher their self-confidence in giving care.

On the other hand, their overall caregiver burden level was High Risk for Burn out, meaning they needed help. Time Dependence *or* restriction of one's time was considered the highest form of burden they felt. This study result reflects the lack of time spent on self and others and the dependency of care receivers on family caregivers. The second burden they experienced was Developmental Burden *or* feeling out of sync with their peers *or* missing out on their lives. The least scored burden was Emotional Burden, which refers to embarrassment *or* shame towards the

patient. This shows that even though they do not have much time to themselves and do not have much of life outside, they do not have negative feelings towards their care recipient.

In the relationship between overall caregiver burden and informal caregivers' demographic and other work-related profiles, the study showed that caregiver burden was unrelated to any demographic and work-related variable used in this study; the relationship does not exist.

Another result of this study was the activity of daily living independence of the care receivers. In this study, care recipients were independent in transferring and mobilizing and severely dependent on grooming. In contrast to transfer and mobility activities, grooming involves fine motor skills, which involve using smaller muscles of the hands. Thus, in general, ADL status care recipients were severely dependent on activities involving fine motor activities.

In the relationship between care-recipient ADL dependency and overall Self-efficacy, the score of caregiver's self-efficacy was higher when caring for the recipients who were unable to bathe, dress, and do bladder care. According to our study results, the more dependent our patients were on these tasks, the higher self-efficacy the caregivers felt.

On the other hand, regarding the relationship between care-recipient ADL dependency and overall caregiver burden, there was a negative relationship between overall caregiver burden and executing transfers and overall caregiver burden and assisting with mobility. Although in this study, care recipients were independent in transferring and mobilizing, the Caregiver burden in informal caregivers was higher when caring for recipients who need significant help in transfers and mobility.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are essential to consider based on the study findings:

To Informal Caregivers

The caregiver role predisposes them to lower self-efficacy and to caregiver burden. It is recommended that informal caregivers have open communication and work with the healthcare team for baseline assessment to improve their self-efficacy and to ease the *High caregiver burden level*. Moreover, *Caring for Themselves Self-efficacy* was the least scored dimension and experienced the most burden on *Time Dependence* or restriction of one's personal time dimension. It is recommended to have a balanced lifestyle by finding time for self-care; this can be made possible if one has an open mind in seeking respite care or having a caregiver substitution and reaching out to support groups. The responsibility of caring is not a lone responsibility. Talking about *Death and Dying*, *Self-Efficacy* was the least subdimension; although it is a sensitive matter, one should consider what benefits the care recipient the most.

In terms of ADL, care recipients were severely dependent on activities that involved fine motor activities, and caregivers felt burdensome in caring for those who needed significant help in transfers and mobility; it is recommended for informal caregivers to seek assistance from the rehabilitation team for care techniques, proper body mechanics, and safe use of mechanical devices.

To Nurses

The caregiver *role* predisposes them to lower self-efficacy and to caregiver burden. It is recommended that nurses give special attention to this role and consider

which dimension of self-efficacy and burden is affected in caregiving by initiating baseline assessment. Although the overall Self-efficacy was high, the overall burden was high; nurses should provide continuous support (e.g., Updating care management and techniques, referrals, and consults), continuous assessment, and finding ways to intervene.

Caregivers struggle the most *with Caring for Themselves*; it was the least scored self-efficacy dimension and experienced the most burden on *Time Dependence* or restriction of one's personal time dimension. Nurses should conduct education about health management, time management, and self-care. Referrals to agencies that offer respite care or ways to get respite care are recommended. Social support plays a significant role in respite care, and conducting assessment is imperative. On the other hand, *Talking About Death and Dying* Self-Efficacy was the lowest score among all self-efficacy subdimensions. Nurses should initiate the conversation, listen attentively, and empathetically encourage the carers to talk about death and dying to have a more beneficial care plan for the care receiver and carer.

Moreover, among the work-related profiles, *Self-efficacy* and *Caregiving Duration* were related, and most caregivers comprised *females*, especially mothers, spouses, and sisters. Nurses should give special attention to informal caregivers who render care for a period of time and those who are female to provide the support they need.

Regarding ADL, care recipients were severely dependent on activities involving fine motor activities, and caregivers felt more self-efficacy when their care receivers were more dependent. However, caregivers feel burdensome when caring for patients needing significant transfers and mobility help. It is recommended that nurses assess

patients with ADL and initiate rehab consultation for proper techniques and device use in executing transfer and mobility.

To Care Recipients

Care recipients were severely dependent on activities that involve fine motor activities; it is recommended to consult rehabilitation to undergo exercises and use devices to improve independence to lessen the caregiver burden.

To Administration

Caregiver's self-efficacy in caring is high, specifically in managing the medical needs of care recipients; it is recommended to keep them updated and be on top of the game with caring techniques by organizing educational and training group sessions, creating websites, and producing booklet.

Caregivers' self-efficacy in caring for themselves was poor, and at a *high-risk* level of caregiver burden, specifically with time dependence burden, it is recommended to administration form agencies for respite care or recommend other forms of respite care. For example, it is introducing them to affordable private nursing to substitute for a day or more or train other family members to take over the role. Having breaks from caregiving will allow caregivers to have time for self-care. Education emphasizing self-care is essential to prevent caregivers from being the next patient after their care recipient. Creating help resources and agencies that tackle topics more than technical caring techniques, like emotional and psychological issues, they may encounter as caregivers and how to care for themselves while caring for others, especially most of the caregivers working in secular jobs.

Administrative initiatives for healthcare providers to expand their healthcare assessment, not just to primary patients, but also to informal caregivers attending to the sick. Formulated plans and form training sessions to make these initiatives part of health assessment. Empower social workers and healthcare providers to be part of care planning, especially talking about death and dying. Form training sessions for nurses on handling or discussing death and dying since nurses are in the first line of caring. Empower rehabilitation as part of the care team to improve patients' ADL independence and prevent physical injury to caregivers by introducing proper body mechanics and using innovations if indicated, especially since most caregivers are female.

To Nursing Research

It is recommended to further examine the self-efficacy and burden by conducting a wider research scale and in longer duration in different intervals to assess change. Moreover, caregivers were Highly Confident in managing care demands; this result indirectly describes the performance of informal caregivers in the quality of care they provide for their care recipient. It is recommended to include quality-of-care or patients' perception of their level of care in future research. Since the culture in UAE is so diverse, it is interesting to assess self-efficacy in caring and caregiver burden by categorizing the culture by continent (e.g., Arab-Asian, Non-Arab Asian, African, etc.).

References

- Abaquin, C and Kuan, L., (2002). *Oncology Nursing*. The Philippines. University of the Philippines Open University.
- Al-Rawashdeh, S., Lennie, T. & Chung, M. (2016). Psychometrics of the Zarit Burden Interview in Caregiver of Patients with Heart Failure. *J Cardiovasc Nursing*. Vol31-Issue 6-p E21-E28. DOI: 10.1097/JCN.0000000000000348
- Anonuevo, C., Abaquin, C, Balabagno, A. et al. (2005). *Theoretical Foundation of Nursing*. The Philippines. University of the Philippines Open University.
- Araki, M. (2019). *Quality of Life of Family Caregiver of Patients with Cancer*. Department of Cancer Science and Research. Vol 6 (4):061. Retrieved from https://jacobsublishers.com/uploads/article_pdf/7/scientific_7_1546_17032020025758.pdf
- Assari, S., (2017). *General Self-efficacy and Mortality in the USA; Racial Difference*. *J Racial Ethn Health Disparities*, 4 (4): 746–757. Doi: 10.1007/s40615-016-0278-0
- Attun, B., Hafiz, S. Malik, A., Shamoan, Z. (2023). Cultural Competence in the Care of Muslim Patients and their Families. National Library of Medicine. Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK499933/>
- Bandura, A. (1994). Self-efficacy. In V. S. Ramachandran (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of human behavior* (Vol. 4, pp. 71–81). New York: Academic Press. (Reprinted in H. Friedman [Ed.], *Encyclopedia of mental health*. San Diego: Academic Press, 1998)
Retrieved from: <https://www.uky.edu/~eushe2/Bandura/Bandura1994EHB.pdf>
- Bandura, A. (1982). Self-efficacy Mechanism in Human Agency. *American Psychological Association*. Vol 37, No. 2, 122-147. Retrieved from <https://www.uky.edu/~eushe2/Bandura/Bandura1982AP.pdf>
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Self-efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioral Change*. *Psychological Review*. Vol. 84, No. 2, 191-215. Retrieved from <https://www.uky.edu/~eushe2/Bandura/Bandura1977PR.pdf>
- Burns, N. et al. (2013). *Understanding Nursing Research: Building an Evidence-based Practice*. Singapore. Elsevier Pte Ltd.
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2018). *Caregiving for Family and Friends- A- A Public Health Issue*. National Association of Chronic Disease Directors. Retrieved from: <https://www.cdc.gov/aging/caregiving/caregiver-brief.html>
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2019). Alzheimer’s Disease and Healthy Aging: Caregivers. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/aging/caregiving/index.htm>

- Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2019). Chronic Diseases. National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/chronicdisease/about/index.htm>
- Cherry, K. & Susman, D. (2022). Erickson's Stages of Development: A Closer Look at the Eight Psychosocial Stages. Verywellmind. Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com/erik-eriksons-stages-of-psychosocial-development-2795740>
- Chinh-Hsuan, W., Jamie, H., Victoria, C., & Xi, L. (2018). Exploring the Relationship Among International Students' English Self-efficacy, Using English to Learn Self-efficacy and Academic Self-efficacy. *Journal of International Students*. Vol 8, Iss 1, p. 223-250. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.1134299
- Cianfrocca, C., Caponnetto, V., Donati, D., Lancia, L., Tartaglini, D., and Di Stasio, E. (2018). A multidisciplinary education course affects the burden, health literacy, and needs of family caregivers. *Applied Nursing Research*, 44, 100-106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apn.2018.10.004>
- Countries and their Cultures, n.d. United Arab Emirates. Retrieved from <https://www.everyculture.com/To-Z/United-Arab-Emirates.html#ixzz88j9Ug15j>
- Commisceo Global (2022). UAE- language, culture, etiquette, and business practices. Retrieved from: <https://www.commisceo-global.com/resources/country-guides/uae-guide>
- Deyhoul, N., Rohani, C., Vasli, P. et al. (2020). The effect of family-centered empowerment program on the family caregiver burden and the activities of daily living of Iranian patients with stroke: a randomized controlled trial study. *Aging Clinical and Experimental Research*. 32 (7): 1343–1352. DOI:10.1007/s40520-019-01321-4
- Dubai Online (2021). UAE Population and Demographics. Retrieved from <https://www.dubai-online.com/essential/uae-population-and-demographics/>
- Duffy, L., Gajree, S., Langhorne, P. et al. (2013). Reliability (Inter-rater Agreement) of the Barthel Index for Assessment of Stroke Survivor. *AHA Journal*. Retrieved from <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/strokeaha.112.678615>
- Durante, A., Greco, A. et al. (2019). Determinants of Caregiver burden in Heart Failure: Does caregiver contribute to heart failure patient self-efficacy increase caregiver burden?. *The European Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing*. Vol. 18 (8) 691-699. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474515119863173>
- Elbazari, I., Devlin, N., Katsaiti, M. et al (2017). The Effects of Religion on the perception of health states among adults in the United Arab Emirates: a qualitative study. *National Library of Medicine*. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-016969

- Ellis K., Janevic, M., Kershaw T., et al. (2017). The Influence of dyadic symptom distress on threat appraisals and self-efficacy in advanced cancer and caregiving. *Supportive Care Cancer*. Vol 25 (1). DOI:10.1007/s00520-016-3385-x
- Fenton et al., (2022). Racial and ethnic disparities in cancer caregiver burden and potential sociocultural mediators. National Library of Medicine. 30(11): 9625-9633. DOI: 10.1007/s00520-022-07367-x
- Gonzalo A. (2019). Dorothea Orem: Self-Care Deficit Theory. *Nurseslabs*. Retrieved from <https://nurseslabs.com/dorothea-orems-self-care>
- Grano, C., Lucidi, F., Violani, C. (2017). The relationship between caregiving self-efficacy and depressive symptoms in family caregivers of patients with Alzheimer disease: a longitudinal study. *International Psychogeriatrics Association*. 29:7, 1095-1103. doi:10.1017/S1041610217000059
- Hampton, M. & Newcomb, P. (2018). Self-efficacy and Stress Among Informal Caregivers of Individuals at the End of Life. *Journal of Hospice & Palliative Nursing*. DOI:10.1097/NJH.0000000000000464
- Harrison, C. (2019). Enhancing self-efficacy for caregivers of family members with spinal cord injury. *ClinicalTrials.gov*. Retrieved from <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT02392052>
- Havyer, R., Ryn, M., Wilson, P. & Griffin, J. (2016). The effect of routine training on the self-efficacy of informal caregivers of colorectal cancer patients. *Support Care Cancer*, Vol 25,1071-1077. Doi.org/10.1007/s00520-016-3494-6
- Hendrix, C., Bailey, D., Steinhauser, K., Olsen, M. et al. (2016). Effects of Enhanced Caregiver Training Program on Cancer Caregiver's Self-Efficacy, Preparedness, and Psychological Well-being. *Support Care Cancer*, 24:327-336. Doi.org/10.1007/s00520-015-2797-3
- Hiseman, P. and Fackrell, R. (2017). Caregiver Burden and Nonmotor Symptoms of Parkinson's Disease. *International Review of Neurobiology*. Doi.org/10.1016/bs.irn.2017.05.035
- Hooker, S., Schmiege, S., Trivedi, R., et al (2018). Mutuality and heart failure self-care in patients and their informal caregivers. *Eur J Cardiovascular Nurs* 2018; 17 (2): 102-113. doi: 10.1177/1474515117730184.
- Khanshan S. & Yousefi M. (2020). The relationship between self-efficacy and instructional practice of in-service soft disciplines, complex disciplines, and EFL teachers. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*. Vol 5, Iss 1. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40862-020-0080-8>.
- Kuzma, J. and Bohnenblust, S., (2005). *Basic Statistics for the Health Sciences* (5th ed.) McGraw-Hill.

- Leung, D., Chan, H., Chan, C., et al. (2017). Psychometric Properties of the Caregiver Inventory for Measuring Caregiving Self-efficacy of Caregivers of Patients with Palliative Care Needs. *Neuropsychiatry*. Vol 7 (6), p 872-879. Retrieved from <https://www.jneuropsychiatry.org/peer-review/psychometric-properties-of-the-caregiver-inventory-for-measuring-caregiving-selfefficacy-of-caregivers-of-patients-with-.pdf>
- Litzelman K., Kent E., Mollica M. & Rowland J. (2016). How does caregiver well-being relate to the perceived quality of care in patients with cancer? Exploring Associations and Pathways. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, Vol 34, p 29. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2016.67.3434>
- Liao, Y., Ku, L., Liu, L. (2022). The Effect of In-home Respite Care on the Burden of Caregiver in Taiwan. *Journal of Applied Gerontology*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/073346482111073876>
- Lopez-Garrido, G. (2020). Self-Efficacy Theory. SimplyPsychology. Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org/self-efficacy.html>
- Mastrangelo, K. (2016). ADL Coding: Where Does the Confusion Begin? Harmony Healthcare International (HHI) Blog. Retrieved from <https://www.harmony-healthcare.com/blog/adl-coding-where-does-the-confusion-begin>
- Mariecurie Organization: Care and support through terminal illness. 2018. *What are palliative care and end-of-life care?* Retrieved from <https://www.mariecurie.org.uk/help/support/diagnosed/recent-diagnosis/palliative-care-end-of-life-care>
- Marie Curie Organization: Care and support through Terminal Illness 2019. *What Does Terminal Illness Mean?* Retrieved at <https://www.mariecurie.org.uk/who/terminal-illness-definition>
- Marvardi, M., Mattioli, P. & Spazzafumo, L. (2005). The Caregiver Burden Inventory in Evaluating the Burden of Caregivers of Elderly Demented Patients: Results from a Multicenter Study. *Aging Clinical and Experimental Research*. Vol 17(1): p 46-53. DOI: 10.1007/BF03337720
- Merluzzi, T., Philip, E., Vanchon, O. & Heitzmann, C. (2011). Assessment of Self-Efficacy for Caregiving: The Critical Role of Self-Care in Caregiver Stress and Burden. *Palliative and Supportive Care*. Vol 9, Issue 1, pp. 15-24. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S1478951510000507>
- Minnesota Department of Health. RUG-IV: What is an ADL Score (2021)? Retrieved from <https://www.health.state.mn.us/facilities/regulation/casemix/rugiv/docs/rugivfs14.pdf>
- Morris, J., Gilden, R. Fries, B. et al (2018). Physical Functioning: Activities of Daily Living Self performance. User Guide for the interRAI HC Assessment Form. Retrieved from

https://www.ciminc.com/help/COMPASS/iHC_Assessment_Manual/iHC_Assessment_Manual.htm#Assessment_Manual.htm

Morrow, A. (2021). Talking about Death with a Dying Person. Very well health. Retrieved from <https://www.verywellhealth.com/interaction-with-a-dying-person-1132502>

National Alliance for Caregiving (2020) *Caregiving in the U.S. 2020*. Retrieved from <https://www.caregiving.org/research/caregivingusa/>

Nursing Theorist (2012). Dorothea Orem's Self-Care Theory. Retrieved from http://currentnursing.com/nursing_theory/self_care_deficit_theory.html

Palacio, C., Krikorian, A. & Limonero, J. (2018). The Influence of Psychological factors on the burden of caregivers of patients with advanced cancer: *Resiliency and Caregiver Burden. Palliative and Supportive Care, Vol 16, p 268-277*. DOI:10.1017/S1478951517000268

Plitchta, S. & Kelvin E. (2013). *Munro's Statistical Methods for Health Care Research 6th edition*. Wolters Kluwer Health/ Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/docview/1844550936/61D85E8B16B94549PQ/1?accountid=207160>

Polit, D. and Hungler, B., (1999). *Nursing Research Principles and Methods (6th ed.)*. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.

Roth, D., Fredman, L., Haley, E. (2015). Informal Caregiving and Its Impact on Health: A Reappraisal from Population-Based Studies. *The Gerontologist*. Doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnu177

Sahai, S., Sahai, R., Beniwal, R. et al (2018). Assessment of functionality in persons with schizophrenia and its impact on burden and self-efficacy of caregivers. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology, Vol 9 p465-469*. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2194001935/fulltextPDF/1C43E61DD3A0446APQ/1?accountid=207160>

Scicolone, M. (2018). Examining pathways of the caregiver burden – health relationship in family caregivers of elderly veterans: the importance of caregiver self-efficacy and social support. The University of Alabama, ProQuest Dissertation Publishing. Retrieved at <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2189079504/2CDDFFAD82B77400CPQ/2?accountid=207160>

Seyedi-Andi, S., Bakouei, F., Rad, H., Khafri, S., & Salavati, A. (2019). The relationship between self-efficacy and some demographic and socioeconomic variables among Iranian Medical Science students. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice* 10 645-651. Doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.SI85780

Sebugwaano, I., (2023). UAE: Skilled Emiratis in the private Sector get equal pay to expats in the same jobs, according to a study. Khaleej Times. Retrieved from:

<https://www.khaleejtimes.com/uae/uae-skilled-emiratis-in-private-sector-get-equal-pay-to-expats-in-same-job-shows-study>

- Sharma, N., Chakrabarti, S., Grover, S. (2016). Gender Differences in Caregiving among family- caregivers of people with mental illness. *World Journal of Psychiatry*. DOI:10.5498/wjp.v6.i1.7.
- Sheikhbardsiri, H., Tavan, A., Afshar, P., Salahi, S., Heidari-Jamebozorgi, M., (2022). Investigating the burden of disease dimensions (Time-dependent, Developmental, Physical, Social, and Emotional) among Family caregivers with COVID-19 patients in Iran. *BMC Primary Care*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-022-01772-1>
- Steffen, A., Gallagher-Thompson, D., Arenella, K. et al. (2019). Validating the Revised Scale for Caregiving Self-Efficacy: A Cross-National Review. *The Gerontological Society of America*. Vol 59 (4), e325-e342. Doi:10.1093/geront/gny004
- Sultan, S., Kanwal, F., Kanwal, S. (2020). Caregiving End of Life Experiences and Well-being of Caregivers of Cardiac Patients: Mediating Role of Caregiving Self-efficacy. *Pakistani Heart Journal*. Vol 53 Issue 1, p2-15. Retrieved from <http://pkheartjournal.com/index.php/pkheart/article/view/1648>
- TGM Research. (2022). United Arab Emirates Demography and Statistics Through a Magnifying Glass. Retrieved at www.tgmresearch.com.
- Queensland Health (n.d.). Islamic beliefs affecting healthcare. Healthcare providers' handbook on Muslim patients. Retrieved from: https://www.health.qld.gov.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0024/157605/islamgde2e-d-s2.pdf
- UAE Government Portal. (2023). Health Insurance. Retrieved from <https://u.ae/en/information-and-services/health-and-fitness/health-insurance>
- UAE Government Portal, (n.d) Emiratis' Employment in the Private Sector. Retrieved from: <https://u.ae/en/information-and-services/jobs/emiratis-employment-in-private-sector>
- United States Census Bureau (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/fact/table/US/RHI125221>
- University of Minnesota (n.d.). *Type of statistics*. Retrieved from <https://cyfar.org/types-statistical-tests>
- Upadhyay, G. (2021). Barthel Index. Physiopedia. Retrieved from https://www.physio-pedia.com/Barthel_Index#Objective
- Uvver, V., Basak, T., Tosun, N., Aslan, O. and Akbayrak, N. (2016). Caregiver burden and self-efficacy levels of family caregivers of older adults in Turkey. *Holist*

NursPract 30(3):166-173.Retrieved from
<https://doi.org/10.1097/HNP.000000000000148>

Way, J., Peterson, M., Dial, K., and Magellan, R. (2023). Role of Physical Therapy on Caregiver Burden: A Mixed Methods Design. American Physical Therapy Association. Retrieved from
<https://apta.confex.com/apta/csm2023/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/38108>

Wikipedia (2023). Religion in the United Arab Emirates. Retrieved from:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Religion_in_the_United_Arab_Emirates

Wikipedia (2023) Emiratis. Retrieved from
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emiratis>

Williams, L.A., et al., (2017). 'Because it is the wife who has to look after the man': A descriptive qualitative study of older women and the intersection of gender and the provision of family caregiving at the end of life. *Palliative Medicine*, 31(3), 223–230.

Williams, M., (2020). Exploration of self-regulation and self-efficacy for academic and career motivation of military student veterans. Wingate University, ProQuest Dissertations Publishing. Retrieved from
<https://www.proquest.com/docview/2476124078/ABC9F07013724772PQ/7?aaccountid=207160>

World Health Organization (n.d).*Life Expectancy: Global Health Observatory Data*. Retrieved from:
https://www.who.int/gho/mortality_burden_disease/life_tables/situation_trends/en/

Yildiz, E., Karakas, S., Güngörmüs, Z. and Cengiz, M. (2017). Levels of care burden and self-efficacy for the informal caregiver of patients with cancer. *Holist Nurs Pract*,31(1):7-15.<https://doi.org/10.1097/HNP.000000000000185>

Yu, Z. & Deng, X., (2022). A Meta-Analysis of Gender Differences in e-Learners' Self-Efficacy, Satisfaction, Motivation, Attitude, and Performance Across the World. Systematic Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*. Retrieve from
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.897327>

Zoladl, M., Afroughi, S., Nooryan, K., et al. (2019). Applying Collaborative Care Model on Intensive Caregiver Burden and Resilient Family Caregivers of Patients with Mental Disorders: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry*. 15 (1). DOI:10.18502/ijps.v15i1.2

APPENDICES

Appendix A

Consent in English and Arabic

Introduction:

My name is Shane Duran, a registered nurse studying the Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden of family members who care for a terminally ill family member. Although the study will not benefit you directly, it will provide information that might enable nurses to identify and assist family members with their needs.

You are being asked to participate in this research study because you provide "free care" for a person with chronic disease. Your participation in this study is voluntary. Refusal to participate or discontinuing your participation at any time will involve no penalty or loss of benefit to which you are otherwise entitled.

Consent Form

Research title: Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden among Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in a Tertiary Hospital in United Arab Emirates

Principle investigator name: Ms. Angelie Rose Betonio
Co-Investigator: Ms. Shane Duran

PI Contact and institution:

For any question/queries, please contact Office of Research Governance at clinicalresearch@seha.ae, contact # 03/7072240, Box 15258 Academic Affairs, Tawam Hospital, Al Ain, UAE.

Consent Statement

The study was explained to me by the investigator in the language that I speak, I was given the time to ask any question regarding the study and all my queries was answered by the investigator. I was informed that my participation in this study is voluntary and I can withdraw my consent at any time without any penalty or any other consequences. The investigator explained to me the importance of participation in this study and my information confidentiality will be protected.

Consent Form

Participant Name: _____

Institution Name: _____

Institution Location: _____

Date: _____

I will fully agree to participate in the above mentioned study, I understand that there are no compensations that I will receive to participate.

Agree to participate, Consented:

 Yes No

This part to be completed by the investigator

I am _____ I have explained the study objectives the rights of the participants and the protection of confidentiality to the participants and he/she was given the chance to ask questions all his/her queries were answered.

Principle / Co-Investigator signature: _____ Date: _____

استمارة موافقة

عنوان الدراسة:

Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden among Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in a Tertiary Hospital in United Arab Emirates

وقدمت الدراسة للموافقة المحققين الرئيسيين: Ms. Angelie Rose Betonio

محقق مشارك: Ms. Shane Duran

رقم التليفون الايميل

اسم المؤسسة: مستشفى توأم، 15258، العين، الإمارات العربية المتحدة.

لاي، استفسار يرجى الاتصال على مركز ادارة الابحاث في مستشفى توام. الشؤون الاكاديميه

اتصال 7072240/03، صندوق بريد 1525، العين، الإمارات العربية المتحدة، Clinicalresaerch@seha.ae

لقد تم شرح شروط المشاركة في هذه الدراسة لي باللغة التي أتحدثها، وتم منحي الفرصة لطرح أي تساؤل بهذا الخصوص، وتم إيضاح جميع الشكوك المتعلقة لدي بمشاركتي في هذه الدراسة من قبل الباحث، كما تم إعلامي بأن المشاركة في هذه الدراسة أمر تطوعي على نحو كامل وأنه بإمكانني الانسحاب من هذا المشروع في أي وقت كان، وتم إعلامي بأهمية البحوث المقترحة، وبأن خصوصية المشاركين في هذه الدراسة محمية بالنظر إلى نتائج البحوث، وبأن عدم المشاركة في هذه الدراسة أو الانسحاب منها في أي وقت كان لا تترتب عليه أي عقوبة أو نتائج من أي نوع كان. أنا _____ الموقع أدناه أوافق على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة بحسب الشروط المشروحة لي.

التوقيع: _____

التاريخ: _____

موافق

نعم

لا

يتم إكمال هذا الجزء من قبل الباحث

أنا _____ قمت بشرح أهداف هذه الدراسة وحقوق المشاركين بها والمحافظة على الخصوصية محقق مشارك / للمشارك وأعطيته/ها الفرصة لطرح الأسئلة.

توقيع الباحث: _____

التاريخ: _____

Appendix B

Ethics Approval

Tawam Human Research Ethics Committee (T-HREC)

Date: 13th December 2021 **Ref. No.:** AA/AJ/815
To:
Principal Investigator: Ms. Angelie Rose Betonio
Department: Nursing
Institute: Tawam Hospital

Subject:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Research Study <input type="checkbox"/> Amendment <input type="checkbox"/> Extension <input type="checkbox"/> Revision		
Research Title:	Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden among Informal Caregivers of Terminally Ill Patients in a Tertiary Hospital in United Arab Emirates		
Study Type:	Questionnaires/Survey		
Ethics Committee Approval #:	MF2058-2021-815		
Decision:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Favorable <input type="checkbox"/> Unfavorable	<input type="checkbox"/> Favorable with Conditions	
Progress Report Submission Requirement:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Annual	<input type="checkbox"/> 6 Months	
Study Expiry Date:	31 st December, 2022		

Dear Ms. Betonio,

The Research Proposal was reviewed by the Ethics Committee members and voted towards the ethics approval.

Any ethical concern arising from the study in due course, should be informed. Annual report plus a terminal report are necessary and the Committee would appreciate receiving copies of abstracts and publications.

Studies approved can't be continued beyond the expiry date mentioned above. In case continuation of study is anticipated, extension request in the prescribed form should be submitted to the committee prior to 60 days of expiry date.

The Research Committee has been organized and operates according to the Good Clinical Practice (GCP) guidelines and the Department of Health, Abu Dhabi (DoH).

It's mandatory to be compliant with the regulatory requirements of the Office of Research Governance ORG, Tawam, whenever required.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Khaled Mohammed Asad Al Dahmani
Chair, Tawam Human Research Ethics Committee (T-HREC)

P.S. Primary investigator using data collectors from outside the hospital are required to obtain HR department approval as visitors through the Office of Research Governance.

Email: TawamHREC@seha.ae | Tel: +971 3 7072240 | PO Box: 15258

00971 3 7677634 : فاكس : 00971 3 7677444 : هاتف : الإمارات العربية المتحدة - 15258 - العين أبوظبي ص.ب - مستشفى نوام - SEHA A SEHA Healthcare Facility
Tawam Hospital - Al Ain - Abu Dhabi. P.O. Box 15258 - United Arab Emirates - Tel : 00971 3 7677444 - Fax: 00971 3 7677634

Assistant researcher becomes the principal investigator for formality, due to principal investigator 's transfer of employment to USA in the middle of the study.

Appendix C

Demographic And Other Work Related Questionnaire In English and Arabic

Instructions: Please check the appropriate spaces or write the answers in the blanks. These questions will let the researcher know more about you.

Title: "Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregiver of Terminally ill patients in Tertiary Hospital in United Arab Emirates".

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

Instructions: Please check the appropriate spaces or write the answers in the blanks. These questions will let the researcher know more about you.

I. General Demographics
Gender: <input type="checkbox"/> Male. <input type="checkbox"/> Female
Marital Status: <input type="checkbox"/> Single (divorced & widow) <input type="checkbox"/> Married
Age Group: <input type="checkbox"/> below 20 <input type="checkbox"/> 21-30 <input type="checkbox"/> 31-40 <input type="checkbox"/> 41-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 51-60 <input type="checkbox"/> above 60
Education: <input type="checkbox"/> Highschool <input type="checkbox"/> Diploma <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor Degree <input type="checkbox"/> Master Degree <input type="checkbox"/> PHD Degree
Race: <input type="checkbox"/> Emirati <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Emirati(Please Specify: _____)
Employment Status
<input type="checkbox"/> Employed <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed / Retired
Has your employment status changed as a result of caregiving duties?
<input type="checkbox"/> No changes
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (If yes, choose what are the changes below)
<input type="checkbox"/> Changed job <input type="checkbox"/> Family/Medical leave <input type="checkbox"/> Leave of Absence
<input type="checkbox"/> Increased work hours <input type="checkbox"/> Decreased work hours <input type="checkbox"/> Early retirement
<input type="checkbox"/> Began working <input type="checkbox"/> Quit job <input type="checkbox"/> others _____
II. Caregiver Relationship to Care Recipient
What is your relationship to the person you care for?
<input type="checkbox"/> Husband <input type="checkbox"/> Wife <input type="checkbox"/> Son in law. <input type="checkbox"/> Daughter in law <input type="checkbox"/> Sister <input type="checkbox"/> Brother <input type="checkbox"/> Mother
<input type="checkbox"/> Father <input type="checkbox"/> Other Relatives: _____
III. Duration of Caregiving
How long have you been providing care for this individual?
<input type="checkbox"/> less than 6 months <input type="checkbox"/> 6 to 11 months. <input type="checkbox"/> 1 to 3 years. <input type="checkbox"/> 3 to 5 years
<input type="checkbox"/> more than 5 years
The following questions are about the person you are providing care :
Does the individual you are caring for live with you? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes. <input type="checkbox"/> No
Do you receive assistance from private nurses or caregivers <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

أ- استبيان اجتماعي ديموغرافي

تعليمات: يرجى اختيار الاجابة الصحيحة او كتابة الاجابة المناسبة في الفراغ .

1. الخصائص الديموغرافية العامة	
الجنس: ذكر. <input type="checkbox"/> انثى <input type="checkbox"/>	
الحالة الاجتماعية: - أعزب (مطلقة وأرملة) - متزوج <input type="checkbox"/>	
الفئة العمرية: أقل من 20 <input type="checkbox"/> 20-30 <input type="checkbox"/> 30-40 <input type="checkbox"/> 40-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 50-60 <input type="checkbox"/> أكثر من 60 <input type="checkbox"/>	
التعليم: ثانوية <input type="checkbox"/> دبلوم <input type="checkbox"/> بكالوريوس <input type="checkbox"/> ماجستير <input type="checkbox"/> دكتوراه <input type="checkbox"/>	
العرق: "إماراتي" غير إماراتي (يرجى التحديد: _____)	
الحالة الوظيفية	
<input type="checkbox"/> عامل <input type="checkbox"/> عاطل عن العمل / متقاعد	
هل تغيرت حالتك الوظيفية نتيجة لمهام تقديم الرعاية؟ <input type="checkbox"/> لا توجد تغييرات <input type="checkbox"/>	
<input type="checkbox"/> نعم (إذا كانت الإجابة بنعم ، حدد أي من التغييرات أدناه)	
<input type="checkbox"/> غيرت عملي <input type="checkbox"/> إجازة عائلية / طبية <input type="checkbox"/> إجازة غياب	
<input type="checkbox"/> زيادة ساعات العمل <input type="checkbox"/> تقليل ساعات العمل <input type="checkbox"/> التقاعد المبكر	
<input type="checkbox"/> بدأ العمل <input type="checkbox"/> ترك الوظيفة <input type="checkbox"/> أخرى _____	
2. علاقة مقدم الرعاية بمتلقي الرعاية	
ما هي علاقتك بمتلقي الرعاية؟ <input type="checkbox"/> الزوج <input type="checkbox"/> الزوجة <input type="checkbox"/> زوج الابنة <input type="checkbox"/> زوجة الابن <input type="checkbox"/> الأخت <input type="checkbox"/> الأخ <input type="checkbox"/> الأم <input type="checkbox"/> الأب <input type="checkbox"/> أقارب آخرون: _____	
3. مدة تقديم الرعاية	
منذ متى وأنت تقدم الرعاية لهذا الفرد؟ <input type="checkbox"/> أقل من 6 أشهر <input type="checkbox"/> من 6 إلى 11 شهراً <input type="checkbox"/> من 1 إلى 3 سنوات <input type="checkbox"/> من 3 إلى 5 سنوات <input type="checkbox"/> أكثر من 5 سنوات <input type="checkbox"/>	
الأسئلة التالية تتعلق بمتلقي الرعاية:	
هل يعيش متلقي الرعاية معك؟ <input type="checkbox"/> نعم <input type="checkbox"/> لا <input type="checkbox"/>	
هل تتلقى مساعدة من طاقم تـمريض خاص أو مقدم رعاية خاص <input type="checkbox"/> نعم <input type="checkbox"/> لا <input type="checkbox"/>	

Appendix D

Caregiver Inventory (CGI) Questionnaire in English and Arabic

This questionnaire contains things that a person might be performing when caring for someone with a terminal condition. We are interested in your confidence that you can do those things. Ensure your ratings reflect your confidence whether or not you have done in the past.

Title: “Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregiver of Terminally ill patients in Tertiary Hospital in United Arab Emirates”.

A. CAREGIVER INVENTORY(CGI)

Instructions: Encircle the number on how confident you are in accomplish a task:
SCALE: One (1) means that you are *Not-at-all Confident* ; Nine (9) means that you are *Totally Confident*. Numbers in the middle of the scale indicate that you are *Moderately Confident*. If you are not sure about an item, please rate it as best you can.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Coping with information overload	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Listening and learning from the person as to how to care better for him/her	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Letting go of things I cannot control	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Expressing negative feelings about the illness	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Maintaining hope	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Being able to notice the “good moments” in caregiving when they occur	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Allowing the person to have and express his/her own Feelings	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Assisting the person with Activities, such as feeding, washing, dressing, or toileting	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Continuing to take care of yourself (for example: exercise, diet, sleep)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Talking openly and honestly with the person	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Continuing to engage in personal activities that you like to do	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Talking about death and dying	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Providing emotional support to the person I am caring for	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Understanding medical information from doctors, nurses or other sources	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Seeking support for yourself	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Dealing with feelings of helplessness	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Dealing with the person expressing negative feelings toward you when they occur	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Assisting and encouraging the person in following through with all treatments and taking all prescribed medications	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Asking physicians and nurses questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Dealing with criticism from others	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Maintaining as close relationship with the person I am caring for	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

أ. استبيان مقدمي الرعاية (CGI)

التعليمات: ضع دائرة حول الرقم الذي يعبر عن مدى ثقّتك في إنجاز أحد المهام:
المقياس: واحد (1) يعني أنك لست واثقاً على الإطلاق؛ تسعة (9) تعني أنك واثق تماماً. تشير الأرقام الموجودة في منتصف المقياس إلى أنك واثق من نفسك بدرجة متوسطة. إذا لم تكن متأكدًا من بند ما، فيرجى تقييمه بأفضل ما يمكنك.

9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

(المقياس 1: غير واثق على الإطلاق؛ الأرقام الوسطى: واثق إلى حد ما، 9- واثق تمامًا)

9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التكيف مع كمية هائلة من المعلومات
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الاستماع والتعلم من الشخص بشأن كيفية العناية به بشكل أفضل
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التخلي عن الأشياء التي لا أستطيع السيطرة عليها
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التعبير عن المشاعر السلبية تجاه المرض
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الإبقاء على الأمل
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	القدرة على ملاحظة "اللحظات الجيدة" في تقديم الرعاية عند حدوثها
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	السماح للشخص بالتعبير عن مشاعره الخاصة
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	مساعدة الشخص في الأنشطة، مثل الطعام أو الغسيل أو ارتداء الملابس أو استخدام المراحيض
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الاستمرار في الاعتناء بنفسك (على سبيل المثال: التمارين، والنظام الغذائي، والنوم)
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التحدث بصراحة وصدق مع الشخص
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الاستمرار في ممارسة الأنشطة الشخصية التي تحب القيام بها
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الحديث عن الموت والاحتضار
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	تقديم الدعم المعنوي لمتلقي الرعاية
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	فهم المعلومات الطبية من الأطباء أو الممرضات أو أي مصادر أخرى
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الرغبة في الحصول على الدعم النفسي
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التعامل مع مشاعر اليأس
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التعامل مع الشخص الذي يعبر عن مشاعر سلبية تجاهك عند حدوثها
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	مساعدة وتشجيع الشخص على المواظبة على جميع العلاجات وتناول جميع الأدوية الموصوفة
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	طرح الأسئلة على الأطباء والممرضات
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	التعامل مع الانتقادات الموجهة من الآخرين
9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	الحفاظ على علاقة وثيقة مع متلقي الرعاية

Appendix E

Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI) Questionnaire in English and Arabic

Instructions: This questionnaire scale asks you about your stress in caregiving. Make sure your ratings reflect what you feel and do. In each case, please rate the question on how you felt or thought a certain way. Circle the number that best fits how often you felt or thought that way.

Caregiver Burden Inventory (CBI)

Instructions: This questionnaire in scale asks you about your stress in care giving. Make sure your ratings reflect what you feel and do. In each case, please rate the question on how you felt or thought a certain way. Circle the number that best fits how often you felt or thought that way.

0= not at all; 1= a little; 2= moderately; 3= much; 4= very much

My care receiver needs my help to perform many daily tasks	0	1	2	3	4
My care receiver is dependent on me	0	1	2	3	4
I have to watch my care receiver constantly	0	1	2	3	4
I have help my care receiver with many basic functions	0	1	2	3	4
I don't have a minute's break from my caregiving chores	0	1	2	3	4
I feel that I'm missing out on life	0	1	2	3	4
I wish I could escape from this situation	0	1	2	3	4
My social life has suffered	0	1	2	3	4
I feel emotionally drained , due to caring for my care receiver	0	1	2	3	4
I expect that things would be different at this point in my life	0	1	2	3	4
I'm not getting enough sleep	0	1	2	3	4
My health has suffered	0	1	2	3	4
Caregiving has made me physically ill	0	1	2	3	4
I'm physically tired	0	1	2	3	4
I don't get along with other family members as well as I used to	0	1	2	3	4
My caregiving efforts aren't appreciated by others in my family	0	1	2	3	4
I've had problems with my marriage	0	1	2	3	4
I don't do as good a job at work as I used to	0	1	2	3	4
I feel resentful of other relatives who could but do not help	0	1	2	3	4
I feel embarrassed by my care receiver's behavior	0	1	2	3	4
I feel ashamed of my care receiver	0	1	2	3	4
I resent my care receiver	0	1	2	3	4
I feel uncomfortable when I have friends over	0	1	2	3	4
I feel angry about my reactions toward my care receiver	0	1	2	3	4

ب. استبيان بشأن أعباء مقدم الرعاية (CBI)

التعليمات: يتضمن هذا الاستبيان بعض الأسئلة على نطاق واسع بشأن الضغوطات التي تواجهها أثناء تقديم الرعاية. تأكد من أن تقييماتك تعكس ما تشعر به وما تفعله. يرجى تقييم السؤال في كل حالة بشأن شعورك أو تفكيرك بطريقة معينة. ضع دائرة حول الرقم الذي يناسب عدد المرات التي شعرت فيها أو فكرت بها بهذه الطريقة.
0 = لا على الإطلاق؛ 1 = قليل؛ 2 = معتدل؛ 3 = كثير؛ 4 = كثير جداً

4	3	2	1	0	يحتاج متلقي الرعاية إلى مساعدتي لأداء العديد من المهام اليومية
4	3	2	1	0	يعتمد متلقي الرعاية علي
4	3	2	1	0	لا بد لي من مراقبة متلقي الرعاية باستمرار
4	3	2	1	0	لقد ساعدت متلقي الرعاية في العديد من المهام الأساسية
4	3	2	1	0	لا أستريح مطلقاً من مهامي في تقديم الرعاية
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر أنني محروم من الحياة
4	3	2	1	0	أود لو أتمكن من الهروب من هذا الوضع
4	3	2	1	0	لقد عانيت على مستوى حياتي الاجتماعية
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر بالاستنزاف العاطفي بسبب الرعاية
4	3	2	1	0	أتوقع أن تكون الأمور مختلفة في هذه المرحلة من حياتي
4	3	2	1	0	لا أحصل على قسط كافٍ من النوم
4	3	2	1	0	لقد تأثرت صحتي
4	3	2	1	0	لقد أصابني تقديم الرعاية بمرض جسدي
4	3	2	1	0	إنني متعب جسدياً
4	3	2	1	0	لا اختلط بأفراد الأسرة الآخرين كما اعتدت
4	3	2	1	0	لا تحظى جهودي في تقديم الرعاية بالتقدير من الآخرين في عائلتي
4	3	2	1	0	لقد واجهت مشاكل في حياتي الزوجية () أعزب
4	3	2	1	0	لا أؤدي عملي جيداً كما اعتدت
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر بالاستياء من أقاربي الآخرين الذين يمكنهم المساعدة ولكنهم لا يفعلون ذلك.
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر بالحرع من سلوك متلقي الرعاية
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر بالخجل من متلقي الرعاية
4	3	2	1	0	مستاء من متلقي الرعاية
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر بعدم الارتياح عند استقبال أصدقائي
4	3	2	1	0	أشعر بالغضب حيال ردود أفعالي تجاه متلقي الرعاية

Appendix F

Barthel Index Questionnaire In English and Arabic

This questionnaire in scale will ask you about your care recipient's capability of daily activities. Circle the number that best describes your care recipient's daily living activities.

Title: “Self-efficacy and Caregiver Burden of Informal Caregiver of Terminally ill patients in Tertiary Hospital in United Arab Emirates”.

C. BARTHEL INDEX

Instructions: This questionnaire will asks you about the capability of daily activities of the person you take care. Circle the number that best describe the activities of daily living of your care recipient.

FEEDING 0 = unable 5 = needs help 10 = independent
BATHING 0 = unable 4 = independent
GROOMING/ Personal care 0 = Unable 5 = independent
DRESSING 0 = unable 5 = needs help 10 = independent
BOWELS 0 = NO control/ incontinent (or needs to be given enemas) 5 = Partial control / occasional accident 10 = Full control/ continent
BLADDER 0 = NO control/ incontinent, or catheterized and unable to manage alone 5 = Partial control/ occasional accident 10 = Full control/ continent
TOILET USE 0 = unable 5 = needs some help 10 = independent
TRANSFERS (BED TO CHAIR AND BACK) 0 = unable, no sitting balance 5 = major help (one or two people assistance; needs physical help), can sit 10 = minor help (needs verbal or physical help) 15 = independent
MOBILITY (ON LEVEL SURFACES) 0 = immobile or less 50 yards 5 = wheelchair independent, greater 50 yards 10 = walks with help of one person, greater 50 yards 15 = independent (but may use any aid; for example, stick) greater 50 yards
STAIRS 0 = unable 5 = needs help (verbal, physical, carrying aid) 10 = independent
TOTAL (0–100): _____

ج. مقياس بارثل

يتناول هذا الاستبيان بعض الأسئلة بشأن إمكانية ممارسة الأنشطة اليومية لمتلقي الرعاية. ضع دائرة حول الرقم الذي يصف بشكل أفضل أنشطة الحياة اليومية لمتلقي الرعاية.

تناول الطعام	0 = غير قادر
	5 = يحتاج إلى مساعدة
	10 = يمكنه بمفرده
الاستحمام	0 = غير قادر
	4 = يمكنه بمفرده
التزين / العناية الشخصية	0 = غير قادر
	5 = يمكنه بمفرده
ارتداء الملابس	0 = غير قادر
	5 = يحتاج إلى مساعدة
	10 = يمكنه بمفرده
الإخراج (حركة الأمعاء)	0 = غير قادر على السيطرة / مصاب بالسلس (أو يحتاج إلى حقن شرجية)
	5 = السيطرة الجزئية / الحوادث العرضية
	10 = سيطرة كاملة / لا يعاني من السلس
التبول	0 = غير قادر على التحكم بالبول / مصاب بالسلس البولي ، أو يحتاج إلى قسطرة وغير قادر على التعامل مع الأمر بمفرده
	5 = السيطرة الجزئية
	10 = سيطرة كاملة
استخدام المراض	0 = غير قادر
	5 = يحتاج إلى بعض المساعدة
	10 = يمكنه بمفرده
التنقل (السريير إلى الكرسي والعودة)	0 = غير قادر ، لا يمكنه الجلوس
	5 = مساعدة كبيرة (مساعدة شخص أو شخصين؛ يحتاج إلى مساعدة جسدية)، يمكنه الجلوس
	10 = مساعدة بسيطة (يحتاج إلى مساعدة لفظية أو جسدية)
	15 = يمكنه بمفرده
الحركة (على الأسطح المستوية)	0 = لا يمكنه التحرك أو أقل من 50 ياردة
	5 = يمكنه التحرك بمفرده على كرسي متحرك، أكثر 50 ياردة
	10 = يمشي بمساعدة شخص واحد، أكثر من 50 ياردة
	15 = يمكنه بمفرده (ولكن قد يستخدم أي أداة مساعدة؛ على سبيل المثال، عصا) أكثر من 50 ياردة
الدرج	0 = غير قادر
	5 = يحتاج إلى مساعدة (لفظية، جسدية، مساعدة عن طريق الحمل)
	10 = يمكنه بمفرده

المجموع (0-100):

Appendix G

Investigator CV

Shane Duran, BSN, RN, CCRN

Contact number: +1 402-218-6546

Email Address: shane.duran90@yahoo.com

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Course : Master of Arts in Nursing
Date Completed : 2012-present
Name of Institute : University of the Philippines (Open University)
Complete Address : Philippines

Course : Bachelor of Science in Nursing
Date Completed : October, 2005
Name of Institute : Saint Paul University Philippines
Complete Address : Philippines

PROFESSIONAL QUALIFICATION

LICENSES:

- Qualification: USA Nurse License
License Number : 2481847
Expiry Date : October 31, 2024
- Qualification: HAAD
License Number : GN7571

Date Expire: December 01, 2020

- Qualification : Philippine Nurse License

License Number : 0391153

Expiry Date : February 17, 2024

TRAINING/CERTIFICATION:

- Basic Life Support

Expiry Date: July 2025

- Advance Cardiac Life Support

Expiry Date: September 2024

- Critical Care Registered Nurse

Expiry: November 30, 2025

- Rapid Stroke Response Level IV Certification September 21, 2023

- NIHSS certification January 14, 2023

NURSING MEMBERSHIP:

American Association of Critical-Care Nurses – Expiry Date: May 31, 2024

EMPLOYMENT HISTORY SUMMARY		
HOSPITAL	DURATION	AREA
Common Health Initiative Lakeside Omaha, Nebraska, USA	October 17, 2022- present	MS-ICU Bed capacity: 16
Apple Valley Village Health, Minnesota, USA <i>-Transitional care and Rehabilitation center -184 Bed Capacity</i>	December 27, 2021 - September, 2022	Transitional Care Unit Bed capacity: 50

<p>Tawam Hospital, United Arab Emirates</p> <p><i>-Serves as a regional referral center for specialized medical care and a national referral center for oncology services.</i></p> <p><i>- Bed capacity of 461</i></p> <p><i>- JCIA Accredited</i></p> <p><i>- John Hopkins Affiliated</i></p> <p><i>-Government and teaching hospital</i></p>	<p>January 7, 2018- December 18, 2021 (3 years and 11 months)</p>	<p>Medical-Surgical ICU ICU bed capacity: 27</p>
<p>Danat Al Emarat Hospital, United Arab Emirates</p> <p><i>-Specialized hospital for women and children</i></p> <p><i>-150 bed capacity</i></p>	<p>September 22, 2014 -November 30, 2017 (3 years and 2 months)</p>	<p>ICU and Anesthesia Unit</p>
<p>Al Ain Cromwell Hospital, United Arab Emirates</p> <p><i>-Specialized hospital for women and children</i></p> <p><i>- 50 bed capacity</i></p>	<p>May 22, 2011 to August 9, 2014 (3 years and 3 months)</p>	<p>High Dependency Unit/ Post Anesthesia Care Unit</p>
<p>Cardinal Santos Medical Centre, Philippines</p> <p><i>-Tertiary hospital specializing in the fields of Cardiology, Neurosurgery,</i></p>	<p>March 22, 2006 to May 21, 2011 (5 years and 2 months)</p>	<p>Medical-Surgical ICU Post-ICU Ward (Medical Ward)</p>

<p><i>Oncology, and Rehabilitation Medicine - 245 bed capacity</i></p>		
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I. Duration : October 2022 to present

Institution : Common Health Initiatives

Position/Unit : Staff Nurse in ICU

Duties and Responsibilities:

1. Functions as a team member with other staff in the performance of duties.
2. Displays an attitude of courtesy and respect for all residents, families, and staff
3. Must be aware of and adhere to all HIPAA regulations.
4. Prepares, administers, assesses the effectiveness of, and documents medications for each resident in accordance with physician's orders.
5. Manages medications, supplies, and equipment, including ordering, receiving, storing, and disposing of all items in accordance with facility policies and procedures.

II. Duration : December 27, 2021 to September, 2022

Institution : Apple Valley Village Health Care

Position/Unit : Staff Nurse in TCU

Duties and Responsibilities:

1. Displays an attitude of courtesy and respect for all residents, families, and staff.
2. Functions as a team member with other staff in the performance of duties.
3. Must be aware of and adhere to all HIPAA regulations.

4. Prepares, administers, assesses the effectiveness of, and documents medications for each resident in accordance with physician's orders.
5. Manages medications, supplies, and equipment, including ordering, receiving, storing, and disposing of all items in accordance with facility policies and procedures.
6. Identifies changes in resident's conditions and initiates rehabilitative measures.
7. Admits, transfers, and discharges residents according to facility procedure

II. Duration : January 7, 2018 to December 18, 2021

Institution : Tawam Hospital

Position/Unit : Staff Nurse in ICU

Additional Training : Preceptorship

Duties and Responsibilities:

1. Demonstrates a professional commitment to patients and fellow healthcare professionals.
2. Demonstrates sound critical thinking, conflict management, and problem-solving abilities.
3. Responsible for the assessment, planning, implementation, and evaluation of patient care in accordance with the organization's policy and procedures and the unit's scope of service.
4. Utilizes evidence-based practice in the provision of care.
5. Maintaining confidentiality and security of patient, family, and organization information per the confidentiality policy.

III. Duration : September 22, 2014 to November 30, 2017

Institution: Danat Al Emarat Women and Children Hospital, UAE

Position/Unit : Staff Nurse in ICU and Anesthesia

Duties and Responsibilities:

1. Provides education, information, and emotional support to the patient's family and caregivers
2. Records all care information concisely, accurately, and thoroughly, in a timely manner, in the appropriate format, and on the appropriate forms
3. Performs all responsibilities/ duties required by the emergency unit/critical care division as defined in the scope of service to ensure that the unique nature of the client is addressed. This includes, but is not limited to, the age of the client served.
4. Demonstrates titration of IV medications and fluids according to the patient's hemodynamic status.

IV. Duration: May 22, 2011 to August 9, 2014

Institution : Al-Ain Cromwell Hospital, UAE

Position/Unit : Staff Nurse in High Dependency Unit / PACU

Duties and Responsibilities:

1. Performs admission assessment immediately upon admission, in accordance with specific unit standards
2. The plan of care includes a nursing diagnosis statement for each identified problem.
3. Performs all responsibilities/ duties required by the emergency unit/critical care division as defined in the scope of service to ensure that the unique nature of the client is addressed. This includes, but is not limited to, the age of the client served.

4. Demonstrates titration of IV medications and fluids according to the patient's hemodynamic status.
5. Demonstrates care for the patient with continuous cardiac monitoring, including rhythm identification, interpretation, and follow-through with appropriate intervention.
6. Demonstrates care for ventilated patients.
7. Provides education, information, and emotional support to the patient's family and caregivers
8. Records all care information concisely, accurately, and thoroughly, in a timely manner, in the appropriate format, and on the appropriate forms.

V. Duration : March 22, 2006 to May 21, 2011

Institution : Cardinal Santos Medical Center

Position/Unit : Staff Nurse II in ICU
Staff Nurse and ACN in Post-ICU (Medical Ward)

Award : Customer Service

Duties and Responsibilities

1. Assesses and Diagnoses patient and family needs to provide quality care to assigned patients.
2. Develops, discusses, and communicates realistic problem lists (plan care) for each patient, in collaboration with each patient/ family/ significant other, to address all identified needs.
3. Demonstrates the skills and judgment necessary to implement medical plan of care, nursing interventions, and procedures as necessary for the care of the patient

4. Maintain up-to-date and accurate documentation of nursing care provided to ensure information integration for the health care team to ensure quality care.
5. Supports and promotes the organization's Infection Control Program
6. Promotes effective working relations and works effectively as part of a department/unit team inter and intra-departmentally to facilitate the department's/unit's ability to meet its goals and objectives

PERSONAL DETAILS

Date of Birth : February 17, 1984
Nationality : Filipino
Marital status : Married
Religion : Christian

CHARACTER REFERENCE

Maher Husni Adel Abdelkhaleq
Nurse Manager ICU
Tawam Hospital , United Arab Emirates
+971 50 612 3153

Ms. Noreen Healey
Nursing Director
Al-Ain Cromwell Hospital
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Lady Diana Jovellanos, RN, MAN

Area Nurse Manager (GNU and ICU)

Cardinal Santos Medical Center

San Juan, Philippines

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Shane D. Duran

Appendix H

Gantt Chart

Appendix I

Research Expenses

PARTICULARS	AMOUNT
A. <i>MORE</i> 1. <i>Contracted Service</i> 1.1 <i>Professional Services</i> <i>(Translation)</i>	AED 350.00 (P4,4550)
1.2 <i>Wages (Assistant Researcher)</i>	AED 1500.00 (P 19,500)
2. <i>Travel</i>	P100 (P1300.00)
3. <i>Supplies</i>	NA
4. <i>Communication</i>	NA
5. <i>Miscellaneous/Sundries</i>	NA
B. <i>Equipment Overlay (printing and binding, subscription expense) – P2000.00</i>	AED 150.00 (P1950.00)
	TOTAL: AED 1787.00 (P27,200.00)
<i>Overhead Cost (10-15% of the combined Personnel Services and MOOE) 1,150-1725</i>	